

SAPIENZA
Università di Roma
Facoltà di Scienze Matematiche Fisiche e Naturali

DOTTORATO DI RICERCA
IN BIOLOGIA CELLULARE E DELLO SVILUPPO

XXX Ciclo
(A.A. 2016/2017)

SIGNALING OF OLIGOGALACTURONIDES IN IMMUNITY
AGAINST MICROBES AND INSECTS

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1. GLOSSARY

ABA	Abcisic Acid
AGB1	Guanine Nucleotide Binding Protein Subunit- β
BAK1	BRI1-Associated Receptor Kinase 1
BBE-like	Berberine Bridge Enzyme-like
BKK1	BAK1-like 1
BRI1	Brassinosteroid Insensitive 1
CDPK	Calcium-Dependent Protein Kinase
CERK1	Chitin Elicitor Receptor Kinase 1
Col-0	Columbia-0
CW	Cell Wall
CWI	Cell Wall Integrity
CWME	Cell Wall Modifying Enzyme
DAMP	Damage-Associated Molecular Pattern
DM	Methylesterification Degree
EFR	EF-Tu Receptor
EF-Tu	Elongation Factor-Thermo unstable
EIN2	Ethylene Insensitive 2
ET	Ethylene
ETI	Effector-Triggered Immunity
ETS	Effector-Triggered Susceptibility
FLS2	Flagellin Sensing 2
GPA	Green Peach Aphid
GroEx	GroEL-enriched aphid extract
GRP3	Glycine-Rich Protein 3
HG	Homogalacturonan
HGME	HG-Modifying Enzyme
HR	Hypersensitive Response
IAA	Indole-3-Acetic Acid

JA	Jasmonic Acid
LRR	Leucine-Rich Repeat
MAMP	Microbe-Associated Molecular Pattern
MAPK	Mitogen-Activated Protein Kinase
Mp10	<i>Myzus persicae</i> 10
OG	Oligogalacturonide
OGOx	OG oxidase
PAMP	Pathogen-Associated Molecular Pattern
PEPR	Pep1-Receptor
PG	Polygalacturonase
PGIP	Polygalacturonase Inhibiting Protein
PME	Pectin Methylesterase
PMEI	Pectin Methylesterase Inhibitor
PR	Pathogenesis-Related
PRR	Pattern Recognition Receptor
Pst	<i>Pseudomonas syringae</i> pv <i>tomato</i>
PTI	PRR-Triggered Immunity
RLK	Receptor-Like Kinase
RLP	Receptor-Like Protein
ROS	Reactive Oxygen Species
SA	Salicylic Acid
SAR	Systemic Acquired Resistance
SERK	Somatic Embryogenesis Receptor-like Kinase
WAK1	Wall-Associated Kinase 1

2. SUMMARY

Background

Plants are engaged in a continuous co-evolutionary struggle for dominance with their pathogens. The cell wall is a major line of defense in plants that prevents invasion by microbial pathogens. For example, transgenic plants that have been engineered to obtain cell walls with an increased methylesterification degree of pectin are protected against the infections with the necrotrophs *Botrytis cinerea* or *Pectobacterium carotovorum*. Emerging evidence indicates that plant cells harbor sophisticated mechanisms for sensing the alteration of cell wall integrity during biotic stress. For instance, they perceive oligogalacturonides (OGs), a class of damage-associated molecular patterns (DAMPs) derived from the partial hydrolysis of homogalacturonan as a consequence of the cellular damage caused by pathogens or wounding. The immunity triggered by OGs protects plants against microbes, such as *B. cinerea*, *P. carotovorum* and Pst. OGs are perceived by the wall-associated kinase 1 (WAK1), a trans membrane receptor-like kinase (RLK) containing epidermal growth factor-like repeats. The glycine-rich protein 3 (GRP3) forms a complex with WAK1 and negatively regulates OG responses. The perception of OGs also involves the coreceptor BRI1-associated receptor kinase 1 (BAK1) and its closest paralogue BAK1-like 1 (BKK1), which belong to the somatic embryogenesis receptor-like kinase (SERK) gene family that comprises five members. If BAK1 and BKK1 associate with the WAK1 perception complex is not yet known. Several elements have been reported to participate in the OG signaling, including the calcium-dependent protein kinases (CDPKs) CPK5, CPK6 and CPK11, the ethylene-insensitive 2 (EIN2) and the Pep1-receptor 1 (PEPR1) and PEPR2. Moreover, the *Pseudomonas syringae* pv *tomato* (Pst)-derived effector AvrPto has been shown to suppress the OG-triggered immunity. Since AvrPto has been described to target perception complexes and not all OG responses were suppressed by this effector, it has been hypothesized that multiple perception/transduction complexes may be involved in the OG signaling. Moreover, among the responses affected by AvrPto, only a subset was affected by the concomitant loss of BAK1 and BKK1, suggesting that other co-receptors, presumably from the SERK family, may be required for the signaling induced by OGs.

OGs also play a role in growth and development. Indeed, they antagonize auxin responses and hyper accumulation of OGs has deleterious effects on plant growth. A specific Arabidopsis berberine bridge enzyme-like (BBE-like) protein, encoded by the gene *At4g20830*, has been shown to oxidize OGs and, doing so, to inactivate their elicitor activity, in a mechanism that may control the homeostasis of OGs and regulate the growth-defense trade off. However, the role of this enzyme, named OG oxidase 1 (OGOX1), in plant immunity and development has not yet been determined.

Aims

- (i) Evaluate the role of other members of SERK family, i.e. SERK1 and SERK2 (SERK5 contains a mutation in an important amino acid residue which likely abolishes its kinase activity in the commonly used Arabidopsis Columbia-0 ecotype), as well as of the G β protein AGB1 (which is required for defense responses to flg22, elf18 and chitin) in the OG signaling.
- (ii) Investigate the role of cell wall and OGs in plant resistance against the green peach aphid/peach-potato aphid *Myzus persicae*.
- (iii) Evaluate the role of OGOX1 in immunity and development.

Results

Data obtained indicate that SERK2 and AGB1, but not SERK1, play a role in the OG-triggered immunity.

Moreover, OGs induce resistance against *M. persicae*. The aphid effector Mp10 suppresses OG-triggered immunity. GRP3 negatively regulate plant resistance against *M. persicae*. A higher pectin methyl esterification degree correlates with enhanced susceptibility to *M. persicae*.

OGOX1 plays a role in resistance against *B. cinerea* and is required for OG- and wound-induced signaling. Furthermore, OGOX1 is involved in root development.

Conclusions

The SERK family members BAK1, BKK1 and SERK2 regulate OG signaling. For SERK2 this is the first example of involvement in immunity described so far. AGB1 is involved in the response not only to flg22, elf18 and chitin, but also to OGs. OGs play an important role in plant resistance not only against fungi and bacteria, but also against insects. Engineering Arabidopsis to obtain a higher pectin methyl esterification degree led to an increased resistance against *B. cinerea* and *P. carotovorum*, but increases susceptibility to *M. persicae*. OGOX1, by regulating OG homeostasis, appears to be a key element of plant immunity and development.

3. GENERAL INTRODUCTION

3.1 The plant immune system

The battle between plants and microbes is evolutionarily ancient and highly complex. This struggle is often described in terms of an “arms race”. Unlike animals, plants have not evolved an adaptive immunity system, but their ability to fend off microbial infection is based on different layers of defense that can be observed at the level of each cell. Plants respond to pathogen attack through constitutive and inducible mechanisms. Structural barriers or reservoirs of antimicrobial compounds represent performed constitutive defenses against tissue colonization. The frontline of the plant defense system consists of physical and chemical barriers such as the cuticle and the cell wall. If these obstacles are overcome, the pathogen is still confronted by elaborate surveillance system in which molecular sentinels, i.e. receptors, operate to activate resistance responses (Jones and Dangl, 2006).

Most plant pathogenic microorganisms actively penetrate the plant apoplast for access to intracellular nutrients. To gain this access, bacterial and fungal pathogens possess a range of enzymatic and/or physical tools. On the other hand plants respond to attempted penetration by a battery of wall-associated defense reactions. The plants often recognize microbial attacks through a non-self recognition that operates through the perception of conserved microbial molecules or by surveillance of host cellular integrity. The presence of microbes in most cases is detected by surface-exposed trans membrane pattern recognition receptors (PRRs) that respond to specific pathogen/microbe-associated molecular patterns (PAMPs/MAMPs), initiating a series of downstream cellular events commonly indicated as PRR-triggered immunity (PTI). PAMPs are usually molecular components that serve essential function for the fitness or survival of microbes and are often highly conserved and are not present in the host (Zipfel *et al.*, 2006).

In addition to sensing PAMPs, sensing a compromised-self (or altered-self) by detecting damage-associated molecular patterns (DAMPs) such as released plant cell wall or cuticle fragments, and endogenous peptides released by the action of activated proteases, is also a central part of PTI (Boller and Felix, 2009).

Well-known examples of PAMPs are bacterial peptidoglycans, flagellin and Elongation Factor-Thermo unstable (EF-Tu), and the fungal chitin. Instead, well-known examples of DAMPs are oligogalacturonides, i.e. pectin-derived fragments, and the so-called Arabidopsis peptides (AtPeps) (Boller and Felix, 2009). The PRRs involved in PAMP/DAMP ligand binding belong to the receptor-like kinases (RLKs) or receptor-like proteins (RLPs) families, which often are characterized by a leucine-rich repeat (LRR) extracellular domain. RLKs have an intracellular kinase domain while RLPs lack this cytosolic signaling domain, and need other receptor-like cytoplasmic kinases (RLCKs) to establish the PTI (Mazzotta and Kemmerling, 2011). The archetypical and best-characterized plant PRRs are the EF-Tu receptor (EFR), a LRR-RLK that recognizes a 18-aa long peptide derived from EF-Tu, called elf18, and the related flagellin sensing 2 (FLS2) that recognizes a 22-aa long peptide derived from flagellin, called flg22 (Zipfel *et al.*, 2006).

PTI activation leads to a series of early and late responses, whose role is to prevent microbial colonization. The early responses occur within minutes, and consist of rapid ion fluxes across the plasma membrane, an oxidative burst, activation of mitogen-activated protein kinases (MAPKs) and calcium-dependent protein kinases (CDPKs), and transcriptional reprogramming. The late responses occur within hours, and consist in the accumulation of defense-related hormones, i.e. salicylic acid (SA), jasmonic acid (JA) and ethylene (ET), phytoalexins and pathogenesis-related (PR) proteins (Boller and Felix, 2009). Deposition of callose, for example in the papillae, is a later response that occurs within days, representing an important feature of immunity that is thought to reinforce the cell wall at the microbial penetration sites to impede infections (Voigt, 2014). PTI can be classified as (1) chemical defense, e.g., production of reactive oxygen species

(ROS), (2) structural defense, e.g., cross-linking of the cell wall and deposition of callose, (3) signaling, e.g., activation of mitogen-activated protein kinases (MAPK), reprogramming of gene expression, hormone signaling and systemic signaling to activate defense responses in neighboring cells (Dodds and Rathjen, 2010).

PTI is effective against a broad spectrum of microbes, but many successful pathogens, to escape detection, adopt a strategy secreting a range of effector molecules (often proteins) that modulate the PTI components to their advantage, leading to effector-triggered susceptibility (ETS) and higher pathogen colonization. The microbial effectors can in turn be counteracted in the plant by an intracellular surveillance system, acquired during a co-evolutionary arms race, consisting of an array of nucleotide binding-LRR (NB-LRR) proteins that detect the presence of such effectors and enable induction of effector-triggered immunity (ETI). ETI is an accelerated and amplified PTI response, resulting in disease resistance and, usually, a hypersensitive cell death response (HR) at the infection site (Jones and Dangl, 2006). ETI also causes a massive increase, in the infected tissues, of SA, which is systemically translocated via the phloem. Accumulation of SA induces defense responses in distal tissues that are responsible for the development of a systemic acquired resistance (SAR). SA also negatively regulates growth, and for this reason, its production is tightly regulated (Seyfferth and Tsuda, 2014). While SA is mostly involved in mounting defenses against biotrophic pathogens, JA is required against insects and, in combination with ET, against necrotrophic pathogens, with some exceptions (Denancé *et al.*, 2013).

3.2 The plant cell wall structure and composition

One of the main differences between plant and animal cells are the walls surrounding plant cells. The cell wall (CW) is a dynamic and complex structure composed for the majority of polysaccharides, phenolic compounds and highly glycosylated proteins. We can distinguish two different types of CWs, namely primary and secondary CW, which are deposited outside the plasma membrane. The first layer of CW to be deposited is the middle lamella, the outermost layer through which adjacent cells are in contact. At the end of cell division, the two daughter cells lay the next layer, the primary wall. Some specialized cells, during differentiation, lay a further layer, the secondary wall.

Primary CW is a highly extensible structure synthesized during growth and is connected to neighbor cells through the middle lamella. It is relatively thin, pliant, highly hydrated structure. Nevertheless it must be strong to withstand the tensile forces arising from turgor pressure, extensible to allow wall stress relaxation, cell water uptake and physical enlargement of the cell, as well as capable of linking newly deposited wall polymers into the load-bearing structure (Smith, 2001). The secondary CW is deposited at the end of development, during differentiation of some cell types (Cosgrove and Jarvis, 2012), providing high tensile strength and rigidity in plant tissues that have ceased growing. For this reason, secondary walls do not need extensibility (Koch, 2004).

The CWs consist of two main components: a microfibrillar component and a matrix. The relatively stiff cellulose microfibrils are embedded in a hydrated matrix of pectins, hemicellulose, phenolic compounds and structural proteins.

The main CW structural polysaccharide is cellulose, which is deposited by an enzymatic complex, called cellulose synthase, on the plasma membrane. Cellulose consists of a repetition of two units of D-glucopiranosose bound by β -1,4 linkages and twisted by 180°. Cellulose aggregates in microfibrils connected through hydrogen bonds with hemicelluloses, forming a network embedded in a matrix of pectin. Hemicelluloses are heterogeneous and branched polysaccharides, comprising xyloglucans (XyGs), xylans, mannans and glucomannans (Scheller and Ulvskov, 2010).

Primary CWs and middle lamellas are rich in pectins, a heterogeneous group of polysaccharides consisting of rhamnogalacturonan I and II (RG-I and RG-II), homogalacturonan (HG) and xylogalacturonan (XGA). RG-I has a backbone composed of galactose and rhamnose residues and lateral branches of galactan and arabinan that vary among cell types and developmental stages. RG-II has a linear backbone of galacturonic residues and side branches comprising 12 different types of sugars. HG is the simplest polymer consisting of a linear chain of galacturonic acid bound by a α -1,4 linkage, which can either be methyl esterified at the C-6 carboxyl (typically 80%) (Wolf *et al.*, 2009) or carry acetyl groups at O2 or O3 (Wolf and Greiner, 2012; Gou *et al.*, 2012a). Lastly, XGA is essentially a linear chain of HG that can be substituted by xylose. HG is synthesized from nucleotide sugars in the Golgi apparatus, and then secreted in a fully methylesterified form into the cell wall where its structure can be modified by the activity of cell wall enzymes, referred to as HG-modifying enzymes (HGMEs). In particular, HGs can be modified by pectin methylesterases (PMEs), whose activity is regulated by endogenous PMEIs (pectin methylesterase inhibitors) and which control the degree of methylesterification (DM) of HGs (Pelloux *et al.*, 2007; Wolf *et al.*, 2009). Pectin acetylerases (PAEs) play a similar role by hydrolyzing the O-acetylated bonds. Overall, the partially demethylesterified HGs can either form Ca^{2+} bonds, which promote the development of the so-called ‘egg box’ structures that underlie the formation of pectin gels, or become a target for pectin-degrading enzymes such as polygalacturonases (endo-PGs and exo-PGs) and pectate lyases-like (PLLs), including pectate lyases (endo-PLs and exo-PLs) and pectin lyases (endo-PNLs). In either case, the demethylesterification of HGs has dramatic consequences on the rheological properties of the cell wall (Peaucelle *et al.*, 2011a; Peaucelle *et al.*, 2011b) and is predicted to affect cell growth. In addition, the hydrolysis of partially demethylesterified HGs can release oligogalacturonides (OGs) with a signaling function, for instance during plant-pathogen interactions (Lionetti *et al.*, 2007; Osorio *et al.*, 2008) or in modulating growth by inhibiting auxin-induced processes such as stem elongation, rhizogenesis, and flower and stomata formation (Ridley *et al.*, 2001; Falasca *et al.*, 2008; Camejo *et al.*, 2011); see sections 1.4, 1.5 and 1.6 for a detailed description of OG structure, function and signaling.

Phenolic compounds are generally abundant in the secondary CW, sometimes present also in the primary CW and in the middle lamella. An important CW phenolic compound is lignin, a complex polymer produced by the quasi-random condensation of three hydroxycinnamyl alcohols, i.e. p-coumaryl, coniferyl and sinapyl alcohol (Rencoret *et al.*, 2011). Lignin deposition makes the CW more rigid, impermeable to water and resistant to enzymatic hydrolysis, and is particularly important for xylem functionality, since xylematic vessels need to transport water without collapsing as a consequence of the highly negative pressure. Lignin is also important for defense against pathogens, and is often deposited in the CW in response to infection.

Among CW structural elements, proteins, even if present in lower amounts, play important functions (Keller, 1993). They are divided into hydroxyproline- and proline-rich proteins (HRPGs and PRPs), glycin-rich proteins (GRP), arabinogalactan proteins (AGPs) and lectins (Rumyantseva, 2005). HRPGs, like extensins, generate scaffolding networks able to interact with pectins (Lamport *et al.*, 2011) and may contribute to stiffen the CW through intra- or inter-crosslinks mediated by specific peroxidase, called extensin peroxidase (Everdeen *et al.*, 1988). AGPs are highly glycosylated hydroxyproline-containing proteins, involved in vegetative growth and reproduction (Rumyantseva, 2005), which may directly bind to CW polymers. GRPs are exported from neighboring xylem parenchyma cells to the protoxylem wall, a rare example of protein transport between cells in plants, and were proposed be part of a repair system of the plant during the stretching phase of protoxylem (Ringli *et al.*, 2001).

3.3 Cell wall represents a physical barrier and a surveillance system against pathogen attacks

The CW is involved in many cellular functions. Besides providing structural support during growth and development, functional specialization of cell types, and cell-to-cell communication, CW represents an impenetrable physical barrier with constitutive rigidity to fend off bioaggressor attacks as well as abiotic factors (Vorwerk *et al.*, 2004; Vallarino and Osorio, 2012). CWs are able to perform these functions because their composition and fine structure are modified in response to different type of stimuli originating in the environment or deriving from the plant itself. Indeed, plants themselves express a broad variety of cell wall modifying enzymes (CWMEs) in the apoplast to maintain proper wall plasticity and flexibility and to assist in wall remodeling and degradation during growth and development as well as during defense responses. In addition, CWMEs produced by microorganisms during host invasion cause cell wall modifications that can initiate plant defense responses.

A major structural role of defense against external stimuli is certainly played by HG and HGMEs. Indeed, A high DM of HG has been correlated to genotype resistance to the aphid *Schizaphis graminum*, the biotrophic fungus *Colletotrichum lindemuthianum*, and the necrotrophic bacterium *Ralstonia solanacearum* (Boudart *et al.*, 1998; Wydra and Berl, 2006; Senechal *et al.*, 2014). This could be related to changes in CW elasticity and mechanics. As shown during organ initiation (Peaucelle *et al.*, 2011a), the lowest wall elasticity is correlated to the highest DM. Furthermore, a high constitutive DM of pectin was structurally related to the borate-RGII cross-link in regulating cell wall stiffness (Ishii and Matsunaga, 2001). As such, plant resistance to the necrotrophic bacterium *Pectobacterium carotovorum* is associated with a high DM of pectin in wild potato plants (McMillan *et al.*, 1993; Marty *et al.*, 1997) and in the *pme3* mutant of *A. thaliana* (Raiola *et al.*, 2011). The enhanced DM level obtained by mutation of PME genes or by overexpression of PMEI genes *in planta* increased the resistance of dicotyledonous and monocotyledonous species to biotrophic or necrotrophic pathogens, but not to the full range of pathogens for each plant (Lionetti *et al.*, 2007; An *et al.*, 2008; Raiola *et al.*, 2011; Volpi *et al.*, 2011). Furthermore, *in vitro*, the hydrolysis of plant pectin by endo-PGs from several necrotrophic pathogens is decreased when pectins of high DM are used as carbon sources (Bonnin *et al.*, 2002). The resistance observed could therefore be related to a decrease in the number of specific substrates for endogenous PGs, as well as the physical or chemical properties of pectins. Nevertheless, enhancing resistance through the modulation of the DM of HG is unlikely to be an easy strategy, as it appears to be pathogen specific. For instance, increased PME activity and the associated lower DM of pectins, in transgenic strawberry overexpressing one PME, enhanced fruit resistance to the necrotrophic fungus *B. cinerea* (Osorio *et al.*, 2008). Understanding this opposite effect is complex as PME activity on HG can have two distinct consequences. On one hand, the linear activity of PME can give rise to blocks of free carboxyl groups that non-covalently interact with Ca^{2+} ions, conferring a gel-like structure and cell wall strengthening (Morris *et al.*, 1982; Micheli, 2001). On the other hand, random PME activity promotes the action of pectin depolymerases (endo-PG or lyase activities) increasing both cell wall loosening and porosity and producing OGs (see below) that elicit plant defense responses (Baron-Epel *et al.*, 1988). Thus, in transgenic plants with modified HGME activity, either the direct or the indirect effect on HG structure could play a role in plant resistance.

Emerging evidences indicate that plant cells exploit sophisticated mechanisms of sensing the alteration of cell wall integrity (CWI) during biotic and abiotic stresses. For instance, they perceive endogenous stimuli such as pectin fragments oligogalacturonides (see below), cellulose-derived oligomers, metabolites, and peptides (Ferrari *et al.*, 2013; Souza *et al.*, 2017), released as consequence of pathogen invasion attempts, which can initiate specific defense responses. Indeed, the CW is strictly connected to the plasma membrane and the cytoskeleton (Humphrey *et al.*, 2007) and a dedicated system constantly monitors its integrity and transduces any change to trigger downstream responses (Hamann, 2015). The existence of a mechanism that perceives wall

alterations was firstly observed in *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*. The plant CWI maintenance system is poorly understood, but it is likely that in plants, as in yeast, it involves perception of osmotic and damage stresses (Hamann and Denness, 2011). This CWI maintenance mechanism appears to modulate physiological growth and to regulate responses to stresses. To date, the proposed sensors for CWI are putative kinase receptors, non-kinase proteins, and ion channels that can physically link the CW to the plasma membrane and the cytoskeleton (Humphrey *et al.*, 2007; Wolf *et al.*, 2012).

Among the proposed CWI receptors, Wall Associated Kinases (WAKs) are RLKs with an extracellular domain that contains Epidermal Growth Factor (EGF)-like repeats that have been reported to directly bind the CW pectins through (Decreux and Messiaen, 2005), thereby linking the cytoplasm to the extracellular matrix. Moreover, AtGRP3 regulates AtWAK1 function through binding to the cell wall domain of AtWAK1 and the interaction of AtWAK1 with AtGRP3 occurs in a pathogenesis-related process *in planta* (Park *et al.*, 2001). Damage of CW components may release CW fragments allowing their binding to specific proteins. This highlights the hypothesis that the CWI maintenance mechanism could form an essential component of plant immunity such as responses to DAMPs.

3.4 Oligogalacturonides: a class of DAMPs and regulators of growth and development

Oligogalacturonides (OGs) are linear molecules of two to about twenty residues of α -1,4-galactopyranosyluronic acid (GalA), the main component of pectin. OGs represent the first plant oligosaccharins, i.e. biologically active carbohydrates that act as signal molecules, to be discovered (Hahn *et al.*, 1981; Bishop *et al.*, 1981). Biological responses to OGs occur in at least five of the six subclasses of dicotyledonous plants Magnoliidae, Hamamelidae, Asteridae, Rosidae, Dilleniidae (Reymond *et al.*, 1996; Cote and Hahn, 1994), in a monocot (Moerschbacher *et al.*, 1999) and a gymnosperm (Asiegbu *et al.*, 1994). A number of different biological responses to OGs have been reported, and the particular response observed depends on the plant species, the bioassay, and the chemical structure of the OG used (Cote *et al.*, 1998). A spectrum of modified and unmodified OGs of various lengths is active in different systems (Cote and Hahn, 1994). The biological responses of plants to OGs can be divided into two broad categories: plant defense and plant growth and development (Cote and Hahn, 1994).

Pathogens enter plant tissues in at least three ways: digesting cell walls, entering through wounds, and invading through natural openings such as stomata. Pectins are one of the first targets of digestion by invading pathogens (Pagel and Heitefuss, 1990). OGs are released upon fragmentation of homogalacturonan (HG) from the plant primary cell wall (Cote *et al.*, 1998) by pathogen-secreted cell wall-degrading enzymes (CWDEs) or by wound-induced plant CDWEs (Savatin *et al.*, 2014b; Cervone *et al.*, 2015). When the activity of a fungal polygalacturonase (PG) is modulated by apoplastic PG-inhibiting proteins (PGIPs), long-chain oligogalacturonides are produced (De Lorenzo *et al.*, 2001; De Lorenzo and Ferrari, 2002). Indeed, PGs are not elicitors per se, but are rather able to release elicitor-active molecules from the host cell wall. The OGs released are a carbon source for the pathogens, but can also be detected by plants as signals to initiate defense responses. OGs cannot be considered true PAMPs, since they are not derived from the pathogen. However, they are considered the classic examples of DAMPs that are generated by the host cell during the infection process.

Chemically pure OGs can act as endogenous elicitors (Galletti *et al.*, 2009), inducing a variety of defense responses, including accumulation of phytoalexins (Davis *et al.*, 1986), glucanase and chitinase (Davis and Hahlbrock, 1987; Broekaert and Pneumas, 1988). Exogenously added OGs inhibit the light-induced opening of stomata in tomato and *Commelina communis* L. leaves (Lee

et al., 1999). Stomatal openings provide access to inner leaf tissues required by many plant pathogens (Agrios, 1997), suggesting that the constriction of stomatal apertures is beneficial for plant defense. One of the first responses observed after the addition of OGs that is clearly involved in plant defense is the production of active oxygen species, including H_2O_2 , and O_2^- (Low and Merida, 1996). This oxidative burst occurs within a few minutes after the addition of OGs to suspension-cultured soybean (Legendre *et al.*, 1993), tobacco (Rout-Mayer *et al.*, 1997; Binet *et al.*, 1998) and tomato (Stennis *et al.*, 1998) cells, Arabidopsis seedlings and leaf discs (Galletti *et al.*, 2008; Bisceglia N.G. *et al.*, 2015). Moreover, OGs induce a transient cytosolic Ca^{2+} mobilization, cytosolic acidification, and plasma membrane depolarization accompanied by an induction of PAL mRNA and enzyme activity in carrot cells (Messiaen and Van Cutsem, 1994).

Several OG-regulated proteins in the Arabidopsis apoplast and nucleus have been identified by 2-D DIGE (Casasoli *et al.*, 2007; Casasoli *et al.*, 2008), many of them present in multiple isoforms likely due to post-translational modifications (PTMs). More recently, a large-scale phosphoproteome analysis of early OG-signaling enabled to determine 100 regulated phosphosites using LC-MS/MS and 46 differential spots corresponding to 34 phosphoproteins using phospho-DIGE (Mattei *et al.*, 2016). Functional classification showed that the OG-responsive phosphoproteins include kinases, phosphatases and receptor-like kinases, heat shock proteins, reactive oxygen species (ROS) scavenging enzymes, proteins related to cellular trafficking, transport, defense and signaling as well as novel candidates for a role in immunity, for which elicitor-induced phosphorylation changes have not been shown before (Mattei *et al.*, 2016).

Arabidopsis full-genome expression analysis reveals that OGs influence the expression of ~2000 genes (Ferrari *et al.*, 2007). Some of these, such as *AtWRKY40* (*At1g80840*), encoding a transcription factor that acts as a negative regulator of basal defense (Xu *et al.*, 2006), *CYP81F2* (*At5g57220*), encoding a cytochrome P450 monooxygenase that is essential for the pathogen-induced accumulation of 4-methoxyindol-3-ylmethylglucosinolate (Bednarek *et al.*, 2009), and *Ret-Ox* (*At1g26380*), encoding a protein with homology to reticuline oxidases, i.e. a class of enzymes involved in secondary metabolism and in defense against pathogens (Dittrich and Kutchan, 1991), are rapidly and strongly up-regulated upon exposure to OGs.

Exogenous treatment with OGs protects grapevine (*Vitis vinifera*) and Arabidopsis leaves against infection with the necrotrophic fungus *Botrytis cinerea* (Aziz *et al.*, 2004; Ferrari *et al.*, 2007), suggesting that production of this elicitor at the site of infection, where large amounts of PGs are secreted by the fungus, may contribute to activate defenses responses. A variety of plant defense responses against microbial pathogens are regulated by the signaling molecules SA, JA and ET. Resistance to *B. cinerea* induced in Arabidopsis by OGs is dependent on ET (Gravino *et al.*, 2015), and requires *PHYTOALEXIN DEFICIENT 3* (*PAD3*) (Ferrari *et al.*, 2007), a gene involved in the metabolism of Trp-derived secondary compounds (Zhou *et al.*, 1999).

OGs play a role also in growth and development of plant tissues (Cote and Hahn, 1994). Indeed, they are active in the tobacco thin-cell layer (TCL) (Tran Thanh Van *et al.*, 1985; Mohnen *et al.*, 1990), and the tobacco leaf explant bioassays (Bellincampi *et al.*, 1993). When biologically active OGs are added to media containing specific phytohormone concentrations, TCLs that would normally form few or no organs form flowers, while TCLs that normally form roots form significantly fewer roots (Eberhard *et al.*, 1989). Biologically active OGs inhibit root formation (Bellincampi *et al.*, 1993) and increase stomata formation (Altamura *et al.*, 1998b) on tobacco leaf explants incubated in media with specific phytohormone concentrations. OGs have been shown to induce ethylene production in the fruits of tomato (Brecht and Huber, 1988; Campbell and Labavitch, 1991a), pear (Campbell and Labavitch, 1991b) and citrus (Baldwin and Biggs, 1988). Pectic fragments that elicit ethylene production have been extracted from tomato fruit at the breaker stage of ripeness. This suggests that OGs, presumably released by PGs, could be involved in initiating the ripening process (Melotto *et al.*, 1994), since exogenous ethylene

initiates the ripening process and the production of ethylene is required for ripening (Theologis *et al.*, 1993). The role of OGs in fruit ripening, however, seems to be complex and is not understood. Indeed, tomato fruits expressing antisense PGs mRNA exhibited a 99% reduction in PGs activity and a substantial reduction in pectin depolymerization, but were unaffected in their ethylene production and overall ripening (Smith *et al.*, 1990). Moreover, the increase in ethylene production during ripening is detected prior to the increase in PGs production, and elevated ethylene levels can induce the accumulation of PGs mRNA (Sitrit and Bennett, 1998). The addition of trigalacturonide to ripening tomato fruit tissue inhibits the increase in PGs mRNA and enzyme activity, as well as fruit ripening (Ben-Arie *et al.*, 1995). These data indicate that although OGs are involved in tomato fruit ripening, their role in the process is not clear.

In every case reported to date where OGs regulate the growth and development of plant tissues, with the exception of fruit ripening, their effect is the opposite of the effect of added auxin (Altamura *et al.*, 1998a; Branca *et al.*, 1988; Eberhard *et al.*, 1989). Accordingly, OGs inhibit the auxin-induced pea stem elongation (Branca *et al.*, 1988), as well as the auxin-induced expression of the plant oncogene *rolB* (Bellincampi *et al.*, 1996), and the auxin-induced division of phloem parenchyma cells (Altamura *et al.*, 1998b) in tobacco leaf disc explants. The OG-induced H₂O₂ production does not appear to have a role in the signaling pathway leading to the inhibition of *rolB* expression (Bellincampi *et al.*, 2000). Recently it was shown that OGs antagonize responses to auxin also in *Arabidopsis* (Savatin *et al.*, 2011). The mechanism by which OGs act in opposition to the action of auxin is presently unknown.

3.5 The structural requirements for the biological activity of oligogalacturonides

Many studies using mixtures of different sizes of OG oligomers reveal little about the OG structure that is required for biological activity. Homogeneous, size-fractionated OGs are relatively easy to prepare, and have been used in some studies (Spiro *et al.*, 1993). Most biological responses have been attributed to OGs with a degree of polymerization (DP) from 10 to 16, with the most active sizes being around DP 12 (Spiro *et al.*, 1993). These responses include: the induction of phytoalexins in soybean (Davis *et al.*, 1986) the induction of casbene synthetase in castor bean (Jin and West, 1984), the induction of PAL in suspension-cultured carrot cells (Messiaen and Van Cutsem, 1994), the induction of *rolB* expression in tobacco leaf explants (Bellincampi *et al.*, 1993), the induction of Ca²⁺ influx in suspension-cultured tobacco cells (Mathieu *et al.*, 1991), and the regulation of organogenesis in tobacco TCL and leaf explants (Marfà *et al.*, 1991; Bellincampi *et al.*, 1993). The same size range of OGs (i.e. DP 10-16) having a GalA or a Δ-4,5 unsaturated GalA residue at the non-reducing terminus induce the production of phytoalexins in soybean cotyledons, indicating that 4,5-unsaturation of the non-reducing terminal GalA does not greatly influence the biological activity of the OGAs (Hahn *et al.*, 1981; Davis *et al.*, 1986). In contrast, modifications of the reducing terminus including biotinylation, tyramination, C1 reduction, and C1 oxidation decrease the biological activity of OGs 2–6 fold in the tobacco TCL bioassay and 2–32 fold in suspension-cultured tobacco cell extracellular alkalization bioassays (Spiro *et al.*, 1998). Chemical esterification of the C6 carboxylates of OGs greatly diminishes their ability to elicit casbene synthetase in castor bean, whereas subsequent de-esterification restores their biological activity (Jin and West, 1984). This shows that, at least in the case of induction of casbene synthetase, free carboxylates are necessary for activity. The minimum size of OGs required for most of the biological activities reported, and the minimum size requirement for the formation of a Ca²⁺-dependent conformation often called the “egg-box” conformation, coincide at a DP of approximately 10 (Kohn, 1975; Messiaen and Van Cutsem, 1994; Cote and Hahn, 1994). Millimolar [Ca²⁺] is required for biological activity of OGs in carrot and tobacco cell suspensions (Messiaen and Van Cutsem, 1994) which suggests that a Ca²⁺-dependent conformation formed by OGs with DPs 5-10 is required for biological activity in

certain bioassays (Cote and Hahn, 1994). The polyamines spermidine and spermine are believed to selectively prevent OGs from adopting the Ca^{2+} -dependent conformation (Messiaen and Van Cutsem, 1999). Physiological concentrations of these polyamines inhibit the biological activity of OGs in carrot cell suspensions, suggesting that they modulate the biological activity of OGs by preventing the Ca^{2+} -dependent formation of an active conformation (Messiaen and Van Cutsem, 1999). There are several reports showing that OGs other than those with DPs from 10 to 16 are biologically active (Cote and Hahn, 1994). For example, OGs from DP 2 to 30 elicit the expression of proteinase inhibitors (PIs) in tomato seedlings, with the disaccharide being the most active (Farmer *et al.*, 1990; Moloshok *et al.*, 1992). In this system, di- and tri-GalA with Δ -4,5 unsaturated GalA at the non-reducing terminus are active, whereas C1 reduced oligomers are not. OGs with a DP from two to six induce ethylene biosynthesis in tomato plants, with the pentasaccharide being the most active (Simpson *et al.*, 1998). Trigalacturonide is active in inhibiting the production of PGs in ripening tomato fruit tissue. Di- and tri- GalA elicit the accumulation of HGRPs in the cell walls of bean seedlings (Boudart *et al.*, 1995). Di- and tri-GalA also suppress the induction of PAL and the hypersensitive response to a fungal pathogen in wheat leaves (Moerschbacher *et al.*, 1999). Nonreducing-end Δ -4,5 unsaturated di-GalA is active in inhibiting tissue maceration in potato tuber tissue infected with the bacterial soft rot pathogen *Erwinia carotovora* (Weber *et al.*, 1996). The transcriptomic data from trimer-treated Arabidopsis seedlings indicate a clear activation of genes involved in defense signaling, phytohormone signaling and a down-regulation of genes involved in processes related to growth regulation and development (Davidsson *et al.*, 2017). Furthermore, treatment with trimers in Arabidopsis improves resistance to the necrotrophic pathogen *P. carotovorum*, induces seedlings growth inhibition, MPK3 and MPK6 phosphorylation, but not ROS production (Davidsson *et al.*, 2017).

3.6 The oligogalacturonide signaling pathway

Although their eliciting activity is well documented, the perception system for OGs has been elusive. The wall-associated kinases (WAK) gene family represents another group of RLKs and comprises five tightly clustered members (WAK1-WAK5) in Arabidopsis. These receptors contain epidermal growth factor (EGF)-like motifs in the extracellular domain. Interestingly, it was shown that the extracellular domain of WAK1 and WAK2 has high affinity to pectin and OGs, *in vitro* (Decreux *et al.*, 2006; Cabrera *et al.*, 2008; Kohorn *et al.*, 2009). This finding opened the prospect that WAK1 or its homologs might be part of the perception system for OGs. Indeed a recent work reveals through a domain swap approach a role of the WAK1 protein as a receptor of OGs (Brutus *et al.*, 2010). Authors firstly, through a test-of-concept study, demonstrated the possibility of obtaining functional plant chimeric receptors and devise an appropriate design for their construction. Specifically, it was analyzed the amenability of the Arabidopsis EFR, an LRR-RLK for recognition of the MAMP EF-Tu and its derived peptide elf18 as a recipient protein structure. EFR was chosen because it is functional when expressed in Nicotiana species (Zipfel *et al.*, 2004), unlike the Arabidopsis FLS2, i.e. the receptor for flagellin and its derived peptide flg22 (Robatzek *et al.*, 2007). Next, they obtained chimeras between EFR and Arabidopsis WAK1 and demonstrated that a chimeric receptor comprising the WAK ectodomain fused with the EFR trans membrane (TM) and intracellular kinase domains is able to perceive OGs and induce typical EFR-mediated responses, such as ethylene production and defense gene expression (Brutus *et al.*, 2010), providing the first evidence that WAK1 is capable to sense OGs *in vivo* and trigger a defense response that mirrors that normally activated by OGs. Similarly, a chimeric receptor comprising the TM and cytoplasmic kinase domains of WAK1 fused with the ectodomain of EFR was able to perceive elf18, triggering an oxidative burst in the *efr* Arabidopsis mutant that lacks EFR (Brutus *et al.*, 2010). Accordingly, the overexpression of

WAK1 led to enhanced H₂O₂ production and callose deposition induced by OGs in Arabidopsis leaves (Gramegna *et al.*, 2016).

In Arabidopsis, WAK1 has been described to form a complex with a cytoplasmic plasma membrane-localized kinase-associated protein phosphatase (KAPP) and a glycine-rich protein (GRP-3) (Park *et al.*, 2001; Anderson *et al.*, 2001) that were found localized mainly in the cell wall and, in a small part, on the plasma membrane (Gramegna *et al.*, 2016). Both GRP-3 and KAPP have been found to negatively regulate OG responses. Indeed, the lack of GRP-3 or KAPP results in increased OG-induced H₂O₂ production, callose deposition and defense genes expression in Arabidopsis (Gramegna *et al.*, 2016). Interestingly, WAK1, GRP-3 and KAPP also affect the local response to wounding and the basal resistance against *B. cinerea*. Indeed, the overexpression of WAK1, as well as the lack of GRP-3 or KAPP enhance Arabidopsis resistance to *B. cinerea* and H₂O₂ production in response to wounding (Gramegna *et al.*, 2016), corroborating the vision that OGs play an important role in the plant response to these stresses.

The signaling pathways mediated by RLKs and RLPs early converge at a small group of RLKs, somatic embryogenesis receptor kinases (SERKs), via ligand-induced heterodimerization and transphosphorylation (Ma *et al.*, 2016). SERKs were initially described as embryogenic markers in carrot cell suspension cultures (Schmidt *et al.*, 1997), hence the name. One of the five SERK proteins in Arabidopsis, SERK3, also known as brassinosteroid insensitive 1 (BRI1)-associated receptor kinase 1 (BAK1), was early on shown to be a positive regulator of the brassinosteroid growth signaling pathway (Li *et al.*, 2002; Nam and Li, 2002). BAK1 controls diverse aspects of plant development and, at the same time, forms an integral part of the plant immune system. Regarding immunity, BAK1 is required for response to necrosis- and ethylene-inducing peptide 1 (nep1)-like protein 20 (nlp20) (Albert *et al.*, 2015), a conserved MAMP from bacteria, oomycetes, and fungi, and to the effector proteins Avr4 or Avr9 from *Cladosporium fulvum* (Postma *et al.*, 2016), and, together with its closest paralogue BAK1-LIKE1/SERK4 (BKK1/SERK4), mediates responses to the bacterial MAMPs flg22 and elf18, and to the Arabidopsis peptide DAMP AtPep1 (Roux *et al.*, 2011). On the contrary, BAK1 is dispensable for responses to the fungal chitin and the necrosis-inducing Phytophthora protein 1 (NPP1) (Shan *et al.*, 2008). Recently, it has been shown that BAK1 and BKK1 have a redundant role in the response to OGs and to affect Arabidopsis susceptibility to *B. cinerea* (Gravino *et al.*, 2017). Intriguingly, the concomitant loss of BAK1 and BKK1 in Arabidopsis affects the OG-induced ROS production, callose deposition, protection against *B. cinerea*, upregulation of the defense genes *FRK1*, *PDF1.2* and *PR1*, but does not influence the OG-induced MAPK activation, upregulation of the defense genes *PHI1*, *RET-OX*, *CYP81F2*, *PAD3*, *PGIP1*, and the inhibition of the auxin response (Gravino *et al.*, 2017), suggesting that different types of perception/transduction complexes mediate OG signaling or that other SERK elements may be required for the OG-induced BAK1/BKK1-independent responses. Whether BAK1, BKK1 or other SERKs interact with WAK1 is not yet known and, in general, none of the five WAK family members has been identified to date among the interactors of BAK1 (Halter *et al.*, 2014).

Upon ligand binding and subsequent pattern recognition receptor (PRR) complex activation, a branched signaling cascade is initiated within minutes. The OG-induced activation of pathways leading to plant defenses has been shown to be mediated by cytosolic Ca²⁺ increase (Navazio *et al.*, 2002; Moscatiello *et al.*, 2006; Manzoor *et al.*, 2013). Plasma membrane Ca²⁺ permeable channels, particularly cyclic nucleotide gated channels (CNGC) and ionotropic glutamate receptors homologs (GLRs) are potential candidates to mediate Ca²⁺ influx (Lacombe *et al.*, 2001; Maser *et al.*, 2001). Indeed, the OG-induced cytosolic Ca²⁺ increase, ROS and NO production, and defense gene expression were reduced by the loss of Arabidopsis clade 3 GLRs or in the presence of widely used GLRs antagonists in wild-type plants (Manzoor *et al.*, 2013). Ca²⁺ signatures are decoded and transmitted by a toolkit of Ca²⁺-binding proteins, also called calcium sensors, which undergo a conformational change that leads to target protein phosphorylation and consequentially downstream cascades initiation. Activation of Ca²⁺-

dependent protein kinase (CDPK) cascade conveys immune signaling to the nucleus, resulting in transcriptional reprogramming to establish PRR-triggered immunity (PTI). Multiple knockouts of Arabidopsis CALCIUM-DEPENDENT PROTEIN KINASE 5 (CPK5), CPK6 and CPK11 impair flg22- and OG-induced transcription of specific sets of genes (Boudsocq *et al.*, 2010; Dubiella *et al.*, 2013; Gravino *et al.*, 2015). Moreover, the three CDPKs also mediate the basal resistance as well as the OG-induced protection against *B. cinerea*, by regulating pathogen-induced ethylene production and accumulation of the ethylene biosynthetic enzymes 1-aminocyclopropane-1-carboxylic acid (ACC) synthase 2 (ACS2) and ACS6 (Gravino *et al.*, 2015). Downstream of ET production, the pathway of OGs that leads to the protection against *B. cinerea*, accumulation of ROS, and upregulation of the defense genes *FRK1*, *CYP81F2*, *RET-OX* and *PR1*, requires ethylene insensitive 2 (EIN2) (Gravino *et al.*, 2015), a major regulator of ET signaling.

During PTI, calcium and CDPKs act upstream of the respiratory burst oxidase homolog D (RBOHD) activation, a NADPH oxidase required for the production of ROS during infection with different bacterial and fungal pathogens, including *B. cinerea* (Torres and Dangl, 2005; Torres *et al.*, 2006), and in response to different type of elicitors, including OGs (Galletti *et al.*, 2008). Plant RBOHs have an additional N-terminal region, which is mostly regulated by Ca^{2+} via direct binding to EF-hand motifs and phosphorylation by CDPKs (Suzuki *et al.*, 2011; Marino *et al.*, 2012). Moreover, Ca^{2+} and ROS can amplify each other (Qi *et al.*, 2017). However, a role of CPK5, CPK6 and CPK11 in the OG-induced ROS production has been ruled out (Gravino *et al.*, 2015). Besides CDPKs, RBOHD could be activated, via phosphorylation, by BOTRYTIS-INDUCED KINASE 1 (BIK1) and PBL1 in a calcium-independent manner (Kadota *et al.*, 2014) and have a feedback effect on the $[Ca^{2+}]_{\text{cyt}}$ response by inducing an additive $[Ca^{2+}]_{\text{cyt}}$ elevation causing a second peak or prolonged plateau (Ranf *et al.*, 2011; Dubiella *et al.*, 2013). Whether BIK1 and PBL1 are involved in OG signaling has not been determined yet.

Mitogen-activated protein kinases MAPKs represent a second vehicle to trigger transcriptional changes upon PAMP or DAMP perception. MAPK cascades contain three sequentially activated protein kinases: MAPK kinase kinase (MAPKKK), MAPK kinase (MAPKK) and MAPK. Multiple knockout of the MAPKKKs ARABIDOPSIS NUCLEUS- AND PHRAGMOPLAST-LOCALIZED KINASE1-RELATED PROTEIN KINASE1 (ANP1), ANP2, and ANP3 and loss of the Arabidopsis MAPK MPK6 impair flg22-, elf18- and OG-induced transcription of specific sets of genes, ROS production and resistance to *B. cinerea* (Galletti *et al.*, 2011; Savatin *et al.*, 2014a).

Successful pathogens must overcome PTI in order to cause disease, either by evading or suppressing this important first layer of plant innate immunity. To do this, pathogens have evolved effectors, which are delivered both to the plant apoplast and inside the host cells. In an evolutionary arms race, plants have developed the ability to detect such effectors through other types of receptor, called resistance (R) proteins, and to counteract the invasion by activating effector-triggered immunity (ETI) (Jones and Dangl, 2006; Macho and Zipfel, 2015). The *Pseudomonas syringae* pv. *tomato* DC3000 (Pst)-derived effector AvrPto, a type III kinase inhibitor, triggers gene-for-gene resistance and hypersensitive response (HR) in tomato plants carrying the corresponding R gene *Pto*, encoding a serine/threonine kinase (Pedley and Martin, 2003). Moreover, it has been shown that AvrPto suppresses responses to MAMPs and OGs (Li *et al.*, 2005; He *et al.*, 2006; Xiang *et al.*, 2008; Gimenez-Ibanez *et al.*, 2009; Gravino *et al.*, 2017). Interestingly, in a comparison between flg22- OG-induced responses, whereas all the flg22-induced defense responses analyzed were affected by AvrPto, only a subset of those induced by OGs were affected by this effector (Gravino *et al.*, 2017). Since AvrPto has been described to target the perception complexes (Shan *et al.*, 2008; Xiang *et al.*, 2008; Gimenez-Ibanez *et al.*, 2009; Wu *et al.*, 2017), these results suggest that the perception of OGs is more complex than that of flg22 and may involve multiple perception complexes, some of which are targeted by AvrPto, others capable of eluding the suppression action of this effector.

3.7 Homeostasis of OGs as mechanism of regulation of growth-defense trade off

Hyperaccumulation of OGs *in planta* has been shown to be deleterious for growth and development. Indeed, tobacco and Arabidopsis transgenic plants expressing an attenuated version of PGII of *Aspergillus niger*, referred to as “PG plants”, display a reduced content of homogalacturonan, constitutively activated defense responses, dwarf phenotype and a concomitant reduced sensitivity to auxin (Ferrari *et al.*, 2008). The constitutive expression of at least some of the defense responses and the antagonism of auxin action observed in PG plants is likely mediated by OGs released by the fungal enzyme expressed in the transgenic plants (Ferrari *et al.*, 2008). Moreover, Arabidopsis plants expressing a chimeric construct comprising a gene encoding the PG from *Fusarium phyllophilum* fused with a gene encoding the PGIP2 from *Phaseolus vulgaris*, referred to as OG machine (OGM) plants, accumulate OGs *in vivo* and exhibit constitutively activated defense responses and a concomitant reduced growth and senescent phenotype (Benedetti *et al.*, 2015), indicating that an elevated concentration of OGs in the cells may be deleterious for the plant fitness and suggesting that a mechanism for controlling the homeostasis of OGs must exist to prevent the impairment of the plant physiological functions. The OGM plants diffusates contained, in addition to small amounts of unmodified OGs, an abundant proportion of oligosaccharides with retention times different from those of standard OGs, which were hydrolyzed by a fungal PG, indicating that they were OGs with modified structural characteristics (Verrascina 2017, PhD thesis; Benedetti *et al.* 2017, in publication). Electrospray ionization mass spectrometry (ESI-MS) analyses showed that the modification consisted in the oxidation to galactaric acid of the residue at the reducing end (Verrascina 2017, PhD thesis; Benedetti *et al.* 2017, in publication). The putative OG-oxidizing enzyme was purified from OGM leaves by affinity chromatography and identified by LC-MS analysis as a reticuline oxidase-like protein isoform 2 encoded by *At4g20830* (Verrascina 2017, PhD thesis; Benedetti *et al.* 2017, in publication). This gene belongs to the superfamily of genes encoding the FAD-binding berberine-bridge like enzymes (BBIE) that comprises 27 members (2015), five of which (*At4g20840*, *At1g30740*, *At1g01980*, *At1g11770*, *At1g30700*) share a similarity > 45% with that of *At4g20830*. After heterologous expression and purification, only *At4g20830*, *At4g20840*, *At1g01980*, *At1g11770* were able to oxidize *in vitro* a mixture of OGs as well as purified OG oligomers with a DP \geq 5, but not cellopentaose, cellotriose and several sugar monomers, including galacturonic acid (Verrascina 2017, PhD thesis; Benedetti *et al.* 2017, in publication). For this feature, the enzymes were named OG oxidase 1 (OGOX1/*At4g20830*), OGOX2/*At4g20840*), OGOX3/*At1g01980* and OGOX4/*At1g11770*. Interestingly, oxOGs were unable to induce responses that are typical readouts of the action of elicitor-active OGs, i.e. the expression of the defense markers *RetOx* and *CYP81F2*, the oxidative burst, the callose deposition, and the inhibition of the auxin-induced responses (Verrascina 2017, PhD thesis; Benedetti *et al.* 2017, in publication). Moreover, oxOGs did not interfere with the elicitor activity of un-oxidized OGs, indicating that they do not compete with the active molecules at the receptor level. Thus, this mechanism emerges as a key element for controlling homeostasis of OGs and likely the trade-off between growth and defense.

3.8 Plant immunity in plant-aphid interactions

Most aphid species are highly specialized and can only infest plants in a single taxonomic family or few related plant species (De Vos *et al.*, 2007) and, for this feature, are considered specialist. However, some aphid species are able to infest plants in many families and are considered polyphagous, or generalist. *Myzus persicae*, also known as green peach aphid (GPA), is one of

the most agricultural important aphid species worldwide. GPA is extremely generalist and feeds on a wide range of host plants in over 40 families, including several families of important vegetable crops, in the absence of genetic specialization. This is achieved through rapid transcriptional plasticity of genes that have duplicated during aphid evolution (Mathers *et al.*, 2017). The major economic cost of green peach aphid is due to its high efficiency as a virus vector. It can transmit numerous plant viruses, including both persistent and non-persistent viruses (Hogenhout *et al.*, 2008). The feeding behavior of GPA contributes to this insect being efficient virus vectors. GPA shows striking capability to develop resistance to more insecticides than any other known species, being able to resist to more than 200 different insecticides (Bass *et al.*, 2014). These characteristics, combined with the capacity of the rapid growth of insect population due to an asexual stage in the aphid life cycle, have made this aphid one of the most economic important agricultural pests as well as a biological model for insect-plant interaction studies.

Aphids have a heteroecious holocyclic life cycle, involving alternate hosts. Sexual reproduction, which occurs only during a portion of their life cycle, results in the production of female and male sexual morphs. The females lay their eggs on the primary host plant, where they can overwinter. In places where a primary host plant is absent or not available, and if climate permits the asexual stages to survive winter, GPA exhibits an anholocyclic life cycle and reproduces parthenogenically (offsprings produced without fertilization) (Shingleton *et al.*, 2003). In the lab, GPA exhibits an anholocyclic life cycle under typical *Arabidopsis* growth conditions.

Traditionally, plant-aphid interactions research has been focused on the plant side, which has provided insights into some of the plant defense mechanisms effective against aphids. There are several steps involved in the initial contact between aphids and plants, prior to any feeding attempts. Aphids first need to land on the plant surface, which may be affected by several plant cues, including volatiles. Upon landing these insects may perceive plant cues and structures present on the leaf surface, such as trichomes and waxes, which may affect their behavior (Powell *et al.*, 2006). Aphids are phloem sap feeders and possess stinging-sucking mouthparts (called stylets) that navigate between cells on their way to phloem sieve cells for long-term feeding (Tjallingii, 2006). During this navigation, however, the stylets probe mesophyll cells and other cell types. Each stylet probe involves a penetration of cell wall and membrane, injection of saliva (and virus particles) into the cell cytoplasm, acquisition of some cell cytoplasm (and viruses if the plant is infected), and finally, retraction of the stylets, which may navigate to another cell for a next probe or start a feeding site elsewhere. All phloem-feeding insects rely on endosymbiont bacteria to synthesize some essential nutrients that are limiting in the phloem sap. In the case of GPA, an obligate bacterial endosymbiont, *Buchnera aphidicola*, which lives inside aphids in specialized cells called bacteriocytes, synthesize essential amino acids required by the aphids, but that are limiting in the phloem sap (Baumann, 2005).

During this constant interaction with their hosts, plant defenses are likely to be triggered. Most studies of plant defense signaling in plant-aphid interactions have focused on the model system *Arabidopsis thaliana-Myzus persicae* (Jaouannet *et al.*, 2014). This revealed the contribution of several signaling pathways involved in activating defenses. For example, GPA feeding was found to induce the expression of SA-, ET-, and ABA (abscisic acid)-signaling pathway marker genes, while JA-responsive genes were repressed, in both local and distal leaves (Moran and Thompson, 2001; De Vos *et al.*, 2005). Moreover, rapid and highly localized $[Ca^{2+}]_{cyt}$ elevations were found in *Arabidopsis* leaves around the feeding sites of GPA (Vincent *et al.*, 2017).

Arabidopsis mutant analyses indicated a role for several defense signaling pathways in the interaction with GPA. Real-time imaging of calcium $[Ca^{2+}]_{cyt}$ elevations during aphid feeding using a GCaMP3 reporter system showed that these $[Ca^{2+}]_{cyt}$ elevations were abolished in transgenic *Arabidopsis* lines of *35S:GCaMP3 x bak1-5*, which is defective in PAMP signaling, and in *35S:GCaMP3 x glr3.3 glr3.6*, which lack the well-characterized plasma membrane Ca^{2+} -permeable channels GLR3.3 and GLR3.6, and reduced in *35S:GCaMP3 x tpc1-2* line, which

lacks the vacuolar ion channel TPC1 (Vincent *et al.*, 2017). The role of SA signaling in resistance to GPA is not clear. Indeed, while Mewis and collaborators showed that both *npr1* mutant and *NahG* transgenic Arabidopsis lines, which are defective in SA signaling, were less susceptible to GPA (Mewis *et al.*, 2005), this difference was not found by Pegadaraju and collaborators who reported no difference of these lines to the control (Pegadaraju *et al.*, 2005). Evidence for a role of JA and ET in the activation of defenses against GPA was provided by Ellis and collaborators who showed that Arabidopsis mutants with constitutive activation of JA-signaling were more resistant to aphids than wild-type plants (Ellis *et al.*, 2002), and by Kettles and collaborators who showed that aphid fecundity is increased on *ethylene-insensitive 2 (ein2)* mutants (Kettles *et al.*, 2013). Interestingly, and despite changes in marker gene expression, no increase in detectable levels of SA, JA, or ET was detected in Arabidopsis plants infested with GPA (De Vos *et al.*, 2005), suggesting that regulation of marker gene expression and defense signaling may be more complex and does not solely rely on the production of these hormones. Defense against aphids also relies on components that act independent from hormone signaling pathways. For example, *PAD4*, which encodes a lipase-like protein with a role in plant immunity, contributes to defense responses against GPA (Pegadaraju *et al.*, 2007; Lei *et al.*, 2014). Another component found to contribute to defense responses is *PAD3* (Kettles *et al.*, 2013), which encodes a cytochrome P450 that is involved in the biosynthesis of the phytoalexin camalexin. Interestingly, the plant miRNA pathway was shown to regulate *PAD3* expression, and consequently, the production of camalexin. Other secondary metabolites with a role in defense against GPA include glucosinolates. Aphid feeding triggers the accumulation of indole glucosinolates (Kim and Jander, 2007). Moreover, mutants with increased levels of indol-3-ylmethylglucosinolate were less susceptible to aphids, while mutants with decreased levels of indole glucosinolates collapsed more rapidly upon aphid attack (Kim *et al.*, 2008).

Despite the activation of host defenses, GPA is able to overcome these to successfully feed from and reproduce on an impressively wide range of plant species. It is evident that aphids are able to manipulate host responses, as reflected by their ability to affect host morphology (Rodriguez *et al.*, 2017), impact host nutrient allocation (Girousse *et al.*, 2005), and suppress plant defense responses (Will *et al.*, 2007). This implies there is an active interplay between plants and aphids at the molecular level. The emerging aphid effector paradigm suggests that aphids, like other plant-associated organisms, secrete effectors inside their host to manipulate host cell processes through the interaction with host molecules (Elzinga and Jander, 2013; Rodriguez and Bos, 2013). In this case, the plant-parasite interaction becomes a complicated molecular-warfare battle, where an evolutionary “arms race” takes place. A zig-zag model has been proposed to shape the interaction that takes place between plants and parasites (Jones and Dangl, 2006). However, to what extent the model would apply to aphids, and potentially other insects, is yet unknown. According to the model, aphids present conserved molecules similar to PAMPs that trigger PTI (Hogenhout and Bos, 2011; Rodriguez and Bos, 2013). Aphids then deliver effectors inside their host to suppress this as well as other defenses promoting effector-triggered susceptibility (ETS). Some plant species/genotypes may carry receptors, or R proteins that can recognize these effectors leading effector-triggered immunity (ETI). In reality the plant defense system is expected to be more complex than the zig-zag model implies and there may be overlap between the molecular requirements for PTI and ETI (Thomma *et al.*, 2011).

Elicitor activity has been detected in both aphid saliva and whole aphid extracts. For example, an unknown elicitor present in the 3-10 kDa fraction of saliva from GPA induces defense responses in *A. thaliana* effective against aphids (De Vos and Jander, 2009). The activation of defenses by aphid saliva was independent of JA, SA, or ET signaling molecules, and only few JA or SA signaling pathway-related genes were induced upon saliva treatment, suggesting alternative defense mechanisms may be involved. To date only one elicitor has been identified as an aphid PAMP in saliva of potato aphids (*Macrosiphum euphorbiae*), i.e. the 60 kDa chaperonin GroEL from the aphid primary endosymbiont *B. aphidicola* (Chaudhary *et al.*, 2014).

Additional evidence for the activation of immunity by aphids is provided by a recent study where treatment with whole aphid extract from GPA activated PTI responses in *Arabidopsis* (Prince *et al.*, 2014). While both the 3-10 and >10 kDa fractions induced resistance to aphids, only the 3-10 kDa fraction triggered the ROS burst, suggesting multiple elicitors were present in the whole aphid extracts. The activation of PTI responses was dependent on BAK1. In addition, induced resistance required PAD3.

Interestingly, not only the saliva, but also the honeydew of aphids can alter plant defenses (Hagenbucher *et al.*, 2014) and has been found to contain bacterial proteins (Sabri *et al.*, 2013). These include EF-Tu, chaperone proteins, and flagellin, which are derived from the aphid microbiota (Sabri *et al.*, 2013). The microbiota of aphids is thought to not only consist of primary and secondary endosymbionts, but also plant pathogenic bacteria such as *Pseudomonas syringae* (Stavriniades *et al.*, 2009), as well as a range of other bacteria, including *Staphylococcus* species, *Serratia marcescens* and *Erwinia* (Sabri *et al.*, 2013). Chitin, a known fungal PAMP, is also an important structural component of the aphid stylets and exoskeleton (Uzest *et al.*, 2010). Whether these aphid-associated microbes and PAMPs are all able to trigger plant defenses and the impact of this on plant-aphid interactions remains to be investigated. However, *Arabidopsis fls2 efr cerk1* triple mutants were able to produce a ROS response upon treatment with whole aphid extracts indicating that the elicitor responsible for the observed activation of PTI responses was not detected by FLS2, EFR and CERK1 (Prince *et al.*, 2014).

Such defenses are thought to be suppressed in host plants by the aphid effectors that are most likely expressed in salivary glands and secreted into saliva, which is delivered inside the host during feeding and probing (Hogenhout and Bos, 2011; Elzinga and Jander, 2013). Among the identified (predicted) secreted salivary proteins, or candidate effectors, to date some have predicted activities. These include cell wall-degrading enzymes (pectinases, glucanases, amylases) and detoxifying enzymes (oxidoreductases, phenol oxidases, peroxidases) (Harmel *et al.*, 2008; Carolan *et al.*, 2009; Cooper *et al.*, 2010; Carolan *et al.*, 2011; Cooper *et al.*, 2011; Nicholson *et al.*, 2012; Rao *et al.*, 2013). However, a large number of candidate effectors have no similarity to proteins of predicted function. A limited number of the GPA-secreted effector proteins have been characterized and have been implicated in promoting virulence, i.e. MpCOO2, Mp1, Mp2 and Mp55, or decreasing virulence, i.e. Mp10, Mp42, Mp56, Mp57 and Mp58, and activating defenses, i.e. Mp10, or suppressing defenses, i.e. Mp10 and Mp55 (Bos *et al.*, 2010; Pitino and Hogenhout, 2013; Elzinga and Jander, 2013; Elzinga *et al.*, 2014; Rodriguez *et al.*, 2014). Mp10 was identified from a functional genomics screen, and reduced aphid virulence upon transient overexpression in *N. benthamiana* (Bos *et al.*, 2010). Mp10 induced chlorosis and local cell death, which are marker responses of ETI, and suppressed the ROS burst triggered by flg22, but not by chitin, which is a PTI response (Bos *et al.*, 2010). When transiently overexpressed in *N. benthamiana*, Mp10 induces SA and JA-related defense genes (Rodriguez *et al.*, 2014), which are induced both during PTI and ETI. Thus, Mp10 by suppressing the PTI and activating the ETI behaves like a canonical effector. However, it remains to be understood why its overexpression *in planta* leads to decreased aphid colonization.

4. AIMS

The capability of plants to survive adverse conditions and reach reproductive maturity critically depends on their ability to continually adapt to changes in the environment. Therefore, plants have evolved an array of intricate regulatory mechanisms that involve the generation of signaling molecules mediating the activation of adaptive responses. In particular, the activation of pathogen-specific defense mechanisms upon microbial infection and the acquisition of architectural and physiological adjustments to environmental changes permit survival, development, and reproduction of plants. Plant activity at the cellular level can be classified as growth (cell division and enlargement) and differentiation (chemical and morphological changes leading to cell maturation and specialization). These processes are often affected in response to microorganisms because plants must grow fast enough to compete, yet maintain the defenses necessary to survive in the presence of pathogens or symbiotic organisms. The plant cell wall (CW) is a complex extracellular structure that plays important roles in plant growth and development. It is also the major line of defense against pathogens and abiotic stress factors. CWs are able to perform these functions because their composition and fine structure are modified in response to different type of stimuli originating in the environment or deriving from the plant itself. A major structural role of defense against external stimuli is certainly played by homogalacturonan (HG) and HG modifying enzymes (HGMEs) that regulate the HG methylesterification degree (DM). Indeed, a high DM of HG has been correlated to genotype resistance to the necrotrophic pathogens *Botrytis cinerea* and *Pectobacterium carotovorum*.

Emerging evidence indicates that plant cells harbor sophisticated mechanisms for sensing the alteration of cell wall integrity during biotic and abiotic stresses. At the early stages of infection, phytopathogenic microorganisms produce enzymes capable of degrading the plant CW; among these enzymes, polygalacturonases (PGs) cleave the α -1,4 glycosidic bonds present between the galacturonic acid units of homogalacturonan. When the activity of a fungal PG is modulated by apoplastic PG-inhibiting proteins (PGIPs), long-chain oligogalacturonides are produced. These fragments of homogalacturonan with a wide degree of polymerization of 9 to 16 residues called oligogalacturonides or OGs accumulate in the plant apoplast and trigger plant defense responses. The defense-related biological responses to OGs are well known and documented. For example, responses activated by OGs in *Arabidopsis* can activate defense responses effective against *B. cinerea*, *P. carotovorum* and Pst. The OG-induced protection against *B. cinerea* is dependent on ethylene and camalexin pathways.

OGs are perceived by the wall-associated kinase 1 (WAK1), a trans membrane receptor-like kinase (RLK) containing epidermal growth factor-like repeats. The glycine-rich protein 3 (GRP3) forms a complex with WAK1 and negatively regulates OG responses. The perception of OGs also involves the coreceptor BRI1-associated receptor kinase 1 (BAK1) and its closest paralogue BAK1-like 1 (BKK1), which belong to the somatic embryogenesis receptor-like kinase (SERK) gene family that comprises five members. If BAK1 and BKK1 associate with the WAK1 perception complex is not yet known. Several elements have been reported to participate in the OG signaling, including the calcium-dependent protein kinases (CDPKs) CPK5, CPK6 and CPK11, the ethylene-insensitive 2 (EIN2) and the Pep1-receptor 1 (PEPR1) and PEPR2. Moreover, the *Pseudomonas syringae* pv *tomato* (Pst)-derived effector AvrPto has been shown to suppress the OG-triggered immunity. Since AvrPto has been described to target perception complexes and not all OG responses were suppressed by this effector, it has been hypothesized that multiple perception/transduction complexes may be involved in the OG signaling. Moreover, among the responses affected by AvrPto, only a subset was affected by the concomitant loss of BAK1 and BKK1, suggesting that other co-receptors, presumably from the SERK family, may be required for the signaling induced by OGs.

In addition to these defense events, OGs have also been shown to induce changes in plant growth and development. Indeed, biologically active OGs inhibit root formation and increase stomata formation in tobacco leaf explants. Moreover, hyper accumulation of OGs has been

shown to be deleterious for the plant. Increasing experimental evidence indicates that these developmental effects may be due to the capability of OGs of antagonizing the action of the phytohormone auxin (indole-3-acetic acid, IAA). Because maintenance of immunity is costly, plants finely tune immunity and activated it only upon sensing danger signals. Immune response activation is accompanied by a down-regulation of growth processes, a phenomenon called growth-defense trade off, and plants that constitutively express defense responses are dwarf, suggesting that an immunity shutdown mechanism must exist to regulate the growth-defense trade off. Indeed, a specific Arabidopsis berberine bridge enzyme-like (BBE-like) protein, encoded by the gene *At4g20830*, has been recently shown to oxidize OGs and, doing so, to inactivate their elicitor activity, in a mechanism that may control the homeostasis of OGs and regulate the growth-defense trade off. However, the role of this enzyme, named OG oxidase 1 (OGOX1), in plant immunity and development has not yet been determined.

The purpose of this thesis is to (i) evaluate the role of other members of SERK family, i.e. SERK1 and SERK2 (SERK5 contains a mutation in an important amino acid residue which likely abolishes its kinase activity in the commonly used Arabidopsis Columbia-0 ecotype) in the OG signaling; (ii) investigate the role of cell wall and OGs in plant resistance against the green peach aphid *Myzus persicae*; (iii) evaluate the role of OGOX1 in immunity and development.

5. SERK2 AND AGB1 PLAY A ROLE IN THE OLIGOGALACTURONIDE-TRIGGERED IMMUNITY IN *ARABIDOPSIS THALIANA*

5.1 SUMMARY

Plants possess an innate immune system capable of restricting invasion by most potential pathogens. At the cell surface, the recognition of microbe-associated molecular patterns (MAMPs) and/or damage-associated molecular patterns (DAMPs) by pattern recognition receptors (PRRs) represents the first event for the prompt mounting of an effective immune response. Pathogens have evolved effectors that block PRR-triggered immunity. The *Pseudomonas syringae* effector AvrPto abolishes immunity triggered by the MAMP peptide flg22, derived from the bacterial flagellin, and the DAMP oligogalacturonides (OGs), i.e. oligomers of α -1,4-linked galacturonosyl residues, released on partial degradation of the plant cell wall homogalacturonan. Both flg22- and OG-triggered immunity require the SOMATIC EMBRYOGENESIS RECEPTOR KINASE (SERK) coreceptor BRI1-ASSOCIATED RECEPTOR KINASE1 (BAK1/SERK3) and its closest paralogue BAK1-LIKE1/SERK4 (BKK1/SERK4). However, a recent comparison of the defense responses induced by flg22 or OGs showed that whereas all the flg22-induced defense responses are affected by AvrPto and the lack of BAK1 and BKK1, only a subset of those induced by OGs is affected by AvrPto, and, among these, only a subset is affected by the lack of BAK1 and BKK1, suggesting that the OG perception system is much more complex than that of flg22. In this work we analyze the role of other SERKs, i.e. SERK1 and SERK2, in the response to OGs. Moreover, we evaluate the involvement in the OG signaling of the G β protein AGB1, which has been shown to be required for defense signaling activated by multiple receptor-like kinases. Our results indicate that SERK2 and AGB1, but not SERK1, play a role in OG-triggered immunity.

5.2 INTRODUCTION

Plants, as sessile organisms, are continually exposed to adverse conditions, both biotic and abiotic. As a result of the absence of an adaptive immune system, plants rely on an innate immune system that depends on efficient pathogen sensing and the rapid establishment of defense responses (Gomez-Gomez, 2004; Bohm *et al.*, 2014). Pathogen detection occurs through the direct binding of broadly conserved pathogen molecules (pathogen-/microbe-associated molecular patterns, PAMPs/MAMPs) by a large arsenal of transmembrane pattern recognition receptors (PRRs). Specific PRRs also detect host-derived damage-associated molecular patterns (DAMPs), including cell wall fragments or peptides produced by mechanical injuries or lytic activities of microbe-secreted enzymes (Savatin *et al.*, 2014b; Cervone *et al.*, 2015). Activated PRRs trigger immune responses by switching on different and parallel signal transduction pathways. This represents the first layer of the plant immune system and is known as PRR-triggered immunity (PTI) (Zipfel, 2014). Successful pathogens must overcome PTI in order to cause disease, either by evading or suppressing this important first layer of plant innate immunity. To do this, pathogens have evolved effectors, which are delivered both to the plant apoplast and inside the host cells. In an evolutionary arms race, plants have developed the ability to detect such effectors through other types of receptor, called resistance (R) proteins, and to counteract the invasion by activating effector-triggered immunity (ETI) (Jones and Dangl, 2006; Macho and Zipfel, 2015).

Studies on plant defense-related signaling pathways have largely focused on MAMP perception and transduction; for insights see reviews (Couto and Zipfel, 2016; Tang *et al.*, 2017). In *Arabidopsis thaliana*, one of the best-characterized PTI systems is that mediated by the Leucine-Rich Repeat (LRR)-Receptor Like Kinase (RLK) FLAGELLIN SENSING 2 (FLS2), which perceives a 22-amino acid long conserved peptide (flg22) derived from bacterial flagellin (Gomez-Gomez and Boller, 2000). Upon binding of flg22 to the extracellular LRR of FLS2, this RLK forms a dynamic complex with the co-receptor BRI1-ASSOCIATED RECEPTOR KINASE 1 (BAK1/SERK3) and its closest paralogue BAK1-LIKE1 (BKK1/SERK4) (Roux *et al.*, 2011), two of the five members of the LRR-LRK SOMATIC EMBRYOGENESIS RECEPTOR KINASE (SERK) family (Albrecht *et al.*, 2008), and the Receptor-Like Cytoplasmic Kinase (RLCK) BOTRYTIS-INDUCED KINASE 1 (BIK1) (Lu *et al.*, 2010), thereby transducing extracellular flg22 perception into downstream signaling phosphorylation events (Benschop *et al.*, 2007). Within minutes, pattern recognition triggers a number of cellular events, including increase of cytoplasmic calcium concentration and activation of CALCIUM-DEPENDENT PROTEIN KINASEs (CDPKs), respiratory burst oxidase homologue D (RBOHD)-mediated production of reactive oxygen species (ROS), activation of the MITOGEN-ACTIVATED PROTEIN KINASES (MAPKs) cascade and transcriptional reprogramming (Tena *et al.*, 2011). PTI signaling is down regulated by FLS2 and BIK1 proteasome- and CDPK-dependent turnover (Lu *et al.*, 2011; Monaghan *et al.*, 2014). A heterotrimeric G protein complex comprising of EXTRALARGE GUANINE NUCLEOTIDE-BINDING PROTEIN 2 (XLG2), GUANINE NUCLEOTIDE BINDING PROTEIN SUBUNIT- β (AGB1) and GUANINE NUCLEOTIDE-BINDING PROTEIN SUBUNIT- γ 1 (AGG1) or AGG2 was recently shown to attenuate BIK1 proteasome degradation and promote immune signaling induced by MAMPs (Liang *et al.*, 2016).

Although much less characterized, signaling by DAMPs appears to involve many of these elements. Most of our knowledge comes from the studies on the peptide Atpeps (Bartels and Boller, 2015) and oligogalacturonides (OGs), i.e. pectin-derived oligosaccharides released from plant cell walls on partial degradation of homogalacturonan, which both represent prototypical classes of DAMPs (Ferrari *et al.*, 2013).

Very early OG-triggered responses include increase of cytoplasmic calcium concentration, ion effluxes and extracellular alkalization (Ridley *et al.*, 2001). Moreover, OGs rapidly and transiently activate, through phosphorylation, MAPK cascades, including the single kinases MPK3 and MPK6 (Galletti *et al.*, 2011) and the triple kinases ARABIDOPSIS NUCLEUS- AND

PHRAGMOPLAST-LOCALIZED KINASE 1-RELATED PROTEIN KINASE 1 (ANP1), ANP2, and ANP3 (Savatin *et al.*, 2014a). Extracellular ROS production is another early response to OGs that is mediated by the NAD(P)H oxidase respiratory burst oxidase homologue D (RBOHD) (Galletti *et al.*, 2008). OGs also induce biosynthesis of ethylene, which is mediated by the CDPK pathway (Gravino *et al.*, 2015), and phytoalexins (Ridley *et al.*, 2001). Transcriptional reprogramming is another response to OGs (Denoux *et al.*, 2008), which is dependent on both MAPK and CDPK pathways (Galletti *et al.*, 2011; Gravino *et al.*, 2015), as well as ethylene signaling (Gravino *et al.*, 2015). OGs also induce late responses, such as callose deposition (Galletti *et al.*, 2008). Moreover, the immunity triggered by OGs confers resistance against the necrotrophic fungus *Botrytis cinerea*, through PHYTOALEXIN DEFICIENT 3 (PAD3)-mediated camalexin production (Ferrari *et al.*, 2007), and signaling pathways mediated by MAPKs, CDPKs, SERKs, Pep receptors (PEPRs) and ethylene (Galletti *et al.*, 2011; Savatin *et al.*, 2014a; Gravino *et al.*, 2015; Gravino *et al.*, 2017). A number of evidences indicate that OGs play a role also in development. Indeed, they antagonize auxin responses and hyper accumulation of OGs has deleterious effects on plant growth (Savatin *et al.*, 2011; Benedetti *et al.*, 2015).

In *A. thaliana*, WALL-ASSOCIATED KINASE 1 (WAK1), a transmembrane RLK containing epidermal growth factor-like repeats, has been identified as an OG receptor (Brutus *et al.*, 2010). The KINASE-ASSOCIATED PROTEIN PHOSPHATASE (KAPP) and the GLYCINE-RICH PROTEIN 3 (GRP3) have been found to form a complex with WAK1 (Park *et al.*, 2001; Anderson *et al.*, 2001) and to negatively regulate OG responses (Gramegna *et al.*, 2016). Moreover, BAK1 and BKK1 are redundantly required for OG-mediated immunity (Gravino *et al.*, 2017). Furthermore, the *Pseudomonas syringae* pv *tomato* (Pst)-derived effector AvrPto has been shown to suppress the immunity triggered by OGs and MAMPs (Li *et al.*, 2005; Gimenez-Ibanez *et al.*, 2009; Gravino *et al.*, 2017). However, AvrPto suppresses a subset of OG responses and, among these, only a subset is affected by the concomitant loss of BAK1 and BKK1 (Gravino *et al.*, 2017), suggesting a high level of complexity in the OG perception and signaling. Indeed, suppression of MAMP-induced responses by AvrPto occurs through direct binding and inhibition of elements in the perception complexes. When, as in the case of flg22, the perception complex is only one, all immune responses are suppressed by AvrPto (Gravino *et al.*, 2017). However, a dispute is open as to whether this effector targets BAK1 or FLS2 (Shan *et al.*, 2008; Xiang *et al.*, 2008), and evidence in support of both possibilities has been provided (Goehre *et al.*, 2008; Cheng *et al.*, 2011; Xiang *et al.*, 2011). In the case of OGs, AvrPto-(in)dependent responses suggests that different types of perception/transduction complexes (not all targeted by AvrPto) mediate OG signaling, whereas AvrPto-dependent BAK1/BKK1-independent responses point to different types of complex(es), which may comprise co-receptors other than BAK1 and BKK1 and/or receptors of a different class, targeted, however, by AvrPto. Members of the SERK family, other than BAK1 and BKK1, i.e. SERK1 and SERK2 [In the commonly used Arabidopsis Columbia-0 ecotype, SERK5 contains a mutation in an important amino acid residue which likely abolishes its kinase activity (He *et al.*, 2007)], are good candidates for playing a role in OG-triggered BAK1/BKK1-independent responses.

SERK1, along with BAK1 and BKK1, positively regulates responses to brassinosteroids (BRs) (Albrecht *et al.*, 2008). SERK1 and SERK2 have redundant roles in male sporogenesis (Albrecht *et al.*, 2008) and, along with BAK1 and BKK1, redundantly regulate stomatal patterning (Meng *et al.*, 2015). A possible role of SERK1 and SERK2 in response to MAMPs was ruled out (Roux *et al.*, 2011).

To elucidate whether SERK1 and SERK2 participate to OG signaling, we analyzed OG responses in the *serk1-1* and *serk2-1* mutants. Moreover, we evaluated the effect of the loss of AGB1 in the OG signaling. Our results indicate that SERK2 and AGB1, but not SERK1, play a role in the OG-triggered immunity.

5.3 RESULTS

Loss of SERK2, but not of SERK1, affects a subset of the OG-triggered responses that are affected by AvrPto but do not require BAK1 and BKK1

Previous work showed that a subset of OG-induced responses, i.e. MAPK activation, upregulation of the defense genes *CYTOCHROME P450 (CYP81F2)*, *RETICULINE-OXIDASE HOMOLOGUE (RET-OX)*, *PHYTOALEXIN DEFICIENT 3 (PAD3)*, and *POLYGALACTURONASE-INHIBITING PROTEIN 1 (PGIP1)* (Gravino *et al.*, 2017), are suppressed by AvrPto but do not require BAK1 and BKK1. Whether two other members of the SERK family, i.e. SERK1 and SERK2, play a role in these responses was investigated, using the corresponding single mutants *serk1-1* and *serk2-1* (see molecular characterization in Fig. S1A and B in the next material and methods section). Upon treatment with OGs, defective responses were observed only in the *serk2-1* mutant. MAPK activation was slightly reduced after 5 and 10 minutes of treatment with elicitor, and unaffected after 15 minutes (Fig. 1A). The OG-induced expression of *CYP81F2* and *RET-OX* was impaired in this mutant relative to the wild type after 15 and 30 minutes, and unaffected after 60 and 180 minutes (Fig. 1B). The OG-induced expression of *PGIP1*, a late elicitor-induced gene, was impaired in the *serk2-1* mutant after 180 minutes of treatment with OGs (Fig. 1B). Interestingly, the same responses were found to be affected in AvrPto transgenic plants (Gravino *et al.*, 2017), although the presence of AvrPto seems to affect these responses to a higher extent than the absence of SERK2. However, unlike in AvrPto plants, the OG-induced expression of *PAD3* was affected in neither *serk1-1* nor *serk2-1* (Fig. 1B).

Figure 1. Analysis of AvrPto-dependent BAK1/BKK1-independent OG-triggered immune responses in the *serk1-1* and *serk2-1* mutants. **A.** Levels of phosphorylated MPK3 and MPK6 (pMPK3 and pMPK6) in seedlings of wild type (Col-0), *serk1-1* and *serk2-1* after elicitation with OGs ($50 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) at the indicated time points were determined by immunoblot analysis using an anti-p44/42-ERK antibody (top panels). Levels of MPK3 and MPK6 total proteins were determined using specific antibodies (bottom panels). The identity of individual MAP kinases, as determined by size, is indicated by arrows. **B.** Expression of the indicated defense genes was analyzed by qRT-PCR in seedlings of Col-0, *serk1-1* and *serk2-1* after treatment with OGs ($50 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) at the indicated time points. Transcripts levels are shown as the mean of at least three independent experiments (\pm SE; $n = 20$ in each experiment) normalized to *UBQ5* expression. Asterisks indicate statistically significant differences between mutant and wild-type samples at the indicated time points, according to Student's *t* test (*, $P < 0.05$; **, $P < 0.01$). In A and B, experiments were repeated three times with similar results.

Loss of SERK2, but not of SERK1, affects a subset of the OG-triggered responses that are independent from AvrPto and BAK1/BKK1

Next, the contribution of SERK1 and SERK2 in OG-triggered responses that emerged as totally independent from AvrPto, BAK1 and BKK1, i.e. induction of the expression of *PHOSPHATE-INDUCED 1 (PHI1)* and the antagonism with auxin responses (Gravino *et al.*, 2017), was examined. Upon 15 and 30 minutes of treatment with OGs, the expression of *PHI1* was impaired in *serk2-1*, but not in *serk1-1*, relative to the wild type (Fig. 2A). Whether the auxin antagonistic activity of OGs is affected in *serk1-1* and *serk2-1* mutants was investigated by analyzing the expression of the auxin-regulated genes, *INDOLE-3-ACETIC ACID-INDUCED PROTEIN5 (IAA5)*, and *SMALL AUXIN UP RNA 16 (SAUR16)*, on 1 h of treatment with indole-3-acetic acid (IAA), or IAA + OGs. The expression of the two genes induced by IAA was comparable in the *serk* mutants and similar to that of the wild type. On IAA + OG co-treatment, both *serk* mutants showed a normal inhibition of IAA-induced expression of both genes (Fig. 2B).

Figure 2. Analysis of AvrPto- and BAK1/BKK1-independent OG-triggered immune responses in the *serk1-1* and *serk2-1* mutants. **A.** Expression of the indicated defense gene was analyzed by qRT-PCR in seedlings of wild type (Col-0), *serk1-1* and *serk2-1* after treatment with OGs ($50 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) at the indicated time points. Transcripts levels are shown as the mean of at least three independent experiments (\pm SE; $n = 20$ in each experiment) normalized to *UBQ5* expression. Asterisks indicate statistically significant differences between mutant and wild-type samples at the indicated time points, according to Student's *t* test (*, $P < 0.05$). **B.** Expression of the indicated auxin-regulated genes analyzed by qRT-PCR in seedlings of wild Col-0, *serk1-1* and *serk2-1* after 1 h of treatment with H₂O, IAA ($1.5 \mu\text{M}$) or IAA+OGs. Transcripts levels are shown as the mean of at least three independent experiments (\pm SE; $n = 20$ in each experiment) normalized to *UBQ5* expression. Asterisks indicate statistically significant differences between co-treatment with IAA + OGs and treatment with IAA alone, according to Student's *t* test (*, $P < 0.05$; **, $P < 0.01$). In A and B, experiments were repeated three times with similar results.

Loss of SERK2, but not of SERK1, affects a subset of the OG-triggered responses that are affected by AvrPto and require BAK1/BKK1

The presence of AvrPto as well as the loss of both BAK1 and BKK1 have been shown to affect protection against *B. cinerea*, ROS production, callose deposition, and upregulation of the defense genes *FLG22-INDUCED RECEPTOR-LIKE KINASE 1 (FRK1)*, *PLANT DEFENSIN 1.2 (PDF1.2)* and *PATHOGENESIS-RELATED GENE 1 (PRI)* (Gravino *et al.*, 2017). We evaluated the contribution of SERK1 and SERK2 also in these responses. Both the *serk1-1* and *serk2-1* single mutants showed no significant alteration of the OG-induced ROS production, callose deposition and protection against *B. cinerea* (Fig. 3A, B and C). Instead, the OG-induced expression of *FRK1*, chosen as representative of the three genes, was affected in the *serk2-1*, but not *serk1-1*, as compared to wild type Col-0 (Fig. 3D).

Figure 3. Analysis of AvrPto- and BAK1/BKK1-dependent OG-triggered immune responses in the *serk1-1* and *serk2-1* mutants. **A.** ROS production, expressed in relative light units (RLUs), was measured in leaf discs of wild type (Col-0), *serk1-1* and *serk2-1* plants during elicitation with OGs. Results are average \pm SE (n = 12). **B.** Callose deposition visualized by aniline blue staining in leaves of Col-0, *serk1-1* and *serk2-1* 24 h after syringe-infiltration with water or OGs. Results are average \pm SE (n = 12). **C.** Col-0, *serk1-1* and *serk2-1* plants were sprayed with water or OGs or and, after 24 h, leaves were inoculated with *B. cinerea* spores. Lesion areas were measured at 48 hpi. Results are average \pm SE (n = 20 lesions). Asterisks indicate statistically significant differences between treatment with water and treatment with OGs in each genotype, according to Student's *t* test (*, $P < 0.05$). **D.** Expression of the indicated defense gene was analyzed by qRT-PCR in seedlings of Col-0, *serk1-1* and *serk2-1* after treatment with OGs (50 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) at the indicated time points. Transcripts levels are shown as the mean of at least three independent experiments (\pm SE; n = 20 in each experiment) normalized to *UBQ5* expression. Asterisks indicate statistically significant differences between mutant and wild-type samples at the indicated time points, according to Student's *t* test (*, $P < 0.05$). In A, B, C and D, experiments were repeated three times with similar results.

Loss of AGB1 differentially impairs immune response induced by OGs

AGB1 has been shown to mediate immune responses to MAMPs (Ishikawa, 2009; Liu *et al.*, 2013), but its role in OG signaling has never been investigated. Early and late responses that are triggered by OGs (Gravino *et al.*, 2017) were therefore analyzed in *agb1-2* mutant (see molecular characterization in Fig. S1C in the next material and methods section) compared to the Col-0 wild type.

The levels of phosphorylated MPK3 and MPK6 in mutant and wild-type seedlings 5 and 10 min were examined after treatment by western blot analysis, using a commercial antibody generated against the human homologues of these MAPKs (α -p44/p42). In response to OGs, the activation of MPK3 and MPK6 was not affected, rather appeared slightly enhanced, in the *agb1-2* mutant compared with the wild type (Fig. 4A).

OG-induced extracellular production of hydrogen peroxide by seedlings was analyzed over a period of 6 hours by a luminescence-based assay (Bisceglia N.G. *et al.*, 2015). In the wild type seedlings two oxidative bursts were observed: the first within 25 minutes and the second starting from 90 minutes. In the *agb1-2* mutant the first burst, but not the second, was found to be severely affected compared with that of the wild type (Fig. 4B). These results suggest that AGB1 is required for the early, but not late, OG-induced H₂O₂ production.

The expression of defense genes that, after OG treatment, reach a maximum within 1 h, i.e. *PHI1*, *FLG22-INDUCED RECEPTOR-LIKE KINASE 1 (FRK1)*, *CYTOCHROME P450 (CYP81F2)* and *RETICULINE-OXIDASE HOMOLOGUE (RET-OX)* (Gravino *et al.*, 2017), was analyzed in a time course up to 30 min by quantitative reverse transcription-polymerase chain reaction (qRT-PCR). In addition, the expression of a late gene that, after elicitor treatment, reaches maximal induction at about 3 hours, i.e. *PHYTOALEXIN DEFICIENT 3 (PAD3)* (Gravino *et al.*, 2017), was analyzed in a time course up to 3 hours. In *agb1-2*, the expression of *PHI1*, *RET-OX*, *FRK1* and *CYP81F2*, was reduced in response to OGs at 15 min, and not altered at 30 min, compared with the wild type (Fig. 5). Instead, the expression of *PAD3* induced by OGs was not affected in *agb1-2*, compared with wild type, at all time points analyzed (Fig. 5). These results suggest that AGB1 is differentially required for the expression of a set of OG-induced defense genes. All the results obtained with the *serk2* and *agb1* mutants, as well as the previously results with the AvrPto plants and the *bak1 bkk1* mutant (Gravino *et al.*, 2017), are summarized in figure 6.

Figure 4. Analysis of OG-triggered MAPK activation and ROS production in the *agb1-2* seedlings. **A.** Levels of phosphorylated MPK3 and MPK6 (pMPK3 and pMPK6) in wild type (Col-0) and *agb1-2* after elicitation with OGs ($50 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) at the indicated time points were determined by immunoblot analysis using an anti-p44/42-ERK antibody (top panels). Levels of MPK3 and MPK6 total proteins were determined using specific antibodies (bottom panels). The identity of individual MAP kinases, as determined by size, is indicated by arrows. **B.** ROS production, expressed in relative light units (RLUs), was measured by a luminescence-based assay in seedlings of Col-0 and *agb1-2* during elicitation with water or OGs ($100 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$), from 0 to 1 h (left panel) and from 1 to 6 h (right panel). Results are average ($n = 8$). In A and B, experiments were repeated three times with similar results.

Figure 5. Analysis of OG-triggered defense gene expression in the *agb1-2* seedlings. Expression of the indicated defense genes was analyzed by qRT-PCR in seedlings of *Col-0* and *agb1-2* after treatment with OGs (50 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) at the indicated time points. Transcripts levels are shown as the mean of at least three independent experiments (\pm SE; $n = 20$ in each experiment) normalized to *UBQ5* expression. Asterisks indicate statistically significant differences between mutant and wild-type samples at the indicated time points, according to Student's *t* test (*, $P < 0.05$; **, $P < 0.01$). Experiments were repeated three times with similar results.

Figure 6. Subsets of OG responses are defined by the differential requirement of SERK co-receptors and AGB1, and sensitivity to AvrPto. On the left of each box, the icon indicates involvement; ?, not yet determined. The letter "e" inside the box indicates that only the early phase of the response is affected in a time course up to 3 h. It is worth of note that the presence of AGB1 appears to negatively regulate MAPKs (see Fig. 4A).

5.4 DISCUSSION

This work deepens our understanding of OG signaling by demonstrating an important role of the pattern recognition co-receptor SERK2 as well as the G-protein AGB1. Our hypothesis that other SERKs may be required for the responses that are AvrPto-dependent and BAK1/BKK1-independent has been confirmed, with the exception of one response, which is the upregulation of *PAD3*. However, this type of response may require the concomitant contribute of SERK2, BAK1 and BKK1, and a role of SERKs in this type of response cannot be ruled out. Interestingly, among the responses depending on both AvrPto and BAK1/BKK1, the upregulation of *FRK1* is reduced by > 75% by the presence of AvrPto and by $\leq 75\%$ by the concomitant loss of BAK1 and BKK1 (Gravino *et al.*, 2017). Since SERK2 also participates in this response at $\sim 50\%$, although only in the very early stages, probably the simultaneous lack of SERK2, BAK1 and BKK1 could have an effect similar to that of AvrPto. In the hypothesis that SERK2, BAK1 and BKK1 may have a redundant role in the response to OGs, the aforementioned results suggest that direct targets of AvrPto are the co-receptors SERKs, as proposed previously (Shan *et al.*, 2008), and that a single OG perception complex comprising the three SERKs that is targeted by AvrPto may exist.

However, the existence of OG responses that are independent by AvrPto and notwithstanding require SERK2, i.e. *PHI1* upregulation, suggests that different types of perception/transduction complexes mediate OG signaling, not all necessarily targeted by AvrPto, and that AvrPto suppresses plant immunity by targeting receptor kinases, as proposed for FLS2, ELONGATION FACTOR-TU (EF-Tu) RECEPTOR (EFR) and CHITIN ELICITOR RECEPTOR KINASE 1 (CERK1) (Xiang *et al.*, 2008; Gimenez-Ibanez *et al.*, 2009). Whether WAK1, the only OG receptor identified so far, interacts with AvrPto or BAK1, BKK1 and SERK2 is not yet known and, in general, none of the five WAK family members has been identified to date among the interactors of either AvrPto or BAK1 (Bogdanove and Martin, 2000; Halter *et al.*, 2014). Moreover, OG-auxin antagonism is independent not only of SERK1, SERK2, BAK1 and BKK1, but also of AvrPto, suggesting that it may be downstream of receptor/co-receptors unique to the OG perception/signaling pathway.

The *Arabidopsis thaliana* SERK family consists of five LRR-RLKs with diverse functions such as brassinosteroid insensitive 1 (BRI1)-mediated brassinosteroids (BRs) perception, development and innate immunity (Ma *et al.*, 2016). In *Arabidopsis*, SERK1, BAK1 and BKK1 form a complex with the LRR-LRK BRI1 for the perception of the steroid hormone BRs and regulation of BR-induced root growth, light response, cell elongation, and stress response (Li *et al.*, 2002; Nam and Li, 2002; Karlova *et al.*, 2006; He *et al.*, 2007). It appears that SERK2 is not involved in BR signaling (Gou *et al.*, 2012b). A recent report indicated that SERK5 in the *Landsberg erecta* ecotype also has an important role in BR signaling and associates with BRI1 (Wu *et al.*, 2015). SERK1, SERK2 and BAK1 form a complex with the LRR-LRK PHYTOSULFOKINE (PSK) RECEPTOR 1 (PSKR1) for the perception of PHYTOSULFOKINE-alpha (PSK), a sulfated and secreted peptide, and regulation of PSK-induced root growth, and cell expansion (Ladwig *et al.*, 2015; Wang *et al.*, 2015). SERK1, SERK2, BAK1 and BKK1 form a complex with the LRR-LRKs ERECTA (ER) and ER-LIKE 1 (ERL1) for the perception of the peptide EPIDERMAL PATTERNING FACTORS (EPFs) and regulation of EPF-induced stomatal patterning (Meng *et al.*, 2015). SERK1 and SERK2, which may associate with TAPETUM DETERMINANT 1 (TPD1)-EXCESS MICROSPOROXYTES 1 (EMS1) ligand-receptor complex, regulate male gametophyte development (Albrecht *et al.*, 2005; Colcombet *et al.*, 2005). SERK1, SERK2, BAK1 and BKK1 form a complex with the LRR-LRKs HAESA (HAE) and HAE-LIKE 2 (HSL2) for the perception of the peptide INFLORESCENCE DEFICIENT IN ABSCISSION (IDA) and regulation of IDA-induced floral organ abscission (Meng *et al.*, 2016; Santiago *et al.*, 2016). In plant immunity, BAK1 and BKK1 regulate signaling activated by multiple RLKs and Receptor Like Proteins (RLPs) (Ma *et al.*, 2016). A role of SERK1 and SERK2 in the FLS2- and EFR-triggered immunity was ruled out, since *flg22-*

or EF-Tu-derived peptide elf18-induced ROS production and growth inhibition was not affected in the *serk1* or *serk2* single mutants (Roux *et al.*, 2011). Moreover, redundancy effects with other SERKs have been excluded as *serk1* or *serk2* mutations do not enhance the phenotype of *bak1-5* mutants (Roux *et al.*, 2011). Thus, the role of SERK2 in the OG signaling described here represents for SERK2 the first example of involvement in immunity described so far.

This work also shows that the G protein AGB1 play a role in the early OG-triggered immunity. In Arabidopsis, heterotrimeric G complexes contain canonical G α protein (GPA1), G β protein (AGB1), G γ proteins (AGG1 or AGG2) and non-canonical G γ protein (AGG3). Moreover they contain extra-large G α proteins (XLG1, XLG2 or XLG3) (Urano *et al.*, 2012). Heterotrimeric G proteins have been implicated in the regulation of a wide range of biological processes, including stress responses and developmental processes (Urano and Jones, 2014). According to the classic paradigm, active G proteins dissociate into two functional signaling elements, the G α subunit and the G $\beta\gamma$ dimer. The heterotrimeric G proteins required for FLS2 signaling include the non-canonical G α proteins XLG2/3, G β protein AGB1, and G γ proteins AGG1/2 (Ishikawa, 2009; Liu *et al.*, 2013; Torres *et al.*, 2013; Liang *et al.*, 2016). However these proteins appear to be implicated in the flg22-triggered ROS production and protection against Pst, but to not play a major role in the activation of MPK3 and MPK6, as well as transcriptional reprogramming of MAPK-(in)dependent genes. On the contrary, the activation of MPK3 and MPK6 triggered the proteases PrpL and ArgC from *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Xanthomonas campestris*, respectively, requires both GPA1 and AGB1, as well as RECEPTOR FOR ACTIVATED C KINASE 1 (RACK1), which functions as a scaffold that binds to AGB1 as well as to all three tiers of the MAPK cascade (Cheng *et al.*, 2015; Cheng, 2016), thereby linking upstream G protein signaling to downstream activation of a MAPK cascade.

The loss of AGB1 has a dual effect in the response of OGs; on one side, potentiates the activation of MPK3 and MPK6, on the other side, leads to a reduction of the early ROS production and expression of a set of defense genes, i.e. *PHI1*, *RET-OX*, *FRK1*, *CYP81F2*, indicating that these genes are activated independently of MAPK cascade and suggesting the existence of parallel pathways downstream of OG perception. Accordingly, the OG- or flg22-triggered expression of *PHI1* has been described to be dependent on CDPK pathway (Boudsocq *et al.*, 2010; Gravino *et al.*, 2015), independently of MAPK pathway (Boudsocq *et al.*, 2010; Galletti *et al.*, 2011). On the contrary, the OG- or flg22-triggered expression of *RET-OX*, *FRK1* and *CYP81F2* has been described to be dependent on both MAPK and CDPK pathways (Boudsocq *et al.*, 2010; Galletti *et al.*, 2011). Moreover, the reduced ROS production and the concomitant enhanced MAPK activation observed in the *agb1* mutant in response to OGs indicate that ROS production is not required for MAPK activation, as previously described for flg22 (Meszaros *et al.*, 2006). Interestingly, both WALL-ASSOCIATED KINASE-LIKE KINASE 22 (WAKL22) and AGB1 are involved in resistance to the necrotrophic fungus *Fusarium oxysporum* (Diener and Ausubel, 2005; Trusov *et al.*, 2006; Trusov *et al.*, 2009). Moreover, *agb1* mutant was found to have a notable reduction in the levels of pectic backbone epitopes (homogalacturonan, rhamnogalacturonan I) (Klopffleisch *et al.*, 2011).

Among the danger signals so far characterized, the complexity of OG signaling is unprecedented. Such a complexity has long been envisioned, as no mutants have been identified to date that are completely insensitive to these elicitors. Moreover, a redundant role of the different WAK members in OG perception is likely, but not yet demonstrated, although WAK2, in addition to WAK1, can bind in vitro OGs and pectin (Decreux and Messiaen, 2005; Decreux *et al.*, 2006; Kohorn *et al.*, 2012).

The multiplicity of perception/transduction complexes for OGs, as suggested by this work, may recall the complexity of the homogalacturonan/OG vertebrate analogue signaling system. This involves the extracellular matrix component hyaluronan (HA) and its fragments, which are produced after tissue injury or on enzymatic activity of hyaluronidases, either synthesized by animal cells or secreted by pathogens (Kreil, 1995), and induce different inflammatory-related

responses in different cell types and tissues, so that HA is now thought to be an immune regulator in human diseases (Jiang *et al.*, 2011). Both HA and HA fragments are bound by different and numerous proteins, both membrane linked and extracellular, such as the PRRs, Toll-like receptors TLR2 and TLR4, CD44, a polymorphic type I trans membrane glycoprotein, known as the major cell-surface HA-binding protein, RHAMM (receptor for HA-mediated motility expressed protein) and BREVICAN [also called BEHAB, for brain enriched hyaluronan binding (Jiang *et al.*, 2011; Lee-Sayer *et al.*, 2015)]. In this case, signaling results from the specific combination of different elements depending on the tissue and cell type, and from the situation that needs to be perceived, e.g. infectious versus non- infectious tissue injury. Signaling mediated by animal PRRs, including the different TLRs, is highly complex (Tan *et al.*, 2014) and, in most cases, involves combinatorial and/or sequential stimulation of different perception/transduction complexes, allowing the activation of different immune responses in a synergistic manner, thus amplifying the signal, and/or in a compensatory manner, providing robustness to the signaling system. The combined action of different elements also allows a fine tuning of the immune response, in order to discriminate between pathogenic and non-pathogenic microbes and, in general, to efficiently respond to different types of pathogen (Kim *et al.*, 2014). A similar complexity may exist in signaling mediated by homogalacturonan/OGs.

5.5 MATERIALS AND METHODS

Plant materials and growth conditions

Arabidopsis (*Arabidopsis thaliana*) Columbia-0 (Col-0) wild-type seeds were purchased from Lehle Seeds. The *serk1-1* and *serk2-1* single knock-out lines (in Col-0 background) were kindly provided by Libo Shan (Department of Plant Pathology and Microbiology, Institute for Plant Genomics and Biotechnology, Texas A&M University, College Station, TX, 77843, USA). The *agbl-2* single knock-out line (in Col-0 background) was kindly provided by Saskia Hogenhout (Department of Crop Genetics, John Innes Centre, Norwich Research Park, Norwich, NR4 7UH, United Kingdom).

For treatments of seedlings, after surface sterilization, seeds were germinated in multiwell plates (approximately 10 seeds/well) containing 2 ml per well of ½ Murashige and Skoog (MS/2) medium (Duchefa Biochemie) supplemented with 0.5% sucrose (CARLO ERBA Reagents). Plates were incubated at 22 °C with a 16-h light/8-h dark cycle at a light intensity of 120 $\mu\text{E}\cdot\text{m}^2\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$. After 9 days, the medium was adjusted to a final volume of 1 ml and, after one additional day, plants were treated with elicitors, as described below.

ROS measurements were performed on leaf discs from 4-weeks-old plants grown at 22 °C under a 12-h light/12-h dark cycle at a light intensity of 120 $\mu\text{E}\cdot\text{m}^2\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$ or on 9-days-old seedlings grown at 22 °C under a 16-h light/8-h dark cycle at a light intensity of 120 $\mu\text{E}\cdot\text{m}^2\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$, as described below. OGs used in this work are the same of those previously described (Gravino *et al.*, 2017).

qRT-PCR assays

For defense genes expression analyses, 10-day-old seedlings were treated with OG (50 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) for 0, 15, 30, 60 or 180 min. For the analysis of the auxin antagonistic action of OGs, seedlings were treated with indol-3-acetic acid (IAA, 1.5 μM), IAA + OGs (50 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$), or water for 1 hour. Seedlings were harvested in 2-ml Eppendorf tubes, snap frozen in liquid nitrogen, and ground to a fine powder using a ball mill (MM301 Retsch). Total RNA was extracted from 3 independent replicates, each composed by 10 seedlings, with Isol-RNA Lysis Reagent (5 Prime) according to the manufacturer's protocol. Total RNA (1 μg) was treated with RQ1 DNase (Promega) and first-strand cDNA was synthesized using ImProm-II reverse transcriptase (Promega) according to the manufacturer's instructions. Quantitative RT-PCR analysis was performed by using a CFX96 Real-Time System (Bio-Rad). Single strand cDNA (corresponding to 50 ng of total RNA) was amplified in a 20- μl -reaction containing 1X GoTaq qPCR Master Mix (Promega) and 0.5 μM of each primer. Three technical replicates were performed for each sample and data analysis was done using LinRegPCR software. Expression levels of each gene, relative to *ubiquitin 5* (*UBQ5*), were determined using a modification of the Pfaffl method (Pfaffl, 2001), as previously described (Ferrari *et al.*, 2006). Primer sequences are shown in Table S1. Experiments were repeated at least three times on different days to generate independent biological replicates.

MAP kinase assays

Ten-days-old seedlings were treated with OGs (50 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) for 0, 5, 10, or 15 minutes. Seedlings were harvested in 2-ml Eppendorf tubes, snap frozen in liquid nitrogen, and ground to a fine powder using a ball mill (MM301 Retsch). Protein extraction buffer (50 mM Tris-HCl pH 7.5, 200 mM NaCl, 1 mM EDTA, 10% glycerol, 1% Tween-20, 1 mM DTT, 1 mM PMSF, 1%

phosphatase inhibitor cocktail [Sigma-Aldrich] and 1% protease inhibitor cocktail [Sigma-Aldrich]) was added. Homogenates were clarified by centrifugation at 13,000 x g for 30 minutes at 4 °C and supernatants were collected. Proteins (60 µg) were diluted with loading buffer and separated on 7.5% (wt/v) SDS-PAGE gels and transferred to a nitrocellulose membrane using the Trans-Blot[®] Turbo[™] Transfer System (BioRad) following manufacturer's instructions. Blotted membranes were blocked by incubation in 5% (w/v) BSA in TBS-Tween (0.2%) for 1 hour, and incubated overnight with anti-p42/44 MAPK primary antibodies (1:2500; Cell Signaling Technology). After incubation with anti-rabbit-HRP secondary antibody (1:8000, Sigma-Aldrich) for 1 hour, activated MAP kinases were detected using Immobilon Western Chemiluminescent HRP Substrate (Millipore) and ChemiDoc MP imaging system (BIORAD). Protein loading was visualized by stripping and re-probing the membrane with a mix of anti-MPK3 (1:2500) and anti-MPK6 (1:10000) primary antibodies (Sigma Aldrich) for 1 hour, followed by incubation with anti-rabbit-HRP secondary antibody for 1 hour and detection as described before. Experiments were repeated at least three times on different days to generate independent biological replicates.

ROS burst assays

H₂O₂ produced by leaf discs was measured by a luminol-based assay as previously described (Bisceglia N.G. *et al.*, 2015). Briefly, leaf discs (0.125 cm²) were obtained from adult plants, washed for 2 h with water and left to recover in a 96-well titer plate (one disc/well). After about 12 h, discs were vacuum infiltrated with the OG solution (200 µg ml⁻¹) or water, as a control, for 2 min before addition of a solution of luminol (Sigma-Aldrich; 30 g ml⁻¹) and horseradish peroxidase (Sigma-Aldrich; 20 g ml⁻¹). Plates were analyzed for 40 min using a GloMax 96 microplate luminometer with dual injectors (Promega) and a signal integration time of 1 s. Luminescence was expressed in Relative Light Units.

For burst in seedlings, Arabidopsis seedlings were grown for 8 days in MS liquid medium (one seedling per 200 µl of medium in wells of 96-well-plates). The medium was removed from the wells and replaced with 200 µl of distilled water. On day 9, 5 µL of horseradish peroxidase and luminol solution containing GroEx (15 µg ml⁻¹) or PBS control was added to each well. Luminescence was captured using a Photech camera system and analyzed using company software and Microsoft Office Excel.

Experiments were repeated at least three times on different days to generate independent biological replicates.

Callose assays

Leaves from adult plants were infiltrated with water or OG solution (200 µg ml⁻¹) using a needleless syringe and, after 24 h, were detached from plants. Leaves were cleared and dehydrated with 100% boiling ethanol. Leaves were fixed in an acetic acid:ethanol (1:3) solution for 2 h, sequentially incubated for 15 min in 75% ethanol, in 50% ethanol, and in 150 mM phosphate buffer, pH 8.0, and then stained for 1 h in 150 mM phosphate buffer, pH 8.0, containing 0.01% (w/v) aniline blue. After staining, leaves were mounted in 10% glycerol and examined by UV epifluorescence using an Axioskop 2 plus microscope (Zeiss). Images were taken with a ProgRes C10 3.3 MegaPixel digital color camera (Jenoptik). Callose quantification was performed by ImageJ software. Experiments were repeated at least three times on different days to generate independent biological replicates.

Botrytis cinerea protection assays

Four-weeks-old intact rosette were sprayed with water or OGs (200 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$), and after 24 h, fully expanded leaves were detached from adult plants, placed in Petri dishes containing 0.8% (w/v) plant agar with the petiole embedded in the medium. Inoculation with *Botrytis cinerea* was performed by placing 5- μl drops of a conidiospore suspension ($5 \times 10^5 \text{ ml}^{-1}$) in potato dextrose broth (PDB, Difco; 24 g L^{-1}) regularly spaced on each side of the middle vein. Plates were incubated at 22 °C with a 12 h photoperiod. High humidity was maintained by covering the plates with a clear plastic lid. Lesion area was determined 48 h after inoculation by ImageJ. Experiments were repeated at least three times on different days to generate independent biological replicates.

Supplemental data

Supplemental Table S1. List of primer sequences used in this study.

Gene	AGI No	Forward primer (5'-3')	Reverse primer (5'-3')
<i>RETOX</i>	<i>At1g26380</i>	AGGTTCTCGAACCCCTAACAACA	GCACAGACGACACGTAAGAAAG
<i>FRK1</i>	<i>At2g19190</i>	TTAAACTCGACGATGCAACA	GATGGAAGTTTTCCCGTTTT
<i>CYP81F2</i>	<i>At5g57220</i>	GTGAAAGCACTAGGCGAAGC	ATCCGTTCCAGCTAGCATCA
<i>PHI1</i>	<i>At1g35140</i>	TTGGTTTACGCGGGATGGTG	ACTCCAGTACAAGCCGATCC
<i>PAD3</i>	<i>At3g26830</i>	CCGGTGAATCTTGAGAGAGCC	GATCAGCTCGGTCATTCCCC
<i>PGIP1</i>	<i>At5g06860</i>	TCTTGAACCTTAGCAGGAAC	GAGAGCTGGTTATGTGATAG
<i>UBQ5</i>	<i>At3g62250</i>	GTTAAGCTCGCTGTTCTTCAGT	TCAAGCTTCAACTCCTTCTTTC

Figure S1. Characterization of the *serk1-1*, *serk1-2* and *agb1-2* mutants. Genotype analysis of the *serk1-1* (A), *serk1-2* (B) and *agb1-2* (C) T-DNA insertion mutants. The *SERK1*, *SERK2* and *AGB1* genes were analyzed by PCR in wild-type (Col-0) and mutant seedlings, using gene-specific primers flanking the left and the right borders of T-DNA insertions and genomic DNA as a template.

6. ARABIDOPSIS THALIANA RESISTANCE AGAINST MYZUS PERSICAE IS REGULATED BY OLIGOGALACTURONIDES AND PECTIN METHYLESTERIFICATION

6.1 SUMMARY

Plants are engaged in a continuous co-evolutionary struggle for dominance with their pathogens. The cell wall is a major line of defense in plants that prevents invasion by fungal and bacterial pathogens. Emerging evidence indicates that plant cells harbor sophisticated mechanisms for sensing the alteration of cell wall integrity during biotic stress. For instance, they perceive endogenous molecules generated and/or released as a consequence of the cellular damage caused by pathogens, e.g. the so-called damage-associated molecular patterns (DAMPs). A well-known class of DAMPs is represented by oligogalacturonides (OGs), pectin-derived oligosaccharides made of α -1,4-linked galacturonic acid that derive from the partial hydrolysis of homogalacturonan. OGs have a pivotal role in defense against fungal and bacterial pathogens; however, their role in defense against insects is not yet clear. Aphids are sap-feeding insects of the order *Hemiptera* and are among the most destructive pests in agriculture. The green peach aphid/peach-potato aphid *Myzus persicae* is a species with a broad host range and colonizes hundreds of plants species in over 40 plant families, including brassicas. In this work we show that OGs enhance *Arabidopsis* resistance against *M. persicae* and that the aphid effector Mp10 inhibits the OG-triggered immunity. Moreover our results indicate that plant resistance against *M. persicae* is negatively regulated by the glycine-rich protein GRP3, a negative regulator of OG responses, and is reduced in mutant/transgenic plants with a high degree of pectin methyl esterification.

6.2 INTRODUCTION

As sessile organisms, plants are continually exposed to pathogens and pests. Beyond the cuticle layer, the plant cell wall represents a mechanical barrier against pathogen invasions (Bellincampi *et al.*, 2014; Serrano *et al.*, 2014; Houston *et al.*, 2016). The cell wall is a complex structure, mainly composed of polysaccharides, in which a network of cellulose and hemicellulose is embedded in a cohesive matrix of pectin and proteins (Ridley *et al.*, 2001). To breach the wall pathogens secrete several cell wall degrading enzymes (CWDEs) belonging to multiple families (Pauchet *et al.*, 2010; Kubicek *et al.*, 2014; Antony *et al.*, 2017).

One of the strategies used by plants to limit the degradation of the cell wall by pathogen CWDEs is the expression of protein inhibitors in the apoplast. The interaction between pathogen polygalacturonases (PGs), i.e. hydrolytic enzymes that depolymerize the homogalacturonan component of pectin, and plant polygalacturonase inhibiting proteins (PGIPs) slows down the degradation of cell wall and favors the accumulation of elicitor-active oligogalacturonides in the apoplast that act as damage-associated molecular patterns (DAMPs) (De Lorenzo *et al.*, 1994; De Lorenzo and Ferrari, 2002; D'Ovidio *et al.*, 2004; Di Matteo *et al.*, 2006; Benedetti *et al.*, 2015; Cervone *et al.*, 2015). OGs are perceived by specific plasma membrane-localized pattern recognition receptors (PRRs), e.g. the receptor WALL ASSOCIATED KINASE 1 (WAK1) (Brutus *et al.*, 2010), to activate PRR-triggered immunity (PTI) (Mathieu *et al.*, 1991; Shibuya and Minami, 2001; Moscatiello *et al.*, 2006; Galletti *et al.*, 2009; Vallarino and Osorio, 2012; Ferrari *et al.*, 2013). The immunity triggered by OGs confers resistance against the necrotrophic fungus *Botrytis cinerea* in grapevine (*Vitis vinifera*) and Arabidopsis (*Arabidopsis thaliana*) (Aziz *et al.*, 2004; Aziz *et al.*, 2007; Galletti *et al.*, 2008; Suarez *et al.*, 2013; Benedetti *et al.*, 2015; Davidsson *et al.*, 2017), through PHYTOALEXIN DEFICIENT 3 (PAD3)-mediated camalexin production (Ferrari *et al.*, 2007), and signaling pathways mediated by WAK1 (Brutus *et al.*, 2010), mitogen activated protein kinases (MAPKs) (Galletti *et al.*, 2011; Savatin *et al.*, 2014a), calcium-dependent protein kinases (CDPKs), somatic embryogenesis receptor kinases (SERKs), Pep receptors (PEPRs) and ethylene (Gravino *et al.*, 2015; Gravino *et al.*, 2017). Moreover, an apoplastic glycine rich protein (GRP3) interacts with WAK1 (Park *et al.*, 2001; Anderson *et al.*, 2001), and negatively regulates OG-triggered immunity and plant resistance against *B. cinerea* (Gramegna *et al.*, 2016). The immunity triggered by OGs confers plant resistance also against bacterial pathogens, since OGs have been shown to protect Arabidopsis, tobacco and potato plants against the biotroph *Pseudomonas syringae* pv. *tomato* (Pst) and the necrotroph *Pectobacterium carotovorum* (Wegener *et al.*, 1996; Weber *et al.*, 1996; Baker *et al.*, 1990; Davidsson *et al.*, 2013; Benedetti *et al.*, 2015; Davidsson *et al.*, 2017).

Besides signaling, the cell wall influences the outcome of plant-pathogen infection also through dynamic changes in its architecture (Lionetti *et al.*, 2012). The cell walls containing a high methylesterification degree (DM) of pectin are somewhat protected against the action of pathogen-secreted CWDEs (Arancibia and Motsenbocker, 2006). Pectin is synthesized in a highly methyl esterified form and is de-esterified *in muro* by pectin methyl esterases (PMEs). The loss of function of a pectin methyl esterase (PME3) and the over expression of pectin methyl esterase inhibitors (PMEIs) increase pectin DM and limit *B. cinerea* and *P. carotovorum* disease symptoms in Arabidopsis and wheat (Lionetti *et al.*, 2007; Raiola *et al.*, 2011; Volpi *et al.*, 2011). Moreover, a high DM of pectin correlates to plant resistance against the aphid *Schizaphis graminum*, the biotrophic fungus *Colletotrichum lindemuthianum*, and the necrotrophic bacterium *Ralstonia solanacearum* (Boudart *et al.*, 1998; Wydra and Berl, 2006; Senechal *et al.*, 2014).

Aphids are sap-feeding insects and are among the most destructive pests in agriculture; these insects cause direct feeding damage and indirectly via the transmission of diverse plant viruses (Hogenhout *et al.*, 2008). The feeding behavior of aphids contributes to these insects being efficient virus vectors. The aphid stinging-sucking mouthparts (called stylets) navigate between cells on their way to phloem sieve cells for long-term feeding (Tjallingii, 2006). During this navigation, however, the stylets probe mesophyll cells and other cell types. Each stylet probe

involves a penetration of cell wall and membrane, injection of saliva (and virus particles) into the cell cytoplasm, acquisition of some cell cytoplasm (and viruses if the plant is infected), and finally, retraction of the stylet, which may navigate to another cell for a next probe or start a feeding site elsewhere (Martin *et al.*, 1997).

Aphid saliva contains several proteins with diverse enzymatic activities (Miles, 1965; Harmel *et al.*, 2008), such as PMEases and PGs (Cherqui and Tjallingii, 2000) that might influence the architecture of plant cell wall and contribute to the release of active OGs (Will and van Bel, 2008; Foyer *et al.*, 2016). It also contains a number of effectors that modulate plant processes to the benefit of these insects (Will *et al.*, 2007; Mutti *et al.*, 2008; Atamian *et al.*, 2013; Pitino and Hogenhout, 2013; Elzinga *et al.*, 2014; Naessens *et al.*, 2015; Kettles and Kaloshian, 2016; Peng *et al.*, 2016; Rodriguez *et al.*, 2017) and highly conserved molecules, i.e. pathogen-associated molecular patterns (PAMPs), which are recognized by hosts to activate PTI (De Vos and Jander, 2009; Prince *et al.*, 2014; Chaudhary *et al.*, 2014). Mp10 is one of a number of candidate effector proteins that have been identified. It is delivered into the cytoplasm of mesophyll cells during aphid feeding (Mugford *et al.*, 2016) and was found to suppress PTI and elicit an effector-triggered immunity-type response, leading to chlorosis and activation of jasmonic acid and salicylic acid signaling pathways (Bos *et al.*, 2010; Rodriguez *et al.*, 2014). As with microbial pathogens, aphids are detected in a BRASSINOSTEROID INSENSITIVE 1-ASSOCIATED RECEPTOR KINASE 1 (BAK1)-dependent manner, although the PRRs involved have remained elusive, with FLAGELLIN-SENSITIVE2 (FLS2), EF-TU RECEPTOR (EFR), CHITIN ELICITOR RECEPTOR KINASE 1 (CERK1), PEP1 RECEPTOR 1 (PEPR1), and PEPR2 not appearing to be involved (Prince *et al.*, 2014; Chaudhary *et al.*, 2014; Vincent *et al.*, 2017).

The green peach aphid/peach-potato aphid *Myzus persicae* is an excellent model organism for studying processes involved in plant resistance to insects, because this aphid species has a broad plant host range of over 40 plant families, including the model plant *A. thaliana* and brassicas. This allows the studying of basic defense processes in *A. thaliana* and subsequent translation of findings to crops, such as brassicas.

In this work we use *A. thaliana* to better understand the role of OGs and cell wall modifications in the plant response to *M. persicae*. Our results indicate that OGs increase plant resistance to *M. persicae* and that the aphid effector Mp10 inhibits the OG-triggered H₂O₂ production and expression of a set of defense genes. Moreover, we show that aphid performance is reduced in *grp3* loss-of-function mutants and increased in *pme3* null mutants, and in transgenic plants overexpressing *AtPMEI1* or *AtPMEI2*.

6.3 RESULTS

Oligogalacturonides induce resistance against *Myzus Persicae*

OGs have been shown to enhance plant resistance against fungal and bacterial pathogens (Aziz *et al.*, 2004; Ferrari *et al.*, 2007; Aziz *et al.*, 2007; Galletti *et al.*, 2008; Brutus *et al.*, 2010; Galletti *et al.*, 2011; Suarez *et al.*, 2013; Paparella *et al.*, 2014; Savatin *et al.*, 2014a; Benedetti *et al.*, 2015; Gravino *et al.*, 2015; Gramegna *et al.*, 2016; Davidsson *et al.*, 2017; Gravino *et al.*, 2017). In order to determine whether OGs enhance Arabidopsis resistance to aphids, wild-type Columbia-0 (Col-0) 5-weeks-old plants were infiltrated with mock (water) or OGs (200 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) solutions and, 24 hours after treatment, *Myzus persicae* adult aphids aged 8 days were caged in the infiltrated leaves. After 9 days, the fecundity of individual adult aphids on these plants was assessed by counting their offspring. Compared with mock infiltration, aphid fecundity was significantly reduced ($P < 0.05$, Student's *t*-test) in Col-0 Arabidopsis leaves infiltrated with OGs (Fig. 1A). This result indicates that OGs induce local resistance against *M. persicae* colonization in Arabidopsis plants.

The aphid effector Mp10 suppresses the OG-triggered ROS burst and defense gene induction

During aphid colonization attempt, OGs have been proposed to be released from the plant cell walls as a result of the action of pectinases secreted by the aphid stylet sheath (Cherqui and Tjallingii, 2000; Will and van Bel, 2008; Foyer *et al.*, 2016). As consequence, aphids would have evolved effectors to inhibit the OG-triggered immunity. Mp10 from *M. persicae* is one of a number of candidate effector proteins that have been identified in aphid saliva and was found to suppress the plant H_2O_2 production triggered by the bacterial flagellin-derived peptide/PAMP flg22 (Bos *et al.*, 2010; Rodriguez *et al.*, 2014).

To determine whether Mp10 can suppress OG-induced PTI, we analyzed PTI responses in wild type and two independent lines that express Mp10 under the control of a dexamethasone (Dex)-inducible promoter in Col-0 background (lines #7 and #9, see supplemental Fig. S1A), obtained from Saskia Hogenhout lab (John Innes Centre, UK). The oxidative burst response is an early response to OGs (Galletti *et al.*, 2008; Savatin *et al.*, 2014a; Gravino *et al.*, 2017) and is required for the plant resistance to aphids (Moloi and van der Westhuizen, 2006; Kusnierczyk *et al.*, 2008; Moloi and van der Westhuizen, 2008; Miller *et al.*, 2009; Sytykiewicz, 2016). To assess whether Mp10 suppresses the oxidative burst response induced by OGs, Arabidopsis seedlings of wild type Col-0 and Mp10 transgenic lines were challenged with OGs and the production of ROS was measured using a luminol-based assay (Bisceglia N.G. *et al.*, 2015). We found that the OG-induced oxidative burst was significantly reduced ($P < 0.01$, ANOVA with Tukey's HSD test) in both Mp10 lines pre-treated with Dex compared to Col-0 seedlings (Fig. 1B), whereas no difference was observed between Mp10 lines and Col-0 pre-treated with mock (DMSO) (see supplemental Fig. S2A).

We also examined the expression of two marker genes typically induced by OGs, flg22 and *M. persicae*-derived elicitors, i.e. *FLG22-INDUCED RECEPTOR-LIKE KINASE 1 (FRK1)*, *CYTOCHROME P450, FAMILY 81, SUBFAMILY F, POLYPEPTIDE 2 (CYP81F2)* (Denoux *et al.*, 2008; Prince *et al.*, 2014; Gravino *et al.*, 2017). We found that the OG-induced expression of *FRK1* and *CYP81F2* was significantly reduced ($P < 0.05$, Student's *t*-test) in both Mp10 lines pre-treated with Dex compared to Col-0 seedlings (Fig. 1C), whereas no difference was observed between Mp10 lines and Col-0 pre-treated with mock (DMSO) (see supplemental Fig. S2B).

These results indicate that the aphid effector Mp10 inhibits the ROS production and expression of a set of defense genes triggered by OGs.

Figure 1. The OG-triggered immunity protects *Arabidopsis* against *M. persicae* colonization and is suppressed by Mp10. **A.** *Arabidopsis* wild-type (Col-0) plants were infiltrated with water or OGs ($250 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) and, after 24 h, the leaves were infested with a single adult aphid and the number of offspring was determined after 9 d. Results are average \pm SE ($n = 5$). Asterisks indicate statistically significant differences between water- and OG-pretreated plants, according to Student's *t* test (*, $P < 0.05$). **B.** Total ROS production over 1 h, expressed in relative light units (RLUs), was measured by a luminescence-based assay in dexamethasone (DEX)-pretreated seedlings of Col-0 and *agb1-2* during elicitation with water or OGs ($100 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$). Results are average \pm SE ($n = 8$). Different letters above the bars indicate statistically significant differences between samples, as determined by analysis of variance (ANOVA) with Tukey's honestly significant difference (HSD) test ($P < 0.01$). **C.** Expression of the indicated defense genes was analyzed by qRT-PCR in DEX-pretreated seedlings of Col-0 and Mp10 (#7-5 and #9-5) after treatment with water or OGs ($25 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) for 1 h. Transcripts levels are shown as the mean of at least three independent experiments (\pm SE; $n = 20$ in each experiment) normalized to *GAPDH* expression. Asterisks indicate statistically significant differences between mutant and wild-type samples at the indicated time points, according to Student's *t* test (*, $P < 0.05$; **, $P < 0.01$). In A, B and C, experiments were repeated three times with similar results.

***GRP3* negatively regulates plant resistance against *Myzus persicae* colonization**

GRP3 has been shown to interact with the OG receptor WAK1 (Park *et al.*, 2001; Anderson *et al.*, 2001) and to negatively regulate immune responses to OGs, wounding and *B. cinerea* (Gramegna *et al.*, 2016). We investigated the role of *GRP3* in the plant resistance to *M. persicae*. Aphid performance was assessed in a *GRP3* loss-of-function mutant (*grp3*, see molecular characterization in supplemental Fig. S1B) and three homozygous independent transgenic lines (#4, #16 and #17) expressing a fusion of *GRP3* with the Red Fluorescent Protein (RFP) driven by the CaMV 35S promoter (35S:*GRP3-RFP*) in Col-0 background (Gramegna *et al.*, 2016), compared to the wild-type Col-0 Arabidopsis. Levels of *GRP3* (endogenous + transgene) transcripts were confirmed to be higher in lines 35S:*GRP3-RFP* #16 and #17, hereafter indicated as *GRP3*-OE plants, and similar in line #4, hereafter indicated as *GRP3* #4 plants, compared with those of the wild type (supplemental Fig. S1C). In our assay, 5-weeks-old plants were seeded with one nymph aged 24 hours. The nymphs were allowed to develop to adulthood and to produce offspring. The number of offspring produced was recorded as fecundity. In our experiment, aphid fecundity was significantly lower on *grp3* mutants relative to Col-0 ($P < 0.05$, ANOVA with Tukey's HSD test), but was unchanged on *GRP3*-OE and *GRP3* #4 plants (Fig. 2A). These data indicate that *GRP3* is a negative regulator of Arabidopsis resistance to *M. persicae*.

Both loss-of-function and overexpression of *GRP3* affect immune responses triggered by *Myzus persicae*-derived elicitors

To better understand the physiological role of *GRP3* in plant immunity activation in response to *M. persicae*, we analyzed the immune responses activated by aphid-derived elicitors (Prince *et al.*, 2014) in *GRP3* mutant/transgenic plants. Aphid-derived saliva, crude extracts, proteins < 10 kDa, and GroEL from the endosymbiont *Buchnera aphidicola* have been shown to trigger defense responses in plants (De Vos and Jander, 2009; Prince *et al.*, 2014; Chaudhary *et al.*, 2014). An extraction protocol was developed to obtain aphid protein extracts enriched in *Buchnera* GroEL (hereafter indicate as GroEx). The presence and enrichment of the elicitor GroEL in our fractions was assessed by western blot analysis (supplemental Fig. S3A). The characterization of GroEx in immunity activation showed that this extract induces MAPKs activation, defense gene up regulation, seedling growth inhibition, ROS production and protection against *M. persicae* in Col-0 Arabidopsis (supplemental Fig. S3B, C, D, E and F). The GroEx-triggered expression of *FRK1*, *CYP81F2* and *PAD3* was affected in *bak1-5* and *bak-5 bkk1-1* mutants compared to Col-0 wild type (supplemental Fig. S4). Moreover, the expression of *FRK1* and *PAD3*, was further downregulated in the triple mutant *serk2-1 bak1-5 bkk1-1* compared to the single and double mutants (supplemental Fig. S4). On contrary the expression of the three genes was unchanged in the *fls2 efr cerk1* triple mutant and in the *pepr1 pepr2* double mutant compared to Col-0 (supplemental Fig. S5). As expected, the defense genes expression was severely affected in the *fls2 efr cerk1* in response to flg22, elf18 or chitin, and in *pepr1 pepr2* in response to pep1 (supplemental Fig. 5). These results indicate that defense gene induction triggered by GroEx requires the co-receptor BAK1 independently from the receptors FLS2, EFR, CERK1 and PEPR1/2, as observed also for the aphid proteins < 10 kDa and GroEL (Prince *et al.*, 2014; Chaudhary *et al.*, 2014). Moreover, these results suggest that also SERK2 and BKK1 may play a role in the GroEx signaling, similarly to as described for the OGs [(Gravino *et al.*, 2017); this work].

Whether *GRP3* is involved in the ROS production triggered by GroEx was investigated, by analyzing the ROS burst in *GRP3* mutant/transgenic seedlings treated with mock (PBS) and GroEx (16 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) over a period of 3 hours. The GroEx-triggered ROS production was

significantly increased ($P < 0.05$, ANOVA with Tukey's HSD test) in both *grp3* and *GRP3*-OE plants compared to Col-0 wild type, and was unchanged in *GRP3* #4 (Fig. 2B).

The induction of *FRK1*, *CYP81F2* and *PAD3* in *GRP3* mutant/transgenic seedlings was analyzed at 0, 30, 60 and 180 minutes from treatment with GroEx ($4 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$). We found that at the time of maximal induction, i.e. 1 h for *CYP81F2* and 3 h for *FRK1/PAD3*, the expression of the three genes was significantly reduced ($P < 0.05$ for *CYP81F2/FRK1* and $P < 0.01$ for *PAD3*, Student *t*-test) in *grp3* and *GRP3*-OE plants compared to wild type, and was unchanged in *GRP3* #4 (Fig. 2C). The expression of *CYP81F2* was significantly reduced ($P < 0.01$, Student *t*-test) in *grp3* and *GRP3*-OE plants compared to wild type and *GRP3* #4 also at 3 h (Fig. 2C). On the contrary, at the earlier time points, i.e. 30/60 min for *FRK1/PAD3* and 30 min for *CYP81F2*, we did not find any difference between *GRP3* mutant/transgenic plants and Col-0 (Fig. 2C). These data suggest that *GRP3* is required mainly for the duration, but not the onset, of the expression of the GroEx-induced genes *FRK1*, *CYP81F2* and *PAD3*.

To investigate if *GRP3* is involved in the GroEx-induced protection against *M. persicae*, wild-type Col-0 and *GRP3* mutant/transgenic 5-weeks-old plants were infiltrated with mock (PBS) or GroEx ($30 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) and, after 24 hours, *Myzus persicae* adult aphids aged 8 days were caged in the infiltrated leaves. After 9 days, the fecundity of individual adult aphids on these plants was assessed by counting their offspring. Compared with mock infiltration, aphid fecundity was significantly reduced ($P < 0.05$, Student *t*-test) in Col-0 and *GRP3* #4 Arabidopsis leaves infiltrated with GroEx (Fig. 2D). On the contrary, *grp3* and *GRP3*-OE plants displayed no GroEx-induced protection against *M. persicae* (Fig. 2D). All these results suggest that, depending on response, *GRP3* plays both positive and negative roles in the signaling to the aphid elicitors present in GroEx.

Figure 2. Analysis of aphid fecundity and GroEx-triggered immunity in the *grp3* mutant, GRP3 #4 and GRP3-OE (#16 and #17) transgenic lines. **A.** Aphid fecundity is reduced on *grp3* mutants, but not on GRP3 #4 and GRP3-OE transgenic plants, compared to wild type (Col-0). Each plant was seeded with one nymph, and the average fecundity of the nymphs as they progressed to adulthood was recorded. Bars represent the mean (\pm SE) of five plants of each genotype. Different letters above the bars indicate statistically significant differences between samples, as determined by analysis of variance (ANOVA) with Tukey's honestly significant difference (HSD) test ($P < 0.05$). **B.** Total ROS production over 3 h, expressed in relative light units (RLUs), was measured by a luminescence-based assay in seedlings of Col-0, *grp3*, GRP3 #4 and GRP3-OE during elicitation with mock (PBS) or GroEx ($16 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$). Results are average \pm SE ($n = 8$). Asterisks above the bars indicate statistically significant differences between Col-0 and mutant/transgenic seedlings treated with GroEx, as determined by ANOVA with Tukey's HSD test (*, $P < 0.05$; **, $P < 0.01$). **C.** Expression of the indicated defense gene was analyzed by qRT-PCR in seedlings of Col-0, *grp3*, GRP3 #4 and GRP3-OE after treatment with GroEx ($4 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) at the indicated time points. Transcripts levels are shown as the mean of at least three independent experiments (\pm SE; $n = 20$ in each experiment) normalized to *UBQ5* expression. Asterisks indicate statistically significant differences between wild-type and mutant/transgenic seedlings at the indicated time points, according to Student's *t* test (*, $P < 0.05$; **, $P < 0.01$). **D.** Arabidopsis Col-0, *grp3*, GRP3 #4 and GRP3-OE plants were infiltrated with PBS or GroEx ($30 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) and, after 24 h, the leaves were infested with a single adult aphid and the number of offspring was determined after 9 d. Results are average \pm SE ($n = 5$). Asterisks indicate statistically significant differences between samples, as determined by ANOVA with Tukey's HSD test ($P < 0.05$). In A, B, C and D, experiments were repeated three times with similar results.

Alteration of pectin structure affects resistance against *Myzus persicae*

The degree of pectin methyl esterification (DM) has been shown to affect plant resistance to fungal and bacterial pathogens. Indeed, *Arabidopsis* plants overexpressing pectin methyl esterase inhibitors (PMEIs) and a loss-of-function mutant of *PME3* showed an increase of DM and a concomitant enhanced resistance to *Botrytis cinerea* and *Pectobacterium carotovorum* (Lionetti *et al.*, 2007; Raiola *et al.*, 2011).

To investigate if the DM affects plant resistance to aphids, wild-type Col-0, *pme3* loss-of-function mutant (see molecular characterization in supplemental Fig. S1D), and *35S:PMEI1* and *35S:PMEI2* overexpressing homozygous lines (*PMEI1*-OE and *PMEI2*-OE, see molecular characterization in supplemental Fig. S1E) were seeded with one 24-hours-old nymph. The nymphs were allowed to develop to adulthood and to produce offspring. In our experiment, the aphid fecundity was significantly higher ($P < 0.05$, Student *t*-test) on *pme3* mutants and in both *PMEIs*-OE transgenic plants compared to Col-0 (Fig. 3). These data indicate that plants having a more methylated form of pectin, caused by either the lack of expression of *PME3* or the overexpression of the *PMEI* inhibitors, are more susceptible to *M. persicae* colonization.

Figure 3. Aphid fecundity is increased on *pme3* mutants and on *PMEI1*-OE and *PMEI2*-OE transgenic plants, compared to wild type (Col-0). Each plant was seeded with one nymph, and the average fecundity of the nymphs as they progressed to adulthood was recorded. Bars represent the mean (\pm SE) of five plants of each genotype. Asterisks indicate statistically significant differences between wild-type and mutant/transgenic plants, according to Student's *t* test (*, $P < 0.05$; **, $P < 0.01$). The experiment was repeated three times with similar results.

6.4 DISCUSSION

Both in animal and plants, activation of the plant innate immune system can be triggered by molecular patterns conserved among different pathogen species but not present in host cells (Nurnberger *et al.*, 2004). However, some host-derived elicitors may also be released during an infection as a consequence of pathogen activity, and examples have been reported (Boller and Felix, 2009; Choi and Klessig, 2016). These endogenous elicitors, like true PAMPs, trigger defense responses that contribute to basal resistance against pathogens (Bhattacharya *et al.*, 2013; Serrano *et al.*, 2014; Tanaka *et al.*, 2014; Cervone *et al.*, 2015; Bartels and Boller, 2015; Souza *et al.*, 2017). OGs represent a good example of endogenous elicitors and have been extensively studied since their identification about 35 years ago (Hahn *et al.*, 1981). OGs are oligomers of alpha-1,4-linked galacturonosyl residues released from plant cell walls upon pathogen attack or mechanical wounding (Ferrari *et al.*, 2013; Savatin *et al.*, 2014b) that are active when they have a degree of polymerization ≥ 3 residues of galacturonic acid (Davidsson *et al.*, 2017). OGs elicit plant defense responses similar to those of well-characterized PAMPs, such as the bacterial flagellin (Ferrari *et al.*, 2007; Denoux *et al.*, 2008; Galletti *et al.*, 2008; Aslam *et al.*, 2009) (Galletti *et al.*, 2011; Gravino *et al.*, 2017). OGs trigger transcriptional reprogramming, changes in protein phosphorylation level, increases of calcium (Ca^{2+}), hormones and secondary metabolites concentration, which contribute to enhanced fungal and bacterial resistance in plants (Moscatiello *et al.*, 2006; Ferrari *et al.*, 2007; Denoux *et al.*, 2008; Galletti *et al.*, 2011; Savatin *et al.*, 2014a; Benedetti *et al.*, 2015; Gravino *et al.*, 2015; Mattei *et al.*, 2016).

In this work we show that OGs enhance Arabidopsis resistance against the green peach aphid/peach-potato aphid *M. persicae*. Aphids feed mainly from the phloem by ingesting sap. In plants, a primary defense response to sap ingestion is the occlusion of sieve elements (SE) (Will *et al.*, 2013). Occlusion mechanisms by callose and phloem proteins (P-proteins) are likely induced by a sudden calcium influx into the SE lumen (Furch *et al.*, 2007). Usually, OGs trigger a variety of plant responses against pathogens and insects in which the activation of Ca^{2+} channels/sensors and synthesis of callose are involved (Vorwerk *et al.*, 2004; Moscatiello *et al.*, 2006; Ferrari *et al.*, 2013; Gravino *et al.*, 2015). The release of OGs from the plant cell walls as a result of the action of enzymes secreted by the stylet sheath (Cherqui and Tjallingii, 2000) might enhance plant resistance to aphids by triggering the SEO, possibly through the pathway mediated by BAK1, BAK1-LIKE1 (BKK1) and CDPKs, which have been described to play a role in the OG signaling and induced resistance against *B. cinerea* (Gravino *et al.*, 2015; Gravino *et al.*, 2017).

Further mechanisms that limit *M. persicae* infestation on Arabidopsis have been reported, including ROS production (Miller *et al.*, 2009); defense signaling mediated by ethylene (Et) (Dong *et al.*, 2004; Kettles *et al.*, 2013), jasmonic acid (JA) (Ellis *et al.*, 2002; Mewis *et al.*, 2005; Mewis *et al.*, 2006), PAD4 (Pegadaraju *et al.*, 2005; Pegadaraju *et al.*, 2007; Louis *et al.*, 2010; Louis *et al.*, 2012; Lei *et al.*, 2014) and microRNAs (miRNAs) pathways (Kettles *et al.*, 2013); biosynthesis of camalexin (Kettles *et al.*, 2013; Prince *et al.*, 2014), glucosinolates (Mewis *et al.*, 2005; Levy *et al.*, 2005; Kim and Jander, 2007; Kim *et al.*, 2008; Pfalz *et al.*, 2009), starch (Singh *et al.*, 2011; Singh and Shah, 2012), oxylipins (Cooper *et al.*, 2004; Avila *et al.*, 2013), lectins (Beneteau *et al.*, 2010; Zhang *et al.*, 2011), trehalose (Singh *et al.*, 2011) and N⁶-acetyloronithine (Adio *et al.*, 2011); senescence (Pegadaraju *et al.*, 2005). A possible role of PAD4 and/or Et in the resistance induced by OGs is likely because (i) transcriptional profiling experiments showed that *PAD4* is up regulated by OGs (Denoux *et al.*, 2008); (ii) OGs induce Et synthesis (Gravino *et al.*, 2015); (iii) Et and ETHYLENE INSENSITIVE 2 (*EIN2*) are required for the OG-triggered resistance to *B. cinerea* (Gravino *et al.*, 2015); (iv) *pad4* and *ein2* mutants are more susceptible to *M. persicae* (Pegadaraju *et al.*, 2005; Kettles *et al.*, 2013). As well, glucosinolates and/or camalexin might be required for the OG-induced resistance since (i) transcriptional profiling and qRT-PCR experiments showed that transcripts of genes involved in glucosinolate metabolism, such as *CYP81F2*, *CYP79B2* and *CYP79B3*, as well as *PAD3*, which is

required for camalexin biosynthesis, are induced by OGs (Denoux *et al.*, 2008; Gravino *et al.*, 2017); (ii) OGs enhance the *B. cinerea*-induced camalexin synthesis (Savatin *et al.*, 2014a; Gravino *et al.*, 2015); (iii) camalexin and PAD3 are required for the OG-triggered resistance to *B. cinerea* (Ferrari *et al.*, 2007; Savatin *et al.*, 2014a); mutations in *CYP81F2*, *CYP79B2*, *CYP79B3* and *PAD3* resulted in lowered resistance to *M. persicae* (Kim *et al.*, 2008; Pfalz *et al.*, 2009; Kettles *et al.*, 2013).

In order to overcome plant defense mechanisms, aphids secrete effectors into host cells that inhibit PAMP- and OG-induced defense signaling [(Hogenhout and Bos, 2011); this work]. Signaling triggered by aphid PAMPs and OGs might play a crucial role in plant immunity to aphids. Indeed, the aphid effector Mp10 inhibits the flg22- and OG-triggered ROS production [(Bos *et al.*, 2010); this work], which is required for resistance against *M. persicae* (Miller *et al.*, 2009). Moreover, Mp10 inhibits the OG-triggered expression of the defense genes *FRK1* and *CYP81F2* (this work), and the latter is involved in resistance to *M. persicae* (Pfalz *et al.*, 2009). The evidence that Mp10 inhibits both flg22- and OG-triggered defense responses supports the vision that OGs and PAMPs act, at least in part, through shared pathways (Galletti *et al.*, 2009; Savatin *et al.*, 2014a; Gravino *et al.*, 2015; Gravino *et al.*, 2017). Interestingly, the Pst-derived effector AvrPto was been described to inhibit the OG-triggered immunity (Gravino *et al.*, 2017), indicating that pathogen mechanisms of OG signaling suppression are conserved among insects and bacteria. Understanding the mechanisms by which OGs enhance plant resistance to *M. persicae* and Mp10 suppresses the OG-triggered immunity remains to be investigated and will be helpful to select plant cultivar more resistant to aphids.

Other than using effectors, pathogens utilize host-derived molecules that favor the colonization process. To overcome the plant cell wall barrier and render the structure more prone to degradation, some pathogens force the host enzyme machinery to work in concert with their own arsenal of hydrolytic enzymes. A high pectin DM has been correlated with an increased resistance against pathogens (Senechal *et al.*, 2014). For example, both *B. cinerea* and *P. carotovorum* induce the expression of *PME3*, which negatively regulate the pectin DM, and the loss of function of *PME3* results in enhanced pectin DM and a concomitant increased resistance against both necrotrophic pathogens (Raiola *et al.*, 2011). In this study we have used *pme3* mutants, and *PME11* or *PME12* overexpressing plants in order to evaluate the impact of the increased levels of pectin DM on *M. persicae* performance. Quite the contrary, the number of nymphs produced was higher on mutant/transgenic plants compared to wild type plants, suggesting that a higher pectin DM is beneficial for *M. persicae*. Moreover, increased PME activity and the associated lower pectin DM enhanced fruit resistance to *B. cinerea* in transgenic strawberry overexpressing *PME1* (Osorio *et al.*, 2008). Understanding this opposite effects is complex as the regulation of pectin DM by PMEs and PMEIs activities can have two distinct consequences. On one hand, higher pectin DM may correlate with a lesser accessibility to pectin-degrading enzymes and therefore with an increased resistance to pathogens. On the other hand, less methylated pectins are more prone to digestion by pectinolytic enzymes and subsequent release of OGs that elicit defense responses.

OGs are perceived by the receptor WAK1 (Brutus *et al.*, 2010), which appears to be a key element in the communication to the cell of an altered state of the wall. WAK1 forms a complex with GRP3 (Park *et al.*, 2001; Anderson *et al.*, 2001), a glycine rich protein that is localized in the apoplast (Gramegna *et al.*, 2016). GRP3 plays a negative role in the response to OGs, flg22 and wounding (Gramegna *et al.*, 2016). Moreover, *grp3* mutant plants are more resistant to *B. cinerea* (Gramegna *et al.*, 2016) and *M. persicae* (this work), supporting the vision that OG signaling plays an important role in these pathosystems (Mengiste, 2012; Foyer *et al.*, 2016). However, the interaction mechanisms of host and pathogen are complex and, besides OGs, the recognition of PAMPs is crucial for the final outcome. The results obtained on the response to aphid-derived PAMPs (i.e. GroEx) are of difficult interpretation, but may be helpful to explain the basis of the enhanced resistance of the *grp3* mutants. On the one hand, the increased GroEx-triggered H₂O₂

production might limit aphid infestation (Miller *et al.*, 2009), and confirms the negative role of GRP3 in the response to PAMPs (Gramegna *et al.*, 2016). On the other hand, the reduced GroEx-triggered defense gene expression and protection against *M. persicae* do not support the model of GRP3 as negative regulator of the aphid resistance and the aphid-triggered immunity, and may depend on the complexity and heterogeneity of GroEx. In any case we observed that the overexpression of GRP3 mimics its loss of function, presumably interfering at some level with the function of the protein or its complex (Park *et al.*, 2001), disrupting stoichiometry and/or acting as an antimorph, as observed for other proteins (Clark-Adams and Winston, 1987; Clark-Adams *et al.*, 1988; Malone *et al.*, 1991; Swanson *et al.*, 1991; Wang *et al.*, 2014).

6.5 MATERIALS AND METHODS

Aphids

Stock colonies of *M. persicae* (Sulzer) [Rothamsted Research genotype O; GPA (Bos *et al.*, 2010)] were reared in 52 x 52 x 50-cm³ cages containing up to six Chinese cabbage (*Brassica rapa*, subspecies *chinensis*) plants with a 14-hours light (90 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ at 18 °C) and a 10-hours dark (15 °C) cycle.

Plant materials and growth conditions

All plants used in this investigation belong to the Arabidopsis Col-0 ecotype. The Mp10 transgenic plants (lines #7-5 and #9-5) were supplied by Saskia Hogenhout (Department of Crop Genetics, John Innes Centre, Norwich Research Park, Norwich, Norfolk, NR4 7UH, UK). The *fls2 efr cerk1* triple mutant, the *pepr1 pepr2* double mutant, and the *bak1-5* mutant were used in a previous study (Prince *et al.*, 2014). The *bak1-5 bkk1-1* double mutant was used in a previous study (Gravino *et al.*, 2017). The *serk2-1 bak1-5 bkk1-1* triple mutant was kindly provided by Libo Shan (Department of Plant Pathology and Microbiology, Institute for Plant Genomics and Biotechnology, Texas A&M University, College Station, TX, 77843, USA). The *grp3* insertional mutant (SALK_084685.46.60) and 35S:*GRP3-RFP* transgenic plants (lines #4, #16 and #17) were used in a previous study (Gramegna *et al.*, 2016). The *pme3* insertional mutant (GK 00210) was used in a previous study (Raiola *et al.*, 2011). The 35S:*PMEI1* (line #1-1) and 35S:*PMEI2* (line #2-7) plants were used in a previous study (Lionetti *et al.*, 2007).

For experiments with adult plants, Arabidopsis (*Arabidopsis thaliana*) seeds were vernalized for 1 week at 4 °C and then germinated and grown in Scotts Levington F2 compost in a controlled-environment room (CER) with a 10-hours light (90 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$) and a 14-hours dark photoperiod at a constant temperature of 22 °C. Plants were used for experiments at 5 weeks old.

For experiments with seedlings, Arabidopsis (*Arabidopsis thaliana*) seeds were surface sterilized, vernalized for 1 week at 4 °C and then germinated and grown in 1/2 Murashige and Skoog (MS) liquid medium [Sigma-Aldrich; (Murashige and Skoog, 1962)] supplemented with 0.5% sucrose (unless stated otherwise), in a CER with a 16-hours light (120 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$) and 8-hours dark photoperiod at a constant temperature of 22 °C. For Mp10 transgenic seedlings, 20 μM dexamethasone (Sigma-Aldrich) or DMSO (Sigma-Aldrich), as a control, were added to the medium 6 and 3 days before analyses. Seedlings were used for experiments at 10 days old (unless stated otherwise).

Preparation of OGs and GroEx for elicitation experiments

OGs with an average degree of polymerization (DP) of 10-16, as assessed by matrix-assisted laser desorption/ionization time-of-flight mass spectrometry, were prepared as described previously (Bellincampi *et al.*, 2000). OG powder was freshly dissolved in distilled water and diluted to working solutions.

Adult aphids were collected using a moist paintbrush, placed in a 2-ml Eppendorf tube, and snap frozen in liquid nitrogen. The aphids were ground to a fine powder using a ball mill (Qiagen) and extraction buffer (1X PBS, 0.5% Triton X-100) was added at 40 $\mu\text{l mg}^{-1}$ tissue powder. The extract was sonicated for 30 seconds and centrifuged at 14,000 rpm for 15 minutes at 4 °C, and the supernatant was collected. Aphid proteins were then precipitated by adding PEG at 6.7% final concentration to the supernatant and incubating at 4 °C for 60 minutes. The fraction was then centrifuged at 14,000 rpm for 15 minutes at 4 °C, and the pellet was resuspended in 1X

PBS (10 $\mu\text{l}/\text{mg}$ tissue powder) at 4 °C for 90 minutes with agitation. The fraction was then centrifuged at 14,000 rpm for 15 minutes at 4 °C, and the supernatant (referred to as GroEx) was collected.

Supernatants and pellets of the three-centrifugation steps and total extract were subjected to SDS-PAGE and western blot analysis. Immunoblots were blocked by incubation in 5% (w/v) BSA in PBS-Tween (0.2%) for 1 hour. GroEL was detected by 1.5 hours incubation with anti-GroEL primary antibody (1:10000; Sigma-Aldrich), followed by incubation with anti-rabbit-HRP secondary antibody (Sigma-Aldrich) for 1 hour. In parallel, protein loading was visualized by gel staining with silver stain (Thermo Fisher Scientific).

Induced resistance assays

Experiments were conducted in a CER with an 8-hours light (90 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ at 18 °C) and 16-hours dark (16 °C) photoperiod. To obtain aphids of the approximately the same age, 5-week old Col-0 Arabidopsis plants were potted into 1-L round black pots (13-cm diameter, 10 cm tall) that were caged inside clear plastic tubing (10-cm diameter, 15 cm tall; Jetran tubing, Bell Packaging), which was pushed inside the soil of the pot and capped at the top with a white gauze-covered plastic lid. Each plant was seeded with 10 adult GPA. After 24 hours, all adults were removed from the Col-0 plants, while the nymphs remained on the plants for 8 days.

For treatment of plants with elicitors, 5-week old Arabidopsis plants in black plastic pots (base measurement, 3.5 cm x 3.5 cm; top measurement, 5.5 cm x 5.5 cm; height, 5.5 cm) were infiltrated with OGs (200 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) or GroEx (30 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) on the first fully expanded leaf using a needleless 1-ml syringe (Terumo). Control plants were infiltrated with distilled water or PBS. The infiltrated leaves were marked. The plants were used for aphid reproduction assays after 24 hours.

To assay aphid reproduction on the infiltrated leaves, one aged adult of 8 days was placed in a clip cage using a moist paintbrush, and the cage was placed on the infiltrated leaf at one aphid per plant. Plants were returned to the experimental CER and left for 9 days. After 9 days, the number of aphids in each clip cage was counted. Each experiment included 5 plants per condition and/or genotype unless otherwise stated. Each plant was randomly placed in a tray of 42 cm x 52 cm x 9 cm. Each experiment was repeated at least two times on different days to generate data from at least two independent biological replicates.

Myzus persicae whole-plant fecundity assays

Experiments were conducted in a CER with an 8-hours light (90 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ at 18 °C) and 16-hours dark (16 °C) photoperiod. Five-weeks-old Arabidopsis plants were potted into 1-l round black pots and caged in clear plastic tubing as described above. Each plant was seeded with two adult GPA. After 48 h, all adults were removed from test plants, while the nymphs remained at one nymph per plant. These nymphs developed into adults and started producing their own nymphs at about day 6. The number of nymphs was counted on days 6, 8 and 10, in which the nymphs were removed at each count. The total number of nymphs produced per adult was calculated for each time point and combined. Each experiment included five plants per genotype, and each plant was randomly placed in a tray of 42 cm x 52 cm x 9 cm. Each experiment was repeated at least two times on different days to generate data from two independent biological replicates.

Seedling growth inhibition assays

Seedlings were germinated and grown on ½ MS agar medium supplemented with 1% sucrose for 5 days. Seedlings were then transferred to MS liquid medium (four seedlings per 400 µl of medium in wells of 24-well-plates) supplied with PBS or GroEx at 1, 5, 25 and 125 µg ml⁻¹ concentrations (two wells per concentration) and incubated for 7 days before determination of fresh weight. Each experiment was repeated at least two times on different days to generate data from two independent biological replicates.

Quantitative reverse transcriptase (qRT)-PCR assays

Ten-days-old seedlings grown in MS liquid medium (ten seedlings per 1.5 ml of medium in wells of 12-well-plates) were treated with PBS or GroEx at 0.5, 1, 2, 4, 8 or 40 µg ml⁻¹ concentrations for 30, 60, or 180 minutes (one well per concentration). Seedlings were harvested in 2-ml Eppendorf tubes, snap frozen in liquid nitrogen, and ground to a fine powder using a ball mill (Qiagen). Total RNA was extracted using Tri-Reagent (Sigma-Aldrich), quantified with a Nanodrop spectrophotometer (Thermo Scientific), and treated with DNase I (RQ1 DNase set; Promega). Complementary DNA (cDNA) was synthesized from 250 ng RNA using the M-MLV-RT Kit (Invitrogen), random and oligo(dT) primers, following the manufacturer's instructions. Each qRT-PCR reaction consisted of 10 µL containing 10 ng cDNA and 0.5 mM of each primer (Supplemental Table S1) added to SYBR Green JumpStart Taq ReadyMix (Sigma-Aldrich) in a single well of a 96-well plate white ABgene PCR plate (Thermo Scientific), which was placed in a CFX96 Real-Time System with a C1000 Thermal Cycler (Bio-Rad). PCRs were carried out using the following thermo cycle: 2 minutes at 95 °C, followed by 40 cycles of 20 seconds at 95 °C, 60 seconds at 60 °C, and melt curve analysis (from 65 °C to 95 °C with 0.5 °C increments, 5 seconds for each). The *GLYCERAL DEHYDE-3-PHOSPHATE DEHYDROGENASE C2* (*GAPDH*, *At1g13440*) and *UBIQUITIN 5* (*UBQ5*, *At3g62250*) genes were used for normalization. Gene expression of *FRK1* (*At2g19190*), *CYP81F2* (*At5g57220*), *PAD3* (*At3g26830*), *GRP3* (*At2g05520*), *PMEI1* (*At1g48020*) and *PMEI2* (*At3g17220*) was measured by quantitative PCR analysis and normalized to *GAPDH* or *UBQ5* (reference genes) expression. Experiments were repeated at least three times on different days to generate independent biological replicates.

MAP kinase assays

Ten-days-old seedlings grown in MS liquid medium (ten seedlings per 1.5 ml of medium in wells of 12-well-plates) were treated with PBS or GroEx at 2 and 4 µg ml⁻¹ concentrations for 5, 15, or 30 minutes (one well per concentration). Seedlings were harvested in 2-ml Eppendorf tubes, snap frozen in liquid nitrogen, and ground to a fine powder using a ball mill (Qiagen). Protein extraction buffer (50 mM Tris-HCl pH 7.5, 200 mM NaCl, 1 mM EDTA, 10% glycerol, 1% Tween-20, 1 mM DTT, 1 mM PMSF, 1% phosphatase inhibitor cocktail [Sigma-Aldrich] and 1% protease inhibitor cocktail [Sigma-Aldrich]) was added. Homogenates were clarified by centrifugation at 13,000 x g for 30 minutes at 4 °C and supernatants were collected. Proteins (60 µg) were diluted with loading buffer and separated on 10% (wt/v) SDS-PAGE gels and transferred to 0.45 mm Protran BA85 nitrocellulose membranes (Whatman) using the BioRad minigel and blotting systems following standard protocols. Blotted membranes were blocked by incubation in 5% (w/v) BSA in TBS-Tween (0.2%) for 1 hour. Activated MAP kinases were detected by overnight incubation with anti-p42/44 MAPK primary antibodies (1:2500; Cell Signaling Technology), followed by incubation with anti-rabbit-HRP secondary antibodies

(Sigma-Aldrich) for 1 hour and detection using Immobilon Western Chemiluminescent HRP Substrate (Millipore). Protein loading was visualized using Ponceau S solution (0.1% [w/v] in 5% acetic acid; Sigma Aldrich). Experiments were repeated at least three times on different days to generate independent biological replicates.

ROS burst assays

For burst in leaf discs, one leaf disc was taken from each of the two youngest fully expanded leaves of 5-weeks-old Arabidopsis plants using a circular cork borer (diameter, 4 mm). The leaf discs were floated on water overnight in 96-well plates (Grenier Bio-One). GroEx (final concentration, 50 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) were added to a solution containing 20 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ horseradish peroxidase (Sigma-Aldrich) and 21 nM luminol (Wako). Before the experiment began, the water was removed from the wells and replaced with 100 μL of horseradish peroxidase and luminol solution containing GroEx or PBS control.

For burst in seedlings, Arabidopsis seedlings were grown for 8 days in MS liquid medium (one seedling per 200 μl of medium in wells of 96-well-plates). The medium was removed from the wells and replaced with 200 μl of distilled water. On day 9, 5 μL of horseradish peroxidase and luminol solution containing GroEx (15 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) or PBS control was added to each well.

Luminescence was captured using a Photek camera system and analyzed using company software and Microsoft Office Excel. Experiments were repeated at least three times on different days to generate independent biological replicates.

Supplemental data

Supplemental Table S1. List of primer sequences used in this study.

Gene	AGI No	Forward primer (5'-3')	Reverse primer (5'-3')
<i>GAPDH</i>	<i>At1g13440</i>	TTGGTGACAACAGGTCAAGCA	AAACTTGTCGCTCAATGCAATC
<i>FRK1</i>	<i>At2g19190</i>	ATCTTCGCTTGGAGCTTCTC	TGCAGCGCAAGGACTAGAG
<i>CYP81F2</i>	<i>At5g57220</i>	TGGCTATGCGTAAACTCGTG	GGTAAACTTCAAAATGGTGGTC A
<i>PAD3</i>	<i>At3g26830</i>	TGCTCCCAAGACAGACAATG	GTTTTGGATCACGACCCATC
<i>GRP3</i>	<i>At2g05520</i>	GGAAGTGGGGGAAGTTACTG	TAGTGACCGGGCTGAGTC
<i>PME3</i>	<i>AT3G14310</i>	GCAGTTACCACGGCAGAGAT	GAAACTTGTTTTGCTATCCGC
<i>PME11</i>	<i>At1g48020</i>	CATCGCTAATCTTCAAGCCT	CCCATACCATCTCCTGAAGCT
<i>PME12</i>	<i>At3g17220</i>	GGTTCTTTGAACGCACAAGT	CTTCATAGTGGGGTTGGTTG
<i>UBQ5</i>	<i>At3g62250</i>	GTAAAGCTCGCTGTTCTTCAGT	TCAAGCTTCAACTCCTTCTTTC

Figure S1. Characterization of the *Mp10*, *GRP3*, *PME3*, *PMEI1/2* mutant/transgenic plants. **A.** Transcripts level of *Mp10* analyzed by qRT-PCR in wild type (Col-0) and *Mp10* (#7-5, #9-5) transgenic plants after treatment with dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) or dexamethasone (DEX, 20 μ M) for 0, 12, 24, 72 and 144 h. The *GAPDH* was used as reference gene. **B.** Genotype analysis of the *GRP3* T-DNA insertion by RT-PCR in Col-0 and *grp3* seedlings, using gene-specific primers flanking the left and the right borders of T-DNA insertion and genomic DNA as a template. **C.** Transcripts level of *GRP3* analyzed by qRT-PCR in Col-0 and *GRP3* (#4, #16, #17) transgenic seedlings, using *UBQ5* as reference gene. **D.** Genotype analysis of the *PME3* T-DNA insertion by PCR in Col-0 and *pme3* seedlings, using gene-specific primers flanking the left and the right borders of T-DNA insertion and genomic DNA as a template. **E.** Transcripts levels of *PMEI1* (left panel) and *PMEI2* (right panel) analyzed by qRT-PCR in Col-0, *PMEI1*-OE and *PMEI2*-OE seedlings, using *UBQ5* as reference gene. In C and E, bars represent the mean (\pm SE) of technical ($n = 3$) replicates of one cDNA sample obtained from twenty seedlings for each genotype.

Figure S2. Analyses of the OG-triggered responses in Mp10 inducible lines pretreated with DMSO. **A.** Total ROS production over 1 h, expressed in relative light units (RLUs), was measured by a luminescence-based assay in dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO)-pretreated seedlings of Col-0 and *agbl-2* during elicitation with water or OGs ($100 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$). Results are average \pm SE ($n = 8$). **B.** Expression of the indicated defense genes was analyzed by qRT-PCR in DMSO-pretreated seedlings of Col-0 and Mp10 (#7-5 and #9-5) after treatment with water or OGs ($25 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) for 1 h. Transcripts levels are shown as the mean of at least three independent experiments (\pm SE; $n = 20$ in each experiment) normalized to *GAPDH* expression. In A and B, experiments were repeated three times with similar results.

Figure S3. Analysis of GroEx-triggered immunity in Arabidopsis wild-type (Col-0) plants. A. Aphid protein fractions were analyzed by immunoblot using an anti-GroEL antibody (left panel). Total proteins were stained with silver staining (right panel). TH, Total Homogenate; ScI, Supernatant centrifugation I; PcI, Pellet centrifugation I; ScII, Supernatant centrifugation II; PcII, Pellet centrifugation II; PcIII, Pellet centrifugation III; ScIII, Supernatant centrifugation III (this sample, indicated as GroEx, was used for elicitation experiments). See materials and methods

for details of the extraction protocol. **B.** Levels of phosphorylated MPK3 and MPK6 (pMPK3 and pMPK6) in elicited seedlings, as indicated, were determined by immunoblot analysis using an anti-p44/42-ERK antibody (top panel). The identity of individual MAP kinases, as determined by size, is indicated by arrows. Total proteins were stained with Ponceau-S staining (PSS, bottom panel). **C.** Expression of *CYP81F2*, normalized to *GAPDH* expression, was analyzed by qRT-PCR in seedlings after 3 h of treatment with GroEx, as indicated. Results are average \pm SE (n = 3). **D.** Analysis of seedling growth inhibition in response to different doses of GroEx, as indicated. Results are average \pm SE (n = 7). Asterisks indicate statistically significant differences between PBS- and GroEx-treated seedlings at the indicated concentrations, according to Student's *t* test (*, $P < 0.05$; **, $P < 0.01$). **E.** ROS production, expressed in relative light units (RLUs), was measured by a luminescence-based assay in seedlings over a period of 60 min of elicitation with PBS or GroEx ($15 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$). Results are average (n = 8). **F.** Adult plants were infiltrated with PBS or GroEx ($30 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) and, after 24 h, the leaves were infested with a single adult aphid and the number of offspring was determined after 9 d. Results are average \pm SE (n = 5). Asterisks indicate statistically significant differences between PBS- and GroEx-pretreated plants, according to Student's *t* test (*, $P < 0.05$). In A, B, C, D, E and F, experiments were repeated at least two times with similar results.

Figure S4. BAK1, BKK1 and SERK2 are required for the GroEx-triggered induction of a set of defense genes. Expression of the indicated defense genes was analyzed by qRT-PCR in seedlings of wild type (Col-0), *bak1-5*, *bak1-5 bkk1-1* and *serk2-1 bak1-5 bkk1-1* after treatment with GroEx ($4 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) at the indicated time points. Transcripts levels are shown as the mean of at least three independent experiments (\pm SE; $n = 20$ in each experiment) normalized to *GAPDH* expression.

Figure S5. FLS2, EFR, CERK1 and PEPR1/2 are not required for the GroEx-triggered induction of a set of defense genes. Expression of the indicated defense genes was analyzed by qRT-PCR in seedlings of wild type (Col-0), *fls2 elfr cerk1* and *pepr1 pepr2* after 3 h of treatment with water, GroEx (4 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$), chitin (100 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$), flg22 (10 nM), elf18 (10 nM) or pep1 (10 nM). Transcripts levels are shown as the mean of at least three independent experiments (\pm SE; $n = 20$ in each experiment) normalized to *GAPDH* expression.

7. THE *ARABIDOPSIS THALIANA* BERBERINE BRIDGE ENZYME-LIKE OGOX1 PLAYS A ROLE IN BOTH IMMUNITY AND DEVELOPMENT

7.1 SUMMARY

Oligogalacturonides (OGs) are pectin fragments that originate during pathogen invasions or mechanical wounding, acting as damage-associated molecular patterns (DAMPs). OGs elicit immunity and protect plants against different pathogens. Evidence indicates that OGs play a role also in development by antagonizing auxin responses. Hyper-accumulation of OGs causes deleterious effects on plant growth. Recently, we identified a specific *Arabidopsis* berberine-bridge enzyme-like (BBE-like) protein that oxidizes OGs and inactivates their elicitor activity. Enzymatic oxidation may be the mechanism that controls the homeostasis of OGs and regulates the growth-defense trade off. The enzyme is encoded by the gene *At4g20830* and was named OG oxidase 1 (OGOX1). Here we report the use of *Arabidopsis* transgenic plants that have been engineered to display enhanced or reduced level of *OGOX1* to characterize role of this gene in immunity and development. Our results indicate that *OGOX1* plays a role not only in the plant resistance against the necrotrophic fungus *Botrytis cinerea*. Moreover we show that *OGOX1* plays a role in the OG signaling, response to wounding, and root development.

7.2 INTRODUCTION

During an attempted pathogen invasion, plants recognize microbe- and damage-associated molecular patterns (MAMPs and DAMPs) by specific plasma membrane-localized pattern recognition receptors (PRR) to activate PRR-triggered immunity (PTI). Successful pathogens evolved molecules able to modulate plant PTI, i.e. effectors, leading to effector-triggered susceptibility and pathogen colonization. In certain pathogen races one or more effectors are being recognized by resistance (R) proteins leading to effector-triggered immunity (ETI) that is specific for the pathogen race (Jones and Dangl, 2006).

Oligogalacturonides (OGs) represent a well-known class of DAMPs. They are oligomers of alpha-1,4-linked residues of galacturonic acid released upon partial degradation of homogalacturonan that is the major component of pectin in plant cell walls (Ridley *et al.*, 2001). OGs accumulate in the extracellular matrix during microbial infections through the action of pathogen-encoded polygalacturonases (PGs) (Davidsson *et al.*, 2013; Cervone *et al.*, 2015), or upon wounding and mechanical damage through the action of plant endogenous PGs (Savatin *et al.*, 2014b). The generation of elicitor-active OGs is favored by plant-encoded PG-inhibiting proteins (PGIPs) that counteract PG activity, impeding the complete hydrolysis of homogalacturonan (Cervone *et al.*, 2015).

OGs are perceived by the wall-associated kinase 1 (WAK1) (Brutus *et al.*, 2010), a trans membrane receptor-like kinase (RLK) containing epidermal growth factor-like repeats (Kohorn, 2001). The perception of OGs involves the co-receptor BRI1-associated receptor kinase 1 (BAK1) and its closest paralogue BAK1-like 1 (BKK1) (Gravino *et al.*, 2017), which are RLK belonging to the somatic embryogenesis receptor-like kinase (SERK) gene family (Li, 2010). The cytoplasmic plasma membrane-localized kinase-associated protein phosphatase (KAPP) and the apoplast-localized glycine-rich protein (GRP3) interact with WAK1 (Park *et al.*, 2001; Anderson *et al.*, 2001) and negatively regulate the OG-triggered responses (Gramegna *et al.*, 2016).

Following the perception of OGs, immune responses are activated through different signaling pathways, leading to a robust apoplastic oxidative burst, the increase of cytoplasmic calcium concentration, the synthesis of phytoalexins, the up-regulation of defense- and pathogenesis-related genes and, consequently, the protection against pathogens (Ridley *et al.*, 2001; Ferrari *et al.*, 2013). Several elements have been reported to participate in the OG signaling, including the NAD(P)H oxidase respiratory burst oxidase homologue D (RBOHD) (Galletti *et al.*, 2008), the calcium-dependent protein kinases (CDPKs) CPK5, CPK6 and CPK11 (Gravino *et al.*, 2015), the Arabidopsis NPK1-related protein kinase 1 (ANP1), ANP2 and ANP3 (Savatin *et al.*, 2014a), the mitogen-activated protein kinase 6 (MPK6) (Galletti *et al.*, 2011), the ethylene-insensitive 2 (EIN2) (Gravino *et al.*, 2015) and the Pep1-receptor 1 (PEPR1) and PEPR2 (Gravino *et al.*, 2017). Moreover, the *Pseudomonas syringae* pv *tomato* (Pst)-derived effector AvrPto has been shown to suppress the immunity triggered by OGs (Gravino *et al.*, 2017).

In addition to plant responses to pathogens, OGs regulate plant growth and development and shown to inhibit auxin-induced pea stem elongation (Branca *et al.*, 1988), stimulate stomatal and pericycle cell differentiation in tobacco (Altamura *et al.*, 1998b), inhibit root formation in tobacco (Bellincampi *et al.*, 1996) and Arabidopsis (Savatin *et al.*, 2011; Davidsson *et al.*, 2017). Moreover, Arabidopsis transgenic plants expressing a PGIP-PG fusion protein accumulate high levels of OGs and display reduced plant growth and a senescent phenotype (Benedetti *et al.*, 2015), indicating that an elevated concentration of OGs is deleterious for the plant fitness. Therefore a mechanism for controlling the homeostasis of OGs must exist to prevent the impairment of the plant physiological functions.

Recently, an Arabidopsis flavoprotein, belonging to the berberine bridge enzyme-like (BBE-like) family was identified (Daniel *et al.*, 2017), which oxidizes the reducing end residue of the OG chain to galactaric acid, in a reaction that lead to a formation of hydrogen peroxide (Benedetti *et al.* 2017, in publication). The enzyme was named OG oxidase 1 (OGOX1) and shown to be encoded by the gene *At4g20830* [*BBE-like 20* or *BBE20*, according to the

nomenclature reported in Daniel *et al.* (2015)]. Two different transcripts are ascribed to this gene in the TAIR databank and both are strongly induced upon pathogen perception or elicitation. The transcripts encode two putatively secreted protein isoforms differing in the C-terminal region and with a length of 540 (BBE20) and 570 amino acids (BBE19). The latter includes a predicted glycosylphosphatidylinositol (GPI)-anchoring site. At least three other BBE-like proteins in *Arabidopsis* are OG oxidases (OGO_X2-4; Benedetti *et al.* 2017, in publication). They share a similarity higher than 50% with OGO_X1, and are encoded by the genes *At4g20840* (OGO_X2/BBE21), *At1g01980* (OGO_X3/BBE1) and *At1g11770* (OGO_X4/BBE2). Oxidized OGs are less hydrolysable by fungal polygalacturonases (PGs) and are unable of activating the immune responses and inhibiting the auxin-induced responses (Benedetti *et al.* 2017, in publication), pointing to a crucial role of OGO_X enzymes in plant immunity and development.

In this work, we used two independent single-insertion homozygous over-expressing lines carrying a CaMV 35S::*OGO_X1* construct, a homozygous single T-DNA insertion null mutant (*ogox1*), as well as two independent single-insertion homozygous lines expressing a β -estradiol-inducible specific artificial miRNA (amiR) capable of targeting both *OGO_X1* transcripts, in order to investigate the physiological role of the *OGO_X1* gene. Moreover, to investigate the regulation of *OGO_X1* gene expression we used four independent single-insertion homozygous lines expressing the β -glucuronidase (GUS) reporter gene driven by the 3-kb *OGO_X1* promoter. The characterization of these plants suggests that *OGO_X1* plays a role in both development and immunity.

7.3 RESULTS

OGOXI is induced under stress conditions

Publicly available expression data indicate the *OGOXI* is up-regulated by pathogens, elicitors and stresses (Thilmony *et al.*, 2006; Truman *et al.*, 2006; Kilian *et al.*, 2007; Denoux *et al.*, 2008; Windram *et al.*, 2012). As a first step in the elucidation of the function of *OGOXI* in plant immunity, we examined its expression patterns in wild-type plants under various stress conditions by quantitative real-time PCR. This analysis showed that indeed *OGOXI* expression is up-regulated in response to the necrotrophic fungus *Botrytis cinerea* and the hemibiotrophic bacterium *Pseudomonas syringae*, endogenous (i.e. OGs) and exogenous (i.e. flg22) elicitors, and wounding (Fig. 1A, B, C, D and E), pointing to a role in plant immunity.

Figure 1. The *OGOXI* transcripts are induced during immunity in *Arabidopsis* wild-type (Col-0) plants. Expression of the *OGOXI* transcripts was analyzed by qRT-PCR in 4-weeks-old plants infected with mock (potato dextrose broth) and *B. cinerea* (5×10^5 conidiospores mL^{-1}) after the indicated hours post infection (hpi, **A**), or with mock (H_2O) and Pst DC3000 (5×10^4 cfu mL^{-1}) for one day (**B**), or in 10-days-old seedlings treated with $50 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ OGs (**C**) or 10 nM flg22 (**D**) for the indicated times, or in unwounded (u) and wounded (w) leaves after 1 h (**E**). Bars represent the mean (\pm SE) of three independent experiments, normalized to *UBQ5* expression. Statistically significant differences between treatments are indicated by asterisks, according to Student's *t* test (*, $P < 0.05$; **, $P < 0.01$), or by letters, according to analysis of variance (ANOVA) with Tukey's honestly significant difference (HSD) test ($P < 0.05$).

GUS reporter-aided localization of *OGOXI* gene expression during *Arabidopsis* immunity

The spatial expression pattern of *OGOXI* in response to elicitors, pathogens and wounding was analyzed using four independent transgenic lines expressing the GUS reporter driven by the endogenous promoter of *OGOXI* ($P_{OGOXI}::GUS$, lines #2, #3, #4 and #5, see molecular characterization in supplemental Fig. S1A).

Figure 2 shows the promoter activities of *OGOXI* in different stress conditions; the GUS staining data are representatives of the results obtained with four independent transgenic lines. In response to *B. cinerea*, histochemical staining of the GUS activity showed a strong induction, with a mainly vascular expression pattern spread to the entire leaf (Fig. 2A). In response to *P. syringae*, the activity of the promoter was much weaker compared to that to *B. cinerea*, but the spatial pattern was similar (Fig. 2B). On the contrary, no GUS activity was observed in tissues infected with the necrotroph *Pectobacterium carotovorum* (Fig. 2C), indicating that *OGOXI* expression is not induced in response to this pathogen. In response to the elicitors OGs and flg22, we again observed a vascular-specific expression of GUS, but mainly localized at the infiltration sites (Fig. 2D). In response to wounding, GUS activity was localized around the wound site and, to a lesser extent, in the vasculature (Fig. 2E).

Figure 2. Analysis of the *OGOXI* activity in transgenic plants expressing the *GUS* reporter gene under the control of the *OGOXI* promoter. GUS activity was visualized in 4-weeks-old transgenic plants inoculated with mock (potato dextrose broth) or *B. cinerea* (5×10^5 conidiospores mL^{-1}) for 48 h (A), or infiltrated with mock (water) and Pst DC3000 (5×10^4 cfu mL^{-1}) for five days (B), or not treated (nt), inoculated with mock (puncture with a sterile needle + 5- μl droplet of 50 mM potassium phosphate buffer [pH 7.0]) and *P. carotovorum* (OD = 0.025) for 16 h (C), or infiltrated with water, OGs ($200 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) and flg22 (100 nM) for 1 h (D), or in un wounded (u) and wounded (w) leaves after 1 h (E). Experiments were repeated three times with similar results.

OGOXI* plays a role in immunity against *Botrytis cinerea* but not against *Pectobacterium carotovorum

To characterize the role of *OGOXI* in immunity, plants altered in *OGOXI* expression, previously generated in the laboratory, were analyzed. These included a null mutant (*ogox1*), two independent conditionally silenced lines, expressing a β -estradiol-inducible specific artificial miRNA (*amiROGOXI*, lines #3.4 and #2.5), and two overexpressing lines carrying the genomic *OGOXI* coding sequence including the entire intron, under the control of the 35S CaMV promoter (*OGOXI*-OE, #1.9 and #11.8). *OGOXI* transcripts were absent in the mutant *ogox1* (supplemental Fig. S1B) and reduced in the *amiROGOXI* lines (supplemental Fig. S1B). As expected, transcripts were increased in the overexpressing lines (supplemental Fig. S1B).

Response to pathogens was analyzed in the mutant/transgenic plants altered in *OGOXI* expression (in collaboration with Dr. Ilaria Verrascina and Dr. Federica Locci). Preliminary data obtained by Ilaria Verrascina showed a moderate but significant increase in susceptibility to *P. carotovorum* in the overexpressing plants. On the contrary, response to *P. carotovorum* was not altered in the *ogox1* mutant and the *amiROGOXI* lines (Verrascina 2017, PhD thesis). However, considering the absence of GUS activity in the *P_{OGOXI}::GUS* transgenic plants in response to *P. carotovorum* (see Fig. 2C), I decided to re-evaluate the resistance against this pathogen. In my experimental conditions (bacterial OD = 0.025), the resistance against *P. carotovorum* was not affected in all mutant/transgenic plants (Fig. 3A), which is consistent with the lack of activity of the *OGOXI* promoter in response to this pathogen.

In response to *B. cinerea*, the loss-of-function or silenced mutants have been shown to be more susceptible, whereas the overexpressing plants were more resistant, compared to wild type (Verrascina 2017, PhD thesis; Benedetti et al., in publication). This is consistent with data showing that *OGOXI* expression is induced in response to this pathogen (see Fig. 2A). These results, however, are in apparent disagreement with a mere role of *OGOXI*s in the inactivation of the OG activity as DAMPs, considering that OGs are known to confer protection against this pathogen (Ferrari et al., 2007; Benedetti et al., 2015; Gravino et al., 2015), and suggest that, during an infection, an altered oxidation of OGs may have more complex effects than the mere modulation of the immune system.

In order to shed light on the basis of the altered susceptibility to *B. cinerea* of the *OGOXI* mutant/transgenic plants, mechanisms that are known to contribute to resistance to this fungus were investigated. An important positive role in resistance against *B. cinerea* is played by the secondary metabolites glucosinolates and the hormones Et and JA, whereas a negative role is played by salicylic acid (SA) (Akagi et al., 2011; Mengiste, 2012; Buxdorf et al., 2013). I therefore investigated whether the expression of defense genes that are involved in the above-mentioned pathways is altered in the *OGOXI* mutant/transgenic plants during the *B. cinerea* infection. The *PDF1.2* genes that is regulated by Et and synergistically by JA, and the *PATHOGENESIS-RELATED GENE 1 (PRI)* gene, a marker of SA response (Ward et al., 1991; Pieterse et al., 2012) were analyzed. Moreover, the expression of *CYTOCHROME P450, FAMILY 81, SUBFAMILY F, POLYPEPTIDE 2 (CYP81F2)*, which encodes a monooxygenase essential for the pathogen-induced accumulation of 4-methoxy-indol-3-ylmethyl glucosinolate (Bednarek et al., 2009) and is required for resistance against *B. cinerea* (Buxdorf et al., 2013) was also analyzed. *OGOXI* mutant/transgenic plants were infected with *B. cinerea* and after 48 hours lesion areas were measured and found to be increased in the *ogox1* mutant and in the β -estradiol-pretreated *amiROGOXI* lines, and decreased in the *OGOXI*-OE plants compared to wild type (Fig. 3B). As expected, lesions were similar between wild type and DMSO-pretreated *amiROGOXI* lines (supplemental Fig. S2D). Fungal growth, evaluated in the infected leaves by measuring levels of *B. cinerea* β -tubulin transcripts by quantitative RT-PCR (qRT-PCR) at 48 hours post inoculation (hpi), was significantly higher in the *ogox1* mutant, whereas it was reduced in the *OGOXI*-OE #1.9 transgenic plants, compared to wild type (Fig. 3C), in agreement with the observation that lesion areas increase in the *ogox1* mutant and decrease in the *OGOXI*-OE #1.9

plants (see Fig. 3B). In the same samples, the expression of *PDF1.2* and *PR1* was higher in the *ogox1* mutant than in the wild type, likely reflecting the higher colonization by the fungus, and was unchanged in the *OGOXI*-OE #1.9 plants (Fig. 3C). On the contrary, *CYP81F2* transcripts showed a lower *B. cinerea*-induced expression in the *ogox1* mutant compared to the wild type, and were unchanged in the *OGOXI*-OE #1.9 plants (Fig. 3C). These results suggest that a defect in the glucosinolates biosynthesis may account the enhanced susceptibility observed in the *ogox1* mutant, but that this gene does not play a role in the increased resistance of the overexpressing plants.

Figure 3. *OGOXI* is required for plant resistance against *B. cinerea*, but not *P. carotovorum*. **A.** Wild-type (Col-0) and indicated *OGOXI* mutant/transgenic plants were inoculated with *P. carotovorum* (OD = 0.025) and lesion size was measured after 16 h. **B.** Col-0 and indicated *OGOXI* mutant/transgenic plants were inoculated with *B. cinerea* (5×10^5 conidiospores mL⁻¹) and lesion size was measured after 48 h. In all infections, bars indicate average lesion area \pm SE of at least two independent experiments (n = 18, in each experiment). Letters indicate statistically significant differences between samples, as determined by analysis of variance (ANOVA) with Tukey's honestly significant difference (HSD) test (P < 0.05). **C.** Expression of the indicated defense gene was analyzed by qRT-PCR in Col-0 and indicated *OGOXI* mutant/transgenic plants 48 h after inoculation with mock (PDB) or *B. cinerea* (5×10^5 conidiospores mL⁻¹). Transcripts levels are shown as the mean of at least three independent experiments (\pm SE; n = 4 in each experiment) normalized to *UBQ5* expression. Asterisks indicate statistically significant differences against control (Col-0), according to Student's t test (*, P < 0.05; **, P < 0.01).

***OGOX1* plays a role in oligogalacturonide-triggered immunity**

To investigate whether alteration of *OGOX1* expression affects response to exogenous OGs, responses typically induced by OGs were analyzed in the mutant/transgenic plants. Because the production of extracellular reactive oxygen species (ROS) is one of the first measurable responses to OGs (Galletti *et al.*, 2008; Savatin *et al.*, 2014a; Gravino *et al.*, 2017), accumulation of H₂O₂ was analyzed in *OGOX1*-OE lines, *ogox1*, and ami*ROGOX1* lines treated with OGs or water using a luminescence-based assay (Bisceglia N.G. *et al.*, 2015). After treatment with OGs, the ROS production by leaf discs was significantly higher in the *ogox1* mutant and the ami*ROGOX1* lines pretreated with β -estradiol than that of wild type (Fig. 4A). No difference was observed in ROS produced by *OGOX1*-OE lines and in the ami*ROGOX1* lines pretreated with DMSO compared to wild type (Fig. 4A and supplemental Fig. S2A).

Callose deposition, another typical response to OGs that is mediated by RBOHD-dependent hydrogen peroxide production (Galletti *et al.*, 2008), was also significantly increased in leaves of the *ogox1* mutant and the ami*ROGOX1* lines pretreated with β -estradiol (Fig. 4B), and unaffected in the *OGOX1*-OE lines and in the ami*ROGOX1* lines pretreated with DMSO (Fig. 4B and supplemental Fig. S2B).

On the contrary, the expression of a set of genes that are markers of the OG response (Denoux *et al.*, 2008; Gravino *et al.*, 2017), i.e. *FLG22-INDUCED RECEPTOR-LIKE KINASE 1 (FRK1)*, *CYTOCHROME P450, FAMILY 81, SUBFAMILY F, POLYPEPTIDE 2 (CYP81F2)* and *RETICULINE-OXIDASE HOMOLOGUE (RET-OX)* genes, was not affected in all mutant/transgenic seedlings (Fig. 4C and supplemental Fig. S3).

These data show that the lack of *OGOX1* differentially impair OG-induced defense responses. On the contrary, its overexpression does not appear to influence signaling by exogenous OGs.

Figure 4. Analysis of OG-triggered ROS production, callose deposition and defense gene expression in the *OGOX1* mutant/transgenic seedlings. **A.** Total ROS production, expressed in relative light units (RLUs), was measured in leaf discs of wild type (Col-0), *OGOX1*-OE, *ogox1* and β -estradiol-(β)-pretreated amiR lines during elicitation with water or OGs ($250 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) for 40 min. Results are average \pm SE ($n = 12$). **B.** Callose deposition visualized by aniline blue staining in leaves of Col-0, *OGOX1*-OE, *ogox1* and β -estradiol-(β)-pretreated amiR lines 24 h after syringe-infiltration with water or OGs ($50 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$). Results are average \pm SE ($n = 12$). **C.** Expression of the indicated defense genes was analyzed by qRT-PCR in seedlings of Col-0, *OGOX1*-OE #1.9, *ogox1* and β -estradiol-(β)-pretreated amiR-*OGOX1* #2.5 after treatment with OGs ($50 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) at the indicated time points. Transcripts levels are shown as the mean of at least three independent experiments (\pm SE; $n = 20$ in each experiment) normalized to *UBQ5* expression. Similar results were obtained in *OGOX1*-OE #11.8 and amiR-*OGOX1* #3.4. In A, B, and C, experiments were repeated three times with similar results. Asterisks indicate statistically significant differences between wild-type and mutant/transgenic plants treated with OGs, according to Student's *t* test (*, $P < 0.05$; **, $P < 0.01$).

***OGOX1* plays a role in wound-induced hydrogen peroxide production**

OGs have been proposed to act as local signals in the response to wounding (Ryan and Jagendorf, 1995; Leon *et al.*, 2001; Savatin *et al.*, 2014b). As the lack of *OGOX1* causes an increase of a subset of OG responses, the role of *OGOX1* in the response to wounding was investigated. Hydrogen peroxide generated in response to wounding can be detected at wound sites and in distal leaf veins as early as 1 hour after wounding (Orozco-Cárdenas and Ryan, 1999). H_2O_2 production at the wound sites was increased in the *ogox1* mutant and the *amiROGOX1* lines pretreated with β -estradiol, and unaffected in the overexpressing plants, compared to wild type (Fig. 5). This is in agreement with the enhanced H_2O_2 production in response to exogenous OGs by the loss-of-function or silenced mutants. As expected, H_2O_2 was unaffected in the *amiROGOX1* lines pretreated with DMSO (supplemental Fig. S2C).

Figure 5. Analysis of wound-triggered H_2O_2 production in the *OGOX1* mutant/transgenic plants. Four-week-old plants of indicated genotypes were wounded with a laboratory forceps and, after 1 h, wounded leaves (w) were excised at the base of the stems and supplied with DAB for 12 h. As control, leaves from unwounded plants (u) were included in the analysis. At least nine leaves from three independent plants were used for each genotype. β indicates β -estradiol pretreatment. Experiments were repeated three times with similar results.

Early expression of *OGOX1* induced by oligogalacturonides requires EIN2

The ethylene (Et) and jasmonic acid (JA) pathways play a major role in induced plant defenses, acting both synergistically and antagonistically (Broekgaarden *et al.*, 2015; Wasternack and Strnad, 2016). In order to assess if Et and JA signaling pathways regulate *OGOX1*, we examined, by qRT-PCR, the expression of *OGOX1* in wild-type seedlings treated for 8 hours with ethephon, an Et-releasing chemical (Lawton *et al.*, 1994), methyl-JA (MeJA) or both. In parallel, we monitored the expression of genes that are regulated by Et and JA in a synergic manner (Pieterse *et al.*, 2012), i.e. *PLANT DEFENSIN 1.1* and *1.2* (*PDF1.1* and *PDF1.2*), *PATHOGENESIS-RELATED 4* (*PR4*), *OCTADECANOID-RESPONSIVE ARABIDOPSIS AP2/ERF 59* (*ORA59*), *ETHYLENE RESPONSE FACTOR 1* and *5* (*ERF1* and *ERF5*), or antagonistic manner (Pieterse *et al.*, 2012), i.e. *VEGETATIVE STORAGE PROTEIN 2* (*VSP2*) and *THIONIN 2.1* (*THI2.1*). Transcript levels of *OGOX1* were significantly induced in response to Et, but not to JA, and were not further up regulated upon Et/JA co-treatment (Fig. 6A), which is consistent with the publicly available expression data (Genevestigator and eFP browser). A similar behavior was observed for *ORA59*, *ERF5* and *PR4* (supplemental Fig. S4). On the contrary, *PDF1.1*, *PDF1.2* and *ERF1* were induced in response to both Et and JA, and were further up regulated upon Et/JA co-treatment (supplemental Fig. S4). As expected, the expression of *VSP2* and *THI2.1* was induced by JA, but not by Et (supplemental Fig. S4). However, only the expression of *VSP2*, but not of *THI2.1*, was reduced by Et/JA co-treatment (supplemental Fig. S4).

Recent analyses showed that OGs induce Et biosynthesis and that EIN2, a central regulator of Et signaling (Alonso *et al.*, 1999), is required only for a subset of OG-induced responses (Gravino *et al.*, 2015). To further understand the role of the ethylene pathway in the expression of *OGOX1*, the expression of the gene induced by OGs was analyzed by qRT-PCR in seedlings of *ein2-5* single mutants, in a time course experiment. In wild type seedlings, we observed that transcript levels of *OGOX1* are induced by OGs as early as after 15 minutes, reach the peak of expression at 60 minutes and strongly decline at 8 hours (Fig. 6B), indicating that *OGOX1* is an early-induced defense gene. The OG-induced expression was reduced in the *ein2-5* mutant, but only at early time points (i.e. up to 30 minutes, see Fig. 6B).

The expression of *OGOX1* induced by oligogalacturonides is inhibited by AvrPto, requires SERK2 and is independent of BAK1 and BKK1

Analysis of mutants showed that also co-receptors of the SERK family (SERK2, BAK1 and BKK1) are required only for a subset of OG-induced responses, and that the bacterial effector AvrPto does not affect all responses (Gravino *et al.*, 2017)(this thesis). In order to determine whether these co-receptors and AvrPto are required for *OGOX1* expression induced by OGs, time course qRT-PCR analyses were performed also in seedlings of the *bak1-5 bkk1* double mutant as well as in AvrPto expressing transgenic seedlings. The induction of *OGOX1* expression was not affected in the *bak1-5 bkk1* mutant (Fig. 6C), whereas it was reduced by the loss of SERK2 and the presence of AvrPto both at early and late time points (Fig. 6C and D).

Figure 6. The expression of *OGOX1* induced by OGs requires EIN2, SERK2 and is suppressed by AvrPto. A. Expression of *OGOX1*, analyzed in 10-days-old wild-type (Col-0) seedlings treated for 8 hours with mock (NaPO₄ + DMSO), methyl jasmonate (MeJA), ethephon (Et) or both (Et+MeJA). The OG-triggered expression of *OGOX1* was analyzed in Col-0, *ein2-5* (B), *bak1-5 bkk1-1*, *serk2-1* (C), or AvrPto (D) seedlings at the indicated times. Analyses were performed by qRT-PCR and transcript levels are shown as the mean of at least three independent experiments (\pm SE; n = 20 in each experiment) normalized to *UBQ5* expression (in A, B, C and D) and plotted relative to expression in the mock-treated sample (only in A). Asterisks indicate statistically significant differences between mock- and hormone-treated seedlings (in A) or between mutants and wild-type seedlings treated with OGs (in B, C and D), according to Student's *t* test (*, $P < 0.05$; **, $P < 0.01$).

***OGOX1* plays a role in development**

Publicly available transcriptome data show a tissue- and organ-specific expression of *OGOX1*, with higher levels in the root maturation and elongation zones and, at a lesser extent, in the transition zone of the seedling (Arabidopsis e-FP browser).

To confirm this expression, GUS activity was monitored in $P_{OGOX1}::GUS$ transgenic lines. Figure 7 shows the promoter activities of *OGOX1* during development. These GUS staining data are representatives of four independent transgenic lines. At the stage of cotyledons fully opened, i.e. 4 days after sowing (in our conditions), GUS activity leading to blue staining was observed in the apical lateral zone of one of the two cotyledons as well as in the primary root and root tip (Fig. 7). Three days later, GUS activity was present in both cotyledons, and in the root with the same pattern of the previous developmental stage (Fig. 7). Interestingly, at the stage of six rosette leaves, i.e. 14 days after sowing in our conditions, GUS activity was also observed in lateral roots, in two of the six leaves with a vascular pattern, and in both cotyledons with differential patterns, i.e. vein or dots patterns (Fig. 7). These data suggest a role of the gene during development of the seedling.

The *OGOX1* silenced plants were analyzed for aberrant morphological phenotypes. Wild type and ami*ROGOX1* seedlings were grown in a vertical orientation for 5 days on MS agar plates and then transferred on MS agar plates supplemented with 5 μ M β -estradiol and root distance from the tip was measured after 1, 2, 3 and 4 days. The transgenic seedlings showed a significantly decreased root length compared to wild type at all time points analyzed (Fig. 8). As expected, root length was similar between wild type and ami*ROGOX1* seedlings growth in the presence of DMSO (Fig. 8). These data show that *OGOX1* plays a positive role during root growth under physiological conditions.

Figure 7. During development *OGOXI* is expressed in cotyledons, leaves, root tip, and primary and lateral roots. GUS expression of $P_{OGOXI}::GUS$ recombinant transgene in the developing transgenic plants. The GUS staining was performed in 4, 7, and 14 days (d) old transgenic seedlings. Experiments were repeated three times with similar results.

Figure 8. Root growth during development is reduced by the silencing of *OGOX1*. Wild type and amiR-*OGOX1* lines were grown for 5 d on MS/2 agar plates and then transferred on MS/2 agar plates supplemented with 5 μM β -estradiol (top chart) or DMSO (bottom chart) and roots were measured after 1, 2, 3 or 4 additional days. Results are average \pm SE (n = 25). Experiments were repeated three times with similar results.

7.4 DISCUSSION

This work contributes to clarify the role *in planta* of OGOX1 in immunity as well as in plant growth and development. OGOX1 is a FAD-dependent oxidase that acts specifically on OGs and likely regulates their activity and homeostasis (Benedetti *et al.* 2017, in publication). Elicitor-active OGs act as DAMPs and antagonize auxin-related responses (Ferrari *et al.*, 2013). On the contrary, oxidized OGs have been shown to be unable to induce expression of the defense responses typically induced by the action of elicitor-active OGs. Oxidized OGs also do not interfere with un-oxidized OG signaling (Benedetti *et al.* 2017, in publication). Homeostasis of OGs is likely regulated also by complex interactions among a wide array of pectin-related proteins, such as polygalacturonases and their inhibitors PGIPs, pectin methylesterases and their inhibitors PMEIs and pectate lyases (Sénéchal F *et al.*, 2015). These proteins are encoded by large gene families and a highly tuned orchestration of their expression and activity, besides the action of OGOX1, is necessary to maintain a physiologically appropriate level of active and inactive OGs, without triggering deleterious hyper-immunity (Benedetti *et al.*, 2015).

My observations on the root growth of OGOX mutants gives further support to the hypothesis of the homeostatic function of OG-oxidizing mechanism and suggest a role of OGOX1 in the development of roots. Under physiological conditions, the root growth is reduced in the *OGOX1*-misexpressing mutant/transgenic plants and increases in the *OGOX1*-overexpressing transgenic plants, compared to wild type. This behavior may be ascribed to the OG homeostasis perturbation and consequent alteration of the antagonistic effect on root growth signals (Kazan, 2013).

The OG oxidation also may act in the phenomenon called “trade-off between growth and defense” (Vos *et al.*, 2013). While the genetic basis of this phenomenon is showing the involvement of several elements of the immune system (Todesco *et al.*, 2010; Palma *et al.*, 2010; Alcazar *et al.*, 2014), nothing is known about the endogenous signals that are responsible for their trigger. OGs are potential candidates for such a role; thereby, the enzymatic function of OGOX1, by preventing their negative effects on growth, is likely to be crucial for plant survival. Mechanisms of DAMP homeostasis are relevant not only in plants but also in animals (Varga *et al.*, 2015; Gadani and Kipnis, 2015; Maverakis *et al.*, 2015). For example, hyaluronic acid (HA) fragments deriving from the extracellular matrix of animals are analogous to OGs and well-known signals of inflammation and immunity (Maverakis *et al.*, 2015; Monslow *et al.*, 2015). It is conceivable that enzyme-based mechanisms, analogous to those mediated by OGOX1, may contribute to HA homeostasis.

The role of OGOX1 in immunity is rather complex. On one hand, OGOX1 does not play a major role in the resistance to the bacterial pathogen *P. carotovorum*. This is in line with the findings the enzyme is not induced upon infection with *P. carotovorum* (this work) and OGs do not protect *Arabidopsis* against this bacterium (Gramegna *et al.*, 2016). On the other hand, overexpression of OGOX1 enhances the resistance against *B. cinerea* while the mutants lacking OGOX1 are more susceptible to the fungus. This apparently is in contrast with the expectation that OGOX1, by dampening the elicitor activity of OGs, should increase susceptibility to *B. cinerea*, against which OGs have been widely shown to confer protection (Aziz *et al.*, 2004; Ferrari *et al.*, 2007; Brutus *et al.*, 2010; Galletti *et al.*, 2011; Suarez *et al.*, 2013; Savatin *et al.*, 2014a; Benedetti *et al.*, 2015; Gravino *et al.*, 2015; Gravino *et al.*, 2017). The unexpected behavior of the loss-of-function/overexpressing plants toward this pathogen may reflect a complex interplay of plant OGOXs, the native and oxidized OGs and the H₂O₂ formed by the enzymes, and requires further studies. On the other hand, we observe an effect on the OG-triggered H₂O₂ and callose production as well as on the wound-induced H₂O₂ production only in the mis-expressing plants. Although similar scenarios have been described for enzymes involved in early steps of metabolic pathways (Kinney, 1998) or for enzymes whose activity depends on cofactors or posttranslational modifications (Blanco *et al.*, 2009), a possible redundancy with other OG oxidases (i.e. OGOX2-4) may explain why we observe an effect on OG signaling only in the knock-out and silenced plants. Nevertheless, the observed phenotypes support the

hypothesis that the *OGOX1*-misexpressing plants, having a reduced OG-oxidizing activity, are less capable of inactivate the substrate, either exogenously-supplied or released as a result of injury (Savatin *et al.*, 2014b), and therefore more responsive in terms of immunity activation. The complexity of the OG perception system (Gravino *et al.*, 2017) may explain the normal response in terms of OG-induced gene expression observed in both *OGOX1* mutants and overexpressing plants, indicating that *OGOX1* plays different roles in OG-mediated signaling pathways.

In the present study we have analyzed the expression of *OGOX1* in different stress conditions and during the early stages of development by qRT-PCR and/or the GUS reporter activity driven by a 3 kb-long 5' flanking region DNA fragment of *OGOX1*. Many of the results obtained are consistent with the role of *OGOX1* in immunity and development. For example, in agreement with the role of *OGOX1* in root development, GUS activity was detected in the main and lateral roots, and root tips. Moreover, in agreement with the role of *OGOX1* in immunity, GUS activity was detected in response to OGs, flg22, wounding, *B. cinerea*, Pst, but not *P. carotovorum*. In many of these cases, and especially in response to *B. cinerea*, but not to wounding, a strong activity was detected in midveins and secondary veins, suggesting that *OGOX1* may have a role also in systemic immunity. Interestingly, a significant increase of *OGOX1* transcripts was detected in response to ethylene. This hormone is central regulator of the plant immune system and is required for mediating responses to OGs (Gravino *et al.*, 2015), flg22 (Mersmann *et al.*, 2010; Boutrot *et al.*, 2010), wounding (O'Donnell *et al.*, 1996), Pst (Guan *et al.*, 2015), and *B. cinerea* (Diaz *et al.*, 2002). In response to these stimuli, *OGOX1* might be upregulated through a pathway mediated by ethylene. For example, data obtained here indicate that upon OG treatment a pathway leading to *OGOX1* expression is activated, which is independent of BAK1 and BKK1, but require EIN2 and is inhibited by the bacterial effector AvrPto.

The JA pathway consists of two distinct branches that respond to different aggressors and antagonize each other. In response to wounding or herbivorous insects, the MYC branch activates MYC transcription factors and JA-responsive genes, including *VSP2*. Necrotrophs utilize the ERF branch, which is controlled by APETALA2/ETHYLENE RESPONSE FACTOR (AP2/ERF) transcription factors, including ERF1 and ORA59. The ERF branch requires the combined activation of JA and ET pathways and induces the marker gene *PDF1.2* (Pieterse *et al.*, 2012). In our experiments *OGOX1* behaves as *ORA59* and not as *VSP2* in response to hormones, indicating that its expression is likely controlled by the ERF branch. However, a more detailed time-course is needed to more accurately understand the role of the JA in the induction of *OGOX1*. Moreover, *OGOX1* share with *ORA59* a role in the plant resistance against *B. cinerea*. Indeed, the lack of both *OGOX1* and *ORA59* leads to enhanced susceptibility to this fungus, whereas their overexpression of *ORA59* causes increased resistance [(Pre *et al.*, 2008); this work].

OGOX1 is encoded by *At4g20830*, which belongs to the BBE-like family that in Arabidopsis comprises 28 members (2015). At least other three other members of the Arabidopsis BBE-like family are OG oxidases and are encoded by the genes *At4g20840* (*OGOX2/BBE21*), *At1g01980* (*OGOX3/BBE1*) and *At1g11770* (*OGOX4/BBE2*; Benedetti *et al.* 2017, in publication), which may share with *OGOX1* a role in plant immunity and development. Recently, *AtBBE-like 3* (also referred to as flavin-dependent oxidase 1, FOX1) has been shown to catalyze the oxidation of indole cyanohydrin to indol-3-carbonyl nitrile in one of the steps of the biosynthetic pathway that leads from tryptophan to 4-hydroxyindole-3-carbonyl nitrile, and was described to play a role in plant immunity against *P. syringae* (Rajniak *et al.*, 2015). Furthermore, *AtBBE-like 13* and *AtBBE-like 15* were identified as monolignol oxidoreductases catalyzing the oxidation of sinapyl-, coniferyl- and p-coumaryl alcohol to their corresponding aldehydes (2015), and the latter was described to be involved in female gametophyte development and function (Pagnussat *et al.*, 2005).

Currently, the BBE-like protein family encompasses sequences found in fungi, plants, bacteria and archaea. In the plant kingdom, BBE-like enzymes catalyze a broad variety of reactions, such as alkaloid and cannabinoid biosynthesis, glucose oxidation, and the aforementioned oxidation of

monolignols and indole cyanohydrin . Interestingly, the BBE-like enzymes *HaCHOX* from sunflower (*Helianthus annuus*) and *LsCHOX* from lettuce (*Lactuca sativa*) have been reported to oxidize cellulose-derived fragments as well as cellobiose and glucose and to be involved in tobacco resistance against *Pectobacterium carotovorum* (Custers *et al.*, 2004). Accordingly, cellodextrins and cellobiose have been shown to possess a DAMP activity in grapevine (Aziz *et al.*, 2007) and more recently in Arabidopsis (Souza *et al.*, 2017).

BBE-like enzymes have also been characterized in phytopathogenic fungi. Glucooligosaccharide oxidase from *Acremonium strictum* (*AsGOOX*) and lactose oxidase from *Microdochium nivale* (*MnLaO*) are secreted enzymes that oxidize mono-, oligo-, or polymeric saccharides and preferentially cello-oligosaccharides, but not uronic acids (Lin *et al.*, 1991; Ahmad *et al.*, 2004). Moreover, five *PiBBE*s with an oligosaccharide oxidizing activity similar to *GOOX* were detected in the predicted secretome of the plant pathogen *Phytophthora infestans* (Raffaele *et al.*, 2010). Interestingly, *AsGOOX*, *MnLaO* and *PiBBE1-5* share the same catalytic activity as *HaCHOX*, which has been assigned a role in plant immune response. Therefore, *AsGOOX*, *MnLaO* and *PiBBE1-5* might act as effectors and suppress the plant immune system through deactivation of the elicitor function of the plant cell wall-released oligosaccharides.

The diversity of oligosaccharide fragments embedded in the cell wall has been hypothesized as a possible reservoir of signal molecules for a variety of biological functions (Hahn *et al.*, 1981; Hamann, 2015). Also the involvement in sensing the cell wall integrity of receptors like Theseus 1 and others (Van der Does *et al.*, 2017) which at the moment remain orphan receptors may indicate that other cell wall fragments may act as signals. The knowledge about the existence and the action of these molecules, however, is still very limited. Much is unknown about how many oligosaccharides other than OGs are released from the cell wall for specific signaling purposes. Further characterization of the BBE-like family may help elucidating this aspect of the cell wall biology.

7.5 MATERIALS AND METHODS

Plant materials and treatments

Arabidopsis (*Arabidopsis thaliana*) Columbia-0 (Col-0) wild-type seeds were purchased from Lehle Seeds. The single T-DNA insertion null mutant *ogox1* (WISCDLSLOX432E05) was purchased from NASC. The 35S::*OGOX1* plants (lines #1.9 and #11.8) were previously described (Verrascina 2017, PhD thesis). The ami*ROGOX1* plants (lines #2.5 and #3.4) were previously obtained in the laboratory. The *ein2-5* mutant was previously described (Gravino *et al.*, 2015). The *bak1-5 bkk1-1* mutant and the inducible AvrPto-expressing plants (line #4.1) were previously described (Gravino *et al.*, 2017).

The promoter sequence of *OGOX1* has been identified in the Arabidopsis Gene Regulatory Information Server (AGRIS; arabidopsis.med.ohio-state.edu/). To generate promoter- β -glucuronidase (GUS) fusion, fragment corresponding to 3002 nucleotides upstream of the predicted translation start of *At4g20830* was amplified from Arabidopsis Col-0 genomic DNA using the *BamHI-P_{OGOX1}* Fwd and *BamHI-P_{OGOX1}* Rev primers (Table S1). The promoter fragments were cloned in the binary vector pBI121 (Stratagene) by a two steps reaction: (i) the CaMV 35S sequence was excised using the HindIII and XbaI restriction enzymes; (ii) the amplified fragment was cloned using the BamHI restriction site of pBI121 upstream of the *uidA* gene. The transgenic plants were generated by *Agrobacterium tumefaciens*-mediated transformation of Arabidopsis Col-0 as described previously (Clough and Bent, 1998). From 6 independent transformed lines, four T3 homozygous lines (*P_{OGOX1}::GUS*, lines #2, #3, #4 and #5) containing a single insertion carrying the *P_{OGOX1}::GUS* cassette were selected for further analyses.

For treatments of seedlings, after surface sterilization, seeds were germinated in multiwell plates (approximately 10 seeds/well) containing 2 ml per well of ½ Murashige and Skoog (MS/2) medium (Duchefa Biochemie) supplemented with 0.5% sucrose (CARLO ERBA Reagents). Plates were incubated at 22 °C with a 16-h light/8-h dark cycle at a light intensity of 120 $\mu\text{E}\cdot\text{m}^2\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$. After 9 days, the medium was adjusted to a final volume of 1 ml and, after one additional day, plants were treated with water or OGs (50 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) for 0, 10, 15, 20, 30, 60, 180 or 480 min. For the response to hormones, seedlings were treated for 8 h with MeJA (50 μM) or mock [dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) 0.01% v/v], 1 mM ethephon or mock (NaPO₄ 50 nM). Gene expression measurement was analyzed as described below. OGs used in this work are the same of those previously described (Gravino *et al.*, 2017).

Infection assays, GUS assays, callose and ROS measurements were performed on rosette leaves of 4-week-old plants grown at 22 °C under a 12-h light/12-h dark cycle at a light intensity of 120 $\mu\text{E}\cdot\text{m}^2\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$.

Arabidopsis root measurements

For root length determination, surface-sterilized seeds were germinated and grown vertically for 5 days in plates containing ½ Murashige and Skoog (MS; Duchefa Biochemie) medium containing 0.8% (w/v) plant agar (Duchefa Biochemie) and 1% (w/v) sucrose (CARLO ERBA Reagents) and then transferred on ½MS medium supplemented with β -estradiol (Sigma-Aldrich), at a final concentration of 5 μM , or DMSO (Sigma-Aldrich), as control. Root length was measured at 6th, 7th, 8th and 9th day of growth using the ImageJ software (National Institutes of Health). Experiments were repeated at least three times on different days to generate independent biological replicates.

GUS assays

For the activities during development, seedlings were grown vertically as described in the previous section and assays were performed after 4, 7 and 14 day from sowing.

For the response to elicitors, adult leaves were infiltrated with water, flg22 (100 nM) or OG solution (200 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) using a needleless syringe and, after 1 h, were detached from plants and assay was performed. For the response to *Botrytis cinerea*, adult leaves were inoculated with 5- μl drops of a conidiospore suspension ($5 \times 10^5 \text{ ml}^{-1}$) in potato dextrose broth (PDB, Difco; 24 g L^{-1}) or mock (PDB) regularly spaced on each side of the middle vein and, after 48 h, were detached from plants and assay was performed. For the response to *Pectobacterium carotovorum*, adult leaves were punctured with the sterile needle of a 1-ml syringe on the epidermis of the adaxial surface of each leaf, at the sides of the middle vein, and a 5- μl droplet of the bacterial suspension ($\text{OD}_{600}=0.05$) or mock (50 mM potassium-phosphate buffer [pH 7.0]) was placed on each punctured site. After 16 h, leaves were detached from plants and assay was performed. For the response to Pst DC3000, adult leaves were infiltrated with water or the bacterial suspension ($5 \times 10^4 \text{ cfu ml}^{-1}$) using a needleless syringe and, after 5 days, were detached from plants and assay was performed. For the response to wounding, adult leaves were wounded by applying a single pressure on each side of the lamina flanking the middle vein with a laboratory forceps and, after 1 h, were detached from plants and assay was performed.

Histochemical staining for GUS activity was performed by incubating the samples with the staining buffer (0.5 mg ml^{-1} X-Glca [5-Bromo-4-chloro-3-indolyl β -D-glucuronic acid cyclohexylammonium salt; Duchefa Biochemie]; 2 mM $\text{K}_3[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]$; 2 mM $\text{K}_4[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]$; 0.2% Triton X-100; 50 mM buffer sodium phosphate [pH 7.2]; 2% DMSO) overnight at 37 °C, with shaking. Subsequently, the samples were cleared and dehydrated with 100% boiling ethanol and rehydrated in 50% ethanol before photography.

Pectobacterium carotovorum infection assays

Pectobacterium carotovorum subsp. *carotovorum* (strain DSMZ 30169) was cultivated in Luria-Bertani (LB) liquid medium overnight at 28 °C, 220 rpm. Bacteria were then collected by centrifugation (6000 \times g for 10 min), washed twice in 50 mM potassium-phosphate buffer (pH 7.0) and suspended at the desired concentration ($\text{OD}_{600}=0.025$). Infections were performed on excised leaves from adult plants, with the cut petiole end immersed in 0.8% (w/v) plant agar medium. Leaves were punctured with the sterile needle of a 1-ml syringe on the epidermis of the adaxial surface of each leaf, at the sides of the middle vein in the central part of the leaf. A 5- μl droplet of the bacterial suspension was placed on each punctured site. The area of water-soaked lesions was determined 16 h after inoculation and measured using ImageJ. Experiments were repeated at least three times on different days to generate independent biological replicates.

Botrytis cinerea infection assays

Fully expanded leaves were detached from adult plants, placed in Petri dishes containing 0.8% (w/v) plant agar with the petiole embedded in the medium. Inoculation with *Botrytis cinerea* was performed by placing 5- μl drops of a conidiospore suspension ($5 \times 10^5 \text{ ml}^{-1}$) in potato dextrose broth (PDB, Difco; 24 g L^{-1}) regularly spaced on each side of the middle vein. Plates were incubated at 22 °C with a 12 h photoperiod. High humidity was maintained by covering the plates with a clear plastic lid. Lesion area was determined 48 h after inoculation by ImageJ. Experiments were repeated at least three times on different days to generate independent biological replicates.

ROS assays

H₂O₂ produced by leaf discs was measured by a luminol-based assay as previously described (Bisceglia N.G. *et al.*, 2015). Briefly, leaf discs (0.125 cm²) were obtained from adult plants, washed for 2 h with water and left to recover in a 96-well titer plate (one disc/well). After about 12 h, discs were vacuum infiltrated with the OG solution (200 µg ml⁻¹) or water, as a control, for 2 min before addition of a solution of luminol (Sigma-Aldrich; 30 g ml⁻¹) and horseradish peroxidase (Sigma-Aldrich; 20 g ml⁻¹). Plates were analyzed for 40 min using a GloMax 96 microplate luminometer with dual injectors (Promega) and a signal integration time of 1 s. Luminescence was expressed in Relative Light Units. Experiments were repeated at least three times on different days to generate independent biological replicates.

For H₂O₂ visualization in response to wounding, adult leaves were wounded by applying a single pressure on each side of the lamina flanking the middle vein with a laboratory forceps and, after 1 h, were detached from plants and dipped for 12 h in a solution containing 1 mg ml⁻¹ 3,3-diaminobenzidine (DAB [pH 5.0]) at room temperature, with shaking. Subsequently, the samples were cleared and dehydrated with 100% boiling ethanol and rehydrated in 50% ethanol before photography.

Callose assays

Leaves from adult plants were infiltrated with water or OG solution (30 or 100 µg ml⁻¹) using a needleless syringe and, after 24 h, were detached from plants. Leaves were cleared and dehydrated with 100% boiling ethanol. Leaves were fixed in an acetic acid:ethanol (1:3) solution for 2 h, sequentially incubated for 15 min in 75% ethanol, in 50% ethanol, and in 150 mM phosphate buffer, pH 8.0, and then stained for 1 h in 150 mM phosphate buffer, pH 8.0, containing 0.01% (w/v) aniline blue. After staining, leaves were mounted in 10% glycerol and examined by UV epifluorescence using an Axioskop 2 plus microscope (Zeiss). Images were taken with a ProgRes C10 3.3 MegaPixel digital color camera (Jenoptik). Callose quantification was performed by ImageJ software. Experiments were repeated at least three times on different days to generate independent biological replicates.

qRT-PCR assays

After treatments, seedlings were frozen in liquid nitrogen and homogenized with a MM301 Ball Mill (Retsch). Total RNA was extracted from 3 independent replicates, each composed by 10 seedlings, with Isol-RNA Lysis Reagent (5 Prime) according to the manufacturer's protocol. Total RNA (1 µg) was treated with RQ1 DNase (Promega) and first-strand cDNA was synthesized using ImProm-II reverse transcriptase (Promega) according to the manufacturer's instructions. Quantitative RT-PCR analysis was performed by using a CFX96 Real-Time System (Bio-Rad). Single strand cDNA (corresponding to 50 ng of total RNA) was amplified in a 20-µl-reaction containing 1X GoTaq qPCR Master Mix (Promega) and 0.5 µM of each primer. Three technical replicates were performed for each sample and data analysis was done using LinRegPCR software. Expression levels of each gene, relative to *ubiquitin 5 (UBQ5)* or *peroxin 4 (PEX4)*, were determined using a modification of the Pfaffl method (Pfaffl, 2001), as previously described (Ferrari *et al.*, 2006). Primer sequences are shown in Table S2. Experiments were repeated at least three times on different days to generate independent biological replicates.

Supplemental data

Supplemental Table S1. Primers used for the construction of the *P_{OGOXL}::GUS* cassette.

Primer name	Primer sequence
<i>Bam</i> HI- <i>P_{OGOXL}</i> Fwd	CGCGGATCCGTTTGATTTTTTTTTTTTTTTTTTTTTC
<i>Bam</i> HI- <i>P_{OGOXL}</i> Rev	CGCGGATCCTGTTCTTTGTACTTATCCGTGT

Supplemental Table S2. List of primer sequences used for expression analyses.

Gene	AGI No	Forward primer (5'-3')	Reverse primer (5'-3')
<i>RETOX</i>	<i>At1g26380</i>	AGGTTCTCGAACCCCTAACCAACA	GCACAGACGACACGTAAGAAAG
<i>FRK1</i>	<i>At2g19190</i>	TTAAACTCGACGATGCAACA	GATGGAAGTTTTCCCGTTTT
<i>CYP81F2</i>	<i>At5g57220</i>	GTGAAAGCACTAGGCCGAAGC	ATCCGTTCCAGCTAGCATCA
<i>OGOXL</i>	<i>At4g20830</i>	GTCGCGACTGCGATTCCGAAGA	CAGGCAACAACATTCCTTC
<i>PDF1.1</i>	<i>At1g75830</i>	TCATGGCTAAGTTTGCTTCC	TGGCTCCTTCAAGGTTAATG
<i>PDF1.2</i>	<i>At5g44420</i>	CGCACCCGGCAATGGTGG	ATCCATGTTTGGCTCCTTCG
<i>PR4</i>	<i>At3g04720</i>	GTACCACCGCGGACTACTGT	CGTGGAGCAATAAGCACTCA
<i>ORA59</i>	<i>At1g06160</i>	GGCTCTCGCTTATGATCAGG	GGACGGTTTCTCATGGAGTG
<i>ERF1</i>	<i>At3g23240</i>	TCGGCGATTCTCAATTTTTTC	ACAACCGGAGAACAACCATC
<i>ERF5</i>	<i>At5g47230</i>	TCTTCGGATCATCGTCTCTTC	GGTTTGCATACGGATTCAGAGAA
<i>VSP2</i>	<i>At5g24770</i>	CGTGCACTAAAAACGAGTGG	TGAGGTGGGGTTATGAGAAA
<i>THI2.1</i>	<i>At1g72260</i>	GTGAGTGGATGCCAAAATC	TAGAACATCCCTTGGCACAT
<i>PEX4</i>	<i>At5g25760</i>	TCATAGCATTGATGGCTCATCCT	ACCCTCTCACATCACCAGATCTTAG
<i>UBQ5</i>	<i>At3g62250</i>	GTAAAGCTCGCTGTTCTTCAGT	TCAAGCTTCAACTCCTTCTTTC
<i>PR1</i>	<i>At2g14610</i>	GTAGGTGCTCTTGTTCTTCCC	CACATAATCCCACGAGGATC
<i>β-tubulin</i>	-	TTCCATGAAGGAGGTTGAGG	TACCAACGAAGGTGGAGGAC

Figure S1. Characterization of the *OGOX1* mutant/transgenic plants. **A.** The transgene in the *P_{OGOX1}::GUS* plants was analyzed by PCR in wild-type (Col-0) and indicated transgenic lines, using *P_{OGOX1}* and *GUS* specific primers and genomic DNA as a template. **B.** The *OGOX1* transcript levels were analyzed by qRT-PCR in Col-0, amiR-*OGOX1* lines pretreated with DMSO or β -estradiol, and in *ogox1* (top chart), or in Col-0 and OGOX1-OE lines (bottom chart). Transcript levels are shown as the mean of at least three independent experiments (\pm SE; n = 4 in each experiment) normalized to *UBQ5* expression.

Figure S2. Basal resistance to *B. cinerea*, OG-triggered ROS and callose production, as well as wound-induced H₂O₂ production, are not affected in the amiR-OGOX1 lines pretreated with DMSO. **A.** Total ROS production, expressed in relative light units (RLUs), was measured in leaf discs of wild type (Col-0), and DMSO-(D)-pretreated amiR-OGOX1 lines during elicitation with water or OGs (250 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) for 40 min. Results are average \pm SE (n = 12). **B.** Callose deposition visualized by aniline blue staining in leaves of Col-0, and DMSO-(D)-pretreated amiR-OGOX1 lines 24 h after syringe-infiltration with water or OGs (50 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$). Results are average \pm SE (n = 12). **C.** Four-weeks-old plants of indicated genotypes were wounded with a laboratory forceps and, after 1 h, wounded leaves (w) were excised at the base of the stems and supplied with DAB for 12 h. As control, leaves from unwounded plants (u) were included in the analysis. At least nine leaves from three independent plants were used for each genotype. Letter D indicates DMSO pretreatment. **D.** Col-0 and DMSO (D)-pretreated amiR-OGOX1 lines were inoculated with *B. cinerea* (5×10^5 conidiospores mL^{-1}) and lesion size was measured after 48 h. Bars indicate average lesion area \pm SE of at least two independent experiments (n = 18, in each experiment). In A, B, C and D, experiments were repeated three times with similar results.

Figure S3. The OG-induced expression of *FRK1* is not affected in all *OGOX1* mutant/transgenic plants. Expression of the indicated defense gene was analyzed by qRT-PCR in seedlings of Col-0, *OGOX1*-OE, *ogox1* and β -estradiol-(β)-pretreated amiR-*OGOX1* after treatment with OGs ($50 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) at the indicated time points. Transcripts levels are shown as the mean of at least three independent experiments (\pm SE; $n = 20$ in each experiment) normalized to *UBQ5* expression. Similar results were obtained in *OGOX1*-OE #11.8 and amiR-*OGOX1* #3.4 (data not shown). Experiments were repeated three times with similar results.

Figure S4. Analysis of gene expression in response to jasmonate, ethylene or both. Expression of the indicated hormone-responsive genes, analyzed in 10-days-old wild-type (Col-0) seedlings treated for 8 hours with mock (NaPO₄ + DMSO), methyl jasmonate (MeJA), ethephon (Et) or both (Et+MeJA). Analyses were performed by qRT-PCR and transcript levels are shown as the mean of at least three independent experiments (\pm SE; n = 20 in each experiment) normalized to *PEX4* expression and plotted relative to expression in the mock-treated sample. Statistically significant differences between treatments are indicated by letters, according to analysis of variance (ANOVA) with Tukey's honestly significant difference (HSD) test (P < 0.05).

8. CONCLUSIONS

Research over the last 30 years has led to an increasingly clear conceptual understanding of the molecular components of the plant immune system. During my PhD program I have identified some steps of the OG signal transduction pathway. I demonstrated the involvement of elements, including CDPKs, SERKs, EIN2, AGB1, PEPRs and OGOX1, and shown that there is overlap between PAMP and OG signaling cascades, at least for some responses (Gravino *et al.*, 2015; Gravino *et al.*, 2017)(this thesis). Indeed, on one hand CPK5/6/11, SERK3/4, EIN2, AGB1 and PEPR1/2 play a role in both OG and PAMP signaling even that, in some cases, with a differential requirement, on the other hand SERK2 seems to be specific of the OG signaling pathway (Roux *et al.*, 2011)(this thesis). Moreover, the comparison between the OG- and flg22-triggered immune responses in the mutant/transgenic plants reveals an unprecedented complexity among the MAMP/DAMP response cascades and suggests that OGs are sensed through multiple and partially redundant perception/transduction complexes (Gravino *et al.*, 2017). Interestingly, the loss of all these OG signaling elements, with the exception of SERK2 led to increased susceptibility against the necrotrophic fungus *B. cinerea* (Llorente *et al.*, 2005; Gravino *et al.*, 2015; Gravino *et al.*, 2017)(this thesis), indicating that they are key elements of the immune system against this fungus and that OG signaling plays an important role in these pathosystems. In addition to being required for the OG signaling and resistance to Botrytis, OGOX1 plays a role in response to wounding and in root development. Thus, the inactivation of OGs mediated by OGOXs (Benedetti *et al.* 2017, in publication) appears to be a mechanism involved in the trade-off between defense and development. Such a mechanism would suggest that OGOXs would in turn be subject to regulation. Indeed, it has been shown herein that *OGOX1* transcript regulation in response to OGs is dependent on SERK2 and the ethylene signaling mediated by EIN2. Interestingly, both of these elements have a role both in defense and development (Denancé *et al.*, 2013; Ma *et al.*, 2016)(this thesis). Moreover, it would be interesting to know whether OGOX1 is subject to regulation at the protein level. Whether OGOX1 plays a role in PAMP response (e.g. flg22) and resistance to other pathogens such as Pst and aphids remains to be investigated. Previously, other OG signaling elements have been identified in the lab, such as WAK1, GRP3, KAPP, RBOHD, MPKs, and ANPs. The next step is to understand if and how these elements can interact physically, as has been demonstrated for WAK1, GRP3, and KAPP (Park *et al.*, 2001; Anderson *et al.*, 2001), and if they are involved in the resistance against aphids, as has been demonstrated for GRP3 (see below).

In this thesis, I have identified some important elements that play a role in the plant defense response against the green peach aphid (GPA) *Myzus persicae*. These are a signaling element, also involved in the regulation of OG- and flg22-triggered immunity, i.e. GRP3 (Gramegna *et al.*, 2016), and structural elements involved in the regulation of the methylesterification degree (DM) of homogalacturonan, i.e. PME3, PME11 and PME12 (Lionetti *et al.*, 2007; Raiola *et al.*, 2011). Interestingly, while the loss of GRP3 led to enhanced resistance against both *B. cinerea* and GPA (Gramegna *et al.*, 2016)(this thesis), the loss of PME3 as well as the overexpression of PME11 or PME12 enhanced resistance against *B. cinerea* (Lionetti *et al.*, 2007; Raiola *et al.*, 2011) but increased susceptibility to GPA (this thesis), suggesting that enhancing resistance through the modulation of the DM of HG is unlikely to be an easy strategy as it appears to be pathogen specific. Furthermore, I showed that OGs protect Arabidopsis plants against GPA colonization and identified pathogen-derived effectors, i.e. AvrPto from Pst and Mp10 from GPA, which suppress the OG-triggered immunity (Gravino *et al.*, 2017)(this thesis), corroborating the vision that the OGs protect plants against bacteria and insects (Benedetti *et al.*, 2015)(this thesis). The next steps are to understand the mechanism by which these effectors suppress the OG responses and to shed light on the signaling pathway that regulates the OG-triggered protection against GPA.

An improved understanding of plant signaling pathways in response to a wide range of pathogens, such as fungi, bacteria and insects, will give the potential for engineering plants for

resistance against individual devastating diseases or multiple pathogens. Generating such crops is important given that pathogens and pests are largely controlled by pesticides that are environmentally damaging and are being taken off the market leaving farmers with limited options to protect their crops. For example, the overexpression of CDPK members has been shown to confer resistance to several pathogens both in monocot and dicot (Coca and Segundo, 2010; Kobayashi *et al.*, 2012; Asano *et al.*, 2012; Dubiella *et al.*, 2013). Likewise, Arabidopsis plants overexpressing AtPROPEP1 or AtPROPEP2 showed enhanced resistance to a root pathogen (Huffaker *et al.*, 2006; Huffaker and Ryan, 2007).

The firsts commercially available transgenic plant species were those with increased resistance towards viruses; recently, thanks to different practices involved in breeding for disease resistance, such as the identification and the editing within the host genome disease-resistance (R) genes, reduced pathogen growth and symptom development, also against fungi and bacteria. Another strategy is to transfer pattern recognition receptors (PRRs) and/or nucleotide binding site (NBS) leucine-rich repeat (LRR) receptors (NLRs) that detect common microbial structures and effectors into species that lack them (Dangl *et al.*, 2013). In contrast to PRRs and NLRs, another class of plant disease resistance genes has evolved to open a “trap door” that stops pathogen proliferation. Transcription activator-like (TAL) effectors are DNA-binding proteins delivered into plant cells, where they activate host gene expression to enhance pathogen virulence; in a neat evolutionary trick, however, both the rice and pepper lineages independently evolved TAL-effector binding sites in the promoters of genes whose products induce hypersensitive host cell death when up-regulated and thus inhibit pathogen proliferation (Dangl *et al.*, 2013).

Our current challenge is to define and to stack multiple resistance specificities active against the daunting array of economically important pathogens, including *Phytophthora*, *Magnaporthe*, *Fusarium*, *Botrytis*, *Pseudomonas*, *Ralstonia*, *Xanthomonas*, *Myzus*, gemini and potyviruses. At the same time, we must maintain complex agronomic traits - such as form, and flavor - and avoid yield penalties.

9. LIST OF PUBLICATIONS

1. **Gravino M.**, Locci F., Tundo S., Cervone F., Savatin D.V., De Lorenzo G. (2017). *Immune responses induced by oligogalacturonides are differentially affected by AvrPto and loss of BAK1/BKK1 and PEPR1/PEPR2*. *Molecular Plant Pathology* 18 (4), 582-595. (Number of citations: 6)
2. **Gravino M.**, Savatin D.V., Macone A., De Lorenzo G. (2015). *Ethylene production in Botrytis cinerea- and oligogalacturonide-induced immunity requires calcium-dependent protein kinases*. *The Plant Journal* 84 (6), 1073-1086. (Number of citations: 15)
3. Bisceglia N.G., **Gravino M.**, Savatin D.V. (2015). *Luminol-based assay for detection of immunity elicitor-induced hydrogen peroxide production in Arabidopsis thaliana leaves*. *Bio-protocol* 5 (24), e1685. (Number of citations: 4)
4. Savatin D.V., Bisceglia N.G., **Gravino M.**, Fabbri C., Pontiggia D., Mattei B. (2015). *Camalexin quantification in Arabidopsis thaliana leaves infected with Botrytis cinerea*. *Bio-protocol* 5 (2), e1379. (Number of citations: 2)

10. FUNDINGS AND COLLABORATIONS

1. **Avvio alla Ricerca 2016** (Fellowship, 2800 EUR)
Funding agency name: Sapienza University of Rome Duration: 19/07/2016 - 18/07/2017
(1 year)
2. Fellowship: **EMBO short-term fellowship** (7500 EUR)
Funding agency name: European Molecular Biology Organization (EMBO)
Duration: 10/01/2017 - 09/04/2017 (3 months)
3. Proposal in revision: **H2020-MSCA-IF-2017**
Host supervisor: Prof. Saskia Hogenhout (JIC)
Submitted on: 14/09/2017
Duration: 2 years

In the course of doctoral program, I collaborated with Prof. Saskia Hogenhout (John Innes Center, Dept. of Crop Genetics, Norwich, UK) working in her lab during the periods from 06/10/2016 to 23/12/2016 and from 10/01/2017 to 30/04/2017, carrying out the following research project: *Study of the role of plant cell wall and cell-wall-derived oligogalacturonides in defense against aphids.*

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